

**EFFECTS OF RESERVATION POLICY FOR THE
INCLUSIVE CIVIL SERVICE OF NEPAL**

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DEDICATED TO...

MY LATE FATHER MOHAN SINGH BHUL

WHO IS MY ENTIRE SPIRIT OF INSPIRATION AND PROVIDED ME
THE LIFELINE OF COURAGE AND DEVOTION FOR DIGNITY

WE MISS YOU!!!

DECLARATION OF AUTHORSHIP

I, hereby, declare that this thesis entitled "**Effects of Reservation Policy for the Inclusive Civil Service of Nepal**" submitted to Central Department of Public Administration, Faculty of Management, Tribhuvan University, has been completed as per the prescribed format of Tribhuvan University. This thesis comprises only my original work and no part of this work has been used for the award for another course or degree and this is my own work done for the partial fulfillment of the requirement of the degree of Master of Philosophy in Public Administration under the guidance and supervision of Dr. Buddhiman Shrestha. I have identified and properly acknowledged all the resource material and information used in this research work as needed. Further, I shall have no objection over the use of my research work in any form for the academic and research purpose.

.....

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RECOMMENDATION

Master of Philosophy (M.Phil.) in Public Administration Program

This is to certify that the Thesis

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“Effects of Reservation Policy for the Inclusive Civil Service of Nepal”

has been prepared as approved by this program in this prescribed format of the Central Department of Public Administration, Faculty of Management, Tribhuvan University. This thesis is candidate's original work and I have carefully read this work and fully satisfied with this thesis. I, therefore recommend this thesis be considered for the award of M.Phil. Degree. This thesis is forwarded for examination.

.....

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ABSTRACT

This research study aims to carry out the perceptual effects of reservation policy for the inclusive civil service of Nepal with the theoretical foundation of equitable and a just society. The access of opportunities is to be provided to every individual and group because the unequal and biased approach of the opportunity obviously leads to a development in a diversified society which causes inequality and injustice. People feel justice when they get equal access to power, resource and opportunity created by the state. In order to increase this access, reservation is one of the tools of social inclusion which has been recently introduced in Nepal. The main motive behind the policy was to increase participation and expand capacities of the marginalized communities as well as women in the civil services. Based on these facts, the dependent variable of the study is reservation policy and independent variables are representativeness, participation, perception and performance ownership, recognition, empowerment and integration of the marginalized people in the civil services.

Therefore, reservation or the affirmative action has been regarded one of the tool to increase the participation of underrepresented groups and communities in public services. However, many scholars believe that this system needs proper handling as it may destroy merit based system in civil service. In case of Nepal, the merit based bureaucratic system of the past somehow failed to proportionately recruit people from different marginalized communities and social imbalance was created in the society from having access to opportunities. Similarly, the absence of respectable and dynamic representation in nation building activities prevented equal benefit sharing of governance and nation's development. This is why Civil Service Act, 2049 of Nepal introduced reservation system in 2064 into government employments. Twelve years of period is sufficient to evaluate the effects of the policy and impacts created needs to be assessed this policy towards its goal. This newly introduced system has been able to give some positive impacts in terms of increasing representation of some marginalized communities but has created some controversies and confusions as well. If reservation is not categorized properly as a tool of inclusion, it may continue to be under the domination of a limited elite group even within the excluded groups.

This study adopted mixed method having both qualitative and quantitative approach. For gathering primary data, a questionnaire survey was carried out to Office of the Auditor

General (OAG), Nepal and Public Service Commission (PSC) Nepal. Similarly, other methods of primary data collection include non-participatory observations, and the participatory interviewed methods. In order to show the linkage between primary and secondary data, content analysis was conducted from the observational notes, field notes, and responses collected by open-ended as well as closed ended questionnaire. For questionnaire survey, total number of respondents were 130 (including 6 key respondents were interviewed). In this study the purposive and quota sampling is used and the researcher has set the questionnaire in statement form of the study. A 4(four) point Likert scale was used to apply value for the categorical data and further this scale was again recoded into two scales for the further analysis. IBM SPSS 25 version was used to gather frequency, percentage, and cross tabulation of the survey. Along with it, the bivariate analysis was done to show the linkage between dependent variable and independent variable.

The bivariate analysis between dependent variable and independent variable shows the effects of gender, age and education matters in inclusiveness of civil service i.e. there is high relationship between these variables. Individual effects of reservation for the inclusiveness shows that there is highly significant relationship between the individual participation and individual performance with the inclusiveness of civil service whereas organizational effects of reservation system shows highly significant relationship between the representativeness and participation in civil service of Nepal. Along with it other variable of individual effects like attraction, recognition, level of confidence, educational achievement, motivation into the civil service, and so on shows high significant relations with the inclusiveness and these factors definitely plays very crucial role in the achievement of the individual desired targets. Along with it, strong relationship with inclusiveness of civil service shows that it differ slightly between the two variable. Therefore, we can conclude that there is less significant relationship between the organizational effects in inclusiveness rather than individual effects into the civil service of Nepal.

Therefore, ultimate objective of this policy is capability enhancement, as said by Sen (2000), so more considerations are needed in building meaningful participation. Nepalese reservation system has not still given comprehensive attention to all the dimensions of exclusion but its effects on generating attraction of some targeted marginalized people towards national bureaucratic system is literally praiseworthy.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AD	:	Anno Domini
ADB	:	Asian Development Bank
BS	:	Bikram Sambat
CBS	:	Central Bureau of Statistics
CESI	:	Centre for Economic and Social Inclusion
CPA	:	Comprehensive Peace Accord
DFID	:	Department for International Development
DoCPR	:	Department of Civil Servants Personnel Records
GSEA	:	Gender and Social Exclusion Assessment
ILO	:	International Labour Organization
INGO	:	International Non-Government Organization
NEFIN	:	Nepal Federation of Indigenous Nationalities
NGO	:	Non-Government Organization
NHDR	:	Nepal Human Development Report
NPC	:	National Planning Commission
NPR	:	National Population Report
MoFAGA	:	Ministry of Federal Affairs and General Administration
OAG	:	Office of the Auditor General
OBC	:	Other Backward Community
PBI	:	Performance Based Incentive
PR	:	Proportional Representation
PREPARE	:	Project to Prepare Public Administration for State Reforms
PRSP	:	Poverty Reduction Strategy Paper
PSC	:	Public Service Commission
SAARC	:	South Asian Association for Regional Cooperation
SPSS	:	Statistical Package for Social Sciences
SWOT	:	Strength Weakness Opportunities and Threats
UNDP	:	United Nations Development Programme
WB	:	World Bank

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

This is the first chapter, it summarizes the contents and discloses brief picture of the overall thesis. The introduction chapter includes background of the study, statement of the problem, objective of the study, significance of the study, limitation of the study and organization of the study.

1.1 Background of the Study

According to the World Bank Report (2018), the aim of affirmative action or reservation policy is to correct historical disadvantages and unfair discrimination by enabling access to full opportunity and benefits to groups that have been excluded'. Affirmative action provides disadvantaged groups with access to education, formal employment and political participation, often based on quotas. The history of affirmative action or reservation system in Nepal shows back to the date of 1995 on which date the government categorized oppressed class and allocated some budget. The main reason of having reservation system was social exclusion in Nepal which has been traced back to the 14th century where King Jayashiti Malla introduced 64 vertical occupational caste groups among the Newar community. Then the act of discrimination had been started from the beginning of Muluki Ain of Nepal (1910 B.S.) which had been created enough discriminations over minority groups in the whole Nepalese society. Then the 'Democratic Movement II'¹ of April 2006 has been historic not only for defeating King Shah regime and declaring Nepal a Federal Democratic Republic by the first meeting of the Constituent Assembly on 28 May 2008, but also as a foundation for several inclusive policies. In the construction of an inclusive nation, affirmative action is one frequently debated issue among citizens, academics, political leaders, government officials, and activists alike. To create an inclusive civil service, the government announced the reservation policy for women, Janajatis, and Dalits; however, it could not take the direction because of the government instability, and now this reservation policy is legislated by the interim constitution of Nepal in 2007 and

¹ **Democratic Movement II** is a name given to the political agitations against the direct and undemocratic rule of King *Gyanendra* of Nepal. The movement is also sometimes referred to as *Jana Andolan*- ("People's Movement-II"), implying it being a continuation of the 1990 *Janandolan I*.

provides quotas for various disadvantaged groups in civil service of Nepal. In Nepalese context, identification of minority groups (Bhattachan, 2009) are as follows:

- a) **Indigenous Nationalities:** There are sixty ethnicities namely Rai, Gurung, Tamang, Magar, Sherpa, Tharu, Newar, Chepang, Raute and so on. They are recognized by the Government of Nepal.
- b) **Dalits:** Government of Nepal has identified twenty-three Dalit castes, who are also minorities. Kami, Damai, Sarki, Paswan, Chyame, Pode, Musahar and so on are in Dalit category. They are treated as untouchable castes in traditional society.
- c) **Madhesis:** Madhesis are also in minorities. They have been treated as second class citizens from the side of state. During the Rana rule they were required to obtain visa to visit the Kathmandu valley.
- d) **Women:** women are also in minorities. All Nepalese women are victims of gender discrimination. But the nature, forms and degree differ among different castes, ethnics, religious and cultural groups.
- e) **Religious Groups:** Other minorities are religious groups. Hindu state had been discriminated among different religions such as Kirata, Buddhist and Christian as well.
- f) **Linguistic Minorities:** There are one hundred twenty-three linguistic groups, but they are in vertical relation and position with each other in the social structure of Nepal.
- g) **Regional Minorities:** Karnali and Far western regions are very poor and backward region, which are located in the mid-western and far-western region of Nepal. But other regions, which are is somehow more developed. This sort of regional disparity exists due to regional discrimination from the central government of Nepal.

The people's movement-II of 2006 A.D. has more strongly highlighted the issues of participation, empowerment and inclusion in politics and government mechanism. Civil service act 2049 has been guaranteed women, Adibasi/Janajati, Madhesi, Dalit, disability and remote area's representation in every state structure. In this context, it is required to give voice, genuine space, dignity and respect to Nepali society for solidarity making of civil service of Nepal It is necessary that for inclusive and equal representation of minorities, all has been working towards movement building and promoting equal rights in Nepal.

In this scenario, National Federation of Indigenous Nationalities demanded the state for the reservations to remove inequality, discrimination and exclusion from Nepalese society, egalitarian, equity and reservation are essential things. It is evident that the brighter sight of the government are reforms and progressive performances into inclusion. Government has been trying to reform existing structure of minorities in different forms of action. For example, we can take formation of National Nationalities Development Committee-2054 B.S.; Dalit Bikas Samittee-2054 B.S.; Aadibasi Janjati Rastriya Utthan Pratisthan-2059; Nepal Women’s Commission-2059; Nepal Dalit Commission-2059; Suggestion Committee for Reservation-2060; and Declaration of Reservation Policy-2061; National Inclusion Commission-2074; Madhesi Commission-2074; Muslim Commission-2074. Except these, some practices of reservation in multisector as a quota in percentage are being practiced in Nepali educational institutions, security forces, public service commission and another employment, which we should take as affirmative action for minorities. Not only these, but in politics too there are efforts to practice the proportional representation model. These steps for minority groups to access the positive role are to mainstream for modeling the nation towards the path of sustainable development. Nowadays, the case of minorities is highlighted in Nepalese politics. The term 'minorities' have been used in different sense. Mostly, it is used for the backward and undeveloped human beings, who have not access in social, economic and political activities of ruling process.

Table 1
Major Caste/Ethnic Groups Population in Nepal

Caste/Ethnicity	Population	Percentage
Chhetri	4,398,179	16.6 %
Bramhin Hill	3,226,903	12.2 %
Magar	1,887,733	7.1 %
Tharu	1,737,470	6.6 %
Tamang	1,539,830	5.8 %
Newar	1,321,933	5.0 %
Kami	1,258,554	4.8 %
Muslim	1,164,255	4.4 %
Yadav	1,054,458	4.0 %
Rai	620,004	2.3 %

(Source: Population and Housing Census, 2011)

The Bramhin and Chhetris are regarded as higher class in the Hindu caste system. They Caste/Ethnicity Population: Percentage: Chhetri 4,398,179 (16.6%) Bramhin Hill 3,226,903 (12.2%), Magar 1,887,733 (7.1%), Tharu 1,737,470 (6.6%), Tamang 1,539,830 (5.8%), Newar 1,321,933 (5.0%), Kami 1,258,554 (4.8%), Muslim 1,164,255 (4.4%), Yadav 1,054,458 (4.0%), Rai 620,004 (2.3%), overall consist of 28.8 percent of the population. The total Indigenous Nationalities includes more than 40 percent of population. The Nepal Federation of Indigenous Nationalities has currently classified the 60 indigenous groups into five categories based on a set of socioeconomic indicators: 'endangered', 'highly marginalized', 'marginalized', 'disadvantaged' and 'advantaged'. At the bottom of the scale are the so-called endangered and highly marginalized groups. These groups rank very low on human development indicators. More than 90% of endangered and highly marginalized groups live in remote rural areas and rely on subsistence agriculture or hunting and gathering. The Thakalis and Newar caste belong to the advantaged category. On the other side, Dalit consist 13 percent of the population. Dalit are untouchable groups under Hindu caste system. By religion, Hindus dominates the country with 81.3 percent of the total population. Moreover, 1.94 percent of total population is disabled and has a kind of or multiple type of disability on literacy side, the total literacy rate 2018 is 67.91 percent. However, 59.72 percent of women are only literate while in male population the percent of literacy is 78.59 percent. This figure also show that women of Nepal are far behind male in terms of education.

However, the system of representation varies across the world whereas some countries, quota for women appeared in politics as early as in the 1930s. However, few countries adopted systematic gender quotas in politics (Krook, 2010). The UN Economic and Social Council decided to reach the target of 30 percent female representation in decision making bodies by 1995 (UN Women, 2016). In some OECD countries, about 50 percent of civil service position was occupied by female in 1997. In France, it was 55.9 percent in 1996 and in Australia and Canada it was 49.2 percent and 49.5 percent respectively in 1997. In United Kingdom, it was 49.1 percent and in the United States 44 percent in 1996 (OECD, 2008). In Korea it was 28.7 percent in 1997 (Kim, 2008) and 40.8 percent in 2008 (Kim 2011). In some none OECD countries, in Bangladesh it was 10 percent in 2002 (Foley & Chowdhury, 2007). In Nepal, one of the prominent steps in 2007 was, the government took several policy actions to increase the

representation of women and excluded groups in political institutions and in the civil service. There is a need to introduce and implement the concept of "affirmative action" to turn welfare state and to achieve the objective of socio-economic justice and mainstreaming by the government.

Inclusion as equity was presented, then, as a new space of politics, possibilities, and opportunity perhaps to create a democratic or even revolutionary world which offered the chance for disability and equality to be located within a new socio-cultural framework. Nepal is one of the most diverse countries in terms of ethnic, culture, religion and languages. The problems/issues regarding these excluded groups have been identified as: poverty, marginalization from mainstreaming development, discrimination, under-representation in politics and bureaucracy and lack of competent power. The recent census of 2011 has categorized 125 castes as well as ethnic communities in Nepal out of 26.5 million populations. Though Nepali speaking people count 44.6 percent of the total population, over 123 identified languages are spoken in Nepal and 10 types of religion are practiced. There are 21 percent of the population (NPR, 2018) living below the poverty line. Social exclusion is known to be one of the main problems in this country. The process of exclusion has been identified to be mainly based on Hindu caste system, socio-cultural stratification and patriarchal system of the society. There is no single set of indicators of socially excluded groups till now. The poor range over a wide variety of social groups irrespective of caste, religion and geographic regions. Women cut across all categories irrespective of caste, ethnicity, individuals with disabilities, or children. Six categories, based on sex, caste, ethnicity, region, religion and physical condition, have been listed as excluded groups. (GSEA, 2006).

In order to increase participation in civil service, government introduced reservation system, with second amendment of Civil Service Act, for women, Ethnic groups (Adibasi), Madhesi, Dalit, disabled, and the people belonging to remote areas. Moreover, political and bureaucratic representation of these marginalized communities has been very low as compared to their proportion in population. Reservation is intended to increase the social diversity in work places by lowering the entry criteria for certain identifiable groups that are grossly under representative in proportional to their number in general population.

1.2 Statement of Problem

Different status leads to social exclusion which is one of the oldest problem in our societies. Social exclusion practiced to limit people's opportunities to participate freely and fully in the community, stumbling the system to achieve the set objectives. It is socio-psychologically painful as well since the class and caste was originated in the society. Its negative effects on society can weaken our nation solidarity and overall national systems. Another aspect is that it is against global concept of human right and natural freedom. Due to many conventions against discrimination at the global level, the issue of exclusion has not remained mere domestic issue in any country. The solution to social exclusion may be different in different context. Basically it depends on the type of behavioral exclusion which exists in the society. As the concept of social exclusion has been used in very different ways in different countries have tried to solve and eradicate those social issues in their own way (Sen, 2000).

Reservation or Affirmative action is one of the tools of inclusion which is mainly focused on increasing participation through employment, of marginalized people in government and related services as well as in education system of the country. However, these efforts are commonly known as inclusive measures. Reversing the process of exclusion needs mainstreaming the marginalized communities and provide them rightful sharing in power, resource and opportunity (Korten, 2011). There may be many kinds of tools for social inclusion; positive discrimination, end of discrimination, equality, social security, and reservation. However, these inclusive measures are not free of controversies. Many scholars believe that social inclusion policies especially reservation policies further increase the discrimination in our society and it is against the principle of equal treatment by a state as well (Pojman, 2010).

Nepal remained under feudal and authoritarian regime for more than 200 years and the foundation for the rule was mostly Hindu system. Nepal is a multifaceted country regarding social structure which involves multi-ethnic, multi-religious and multi-linguistic societies. There are several caste/ethnic groups speaking their indigenous languages living in different parts of Terai, hill and mountains in this country. The facts given above clearly point out that several communities of Nepal have been excluded from the mainstream. The facts given above clearly point out that several communities of Nepal have been excluded from the mainstream. Not only direct or indirect

discrimination but deficiency and under-representation in governance system have also been some common problems they are facing. It is responsibility of a state to correct this undesirable situation as soon as possible. Bhattachan (2009) blames practice of Hindu caste system and discriminatory laws practiced by feudal rulers as the main culprit. As the mechanism for the governance was based on Hindu system in Nepal, caste system also reflected in the domestic laws. Not only direct or indirect discrimination but poverty and under-representation in governance system have also been some common problems they are facing. It is responsibility of a state to correct this undesirable situation as soon as possible.

Moreover, with the spirit of the constitutional provision of making the civil service inclusive, the second amendment in 2064 BS was made to the Civil Service Act 2049 stating in the sub clause (11) of the Act, there is the clause that the provisions for the fulfillment of posts through the percent determined pursuant to sub-section (7) in order to make inclusive civil service, forty-five percent posts of the posts to be fulfilled by open competition shall be set apart and be filled up by having separate competition between the following candidates only, by considering the percentage into cent percent, Women (33%), Adibasi/janjati (27%), Madhesi (22%), Dalit (9%), persons with Disability (5%) and candidates from Backward areas (4%). This measure, made to encourage Women, Adibasi/Janjati, Madhesi, Dalit, Disabled and Backward area to join the civil service. Sub-section (7) shall be reviewed in every ten years. And the ten years of implementation of the reservation policy has already been completed in 2074/75 F/Y. After almost twelve years' implementation of the reservation policy in Nepalese civil service, there has been various changes made in civil service system. The organizational changes and individual perception are made during the execution which are the major effects of reservation policy implementation in civil service of Nepal. The main focus of the problem is concerned with the outcomes after implementation of reservation policy which are both negative and positive side of the reservation policy in Nepal. The impact of reservation policy in the recruitment of civil servants shows that there is a significant increase in the percentage of the marginalized groups within the incorporation of such policy by the government. However, it is not possible to change a whole structure overnight; so, this initiative taken by the government has brought some positive impact in making a bureaucracy somehow representation of people from different socio-economic status. Considering these

reasons, it is the right time to study the effects of the reservation policy implementation status in civil service of Nepal.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

As we know that the history of Nepalese civil service was so not so long and failed to become a guardian of all citizens, commanded by the majority of very small controlling group of society. In this regards, the second amendment (2064 BS) to the Civil Service Act, 2049 was made as a result of second revolution of 2062/063 to make the civil service of Nepal more inclusive and more representative according the nature of Nepalese primitive society. The major research objective of the study is to assess the various effects of the reservation policy in the process of transformation of civil service of Nepal. Specifically, this research execution is supporting the main research objective areas which are as follows:

- a) To analyze the representative outcomes of reservation system after twelve years of implementation by the executing organizations of civil service of Nepal;
- b) To examine the perceptual effects of reservation system in the civil service;
- c) To recognize the factors effecting reservation system in Civil Service of Nepal.

1.4 Research Question of the Study

In a scientific research work, the intention of a researcher is expressed in the form of research questions. The research questions, thus, capture the main purpose and motive of the researcher (Wolf and Pant, 2007, p.77). A researcher can narrow down the objectives of the study into specific research questions to be answered during the investigation (Creswell, 2003, p.105). Nepal is constitutionally promoting the unity amongst diversity, socio-cultural solidarity, tolerance and harmony by internalizing the characteristics with multiethnic, multilingual, multi-religious, multicultural and geographical diversities, and to ensure economic equality, prosperity and social justice by ending class-based, ethnic, regional, lingual, religious, and gender-based and all forms of caste-based untouchability. On this ground, the main questions of my research topic for the study deals with following problems;

- What were the major objectives of reservation policy undertaken since 2064 BS to uplift disadvantaged sections of society with the concept of equity for the inclusive civil service according to our society?

- What is the current status of back-warded employees in comparison with other employees in civil service of Nepal after twelve years of implementation and how they are performing their public responsibility with the bureaucratic system?
- What is the perception level of Civil Servants towards inclusiveness and its impact on their attitudes or behavioral changes?
- What are the major effects of reservation policy to equally mainstream and participate the women and disadvantaged people in the all level of civil service of Nepal?

1.5 Hypothesis

Hypothesis is a statement about the relationship between two or more variables which needs to be investigated for its verification. Researcher through hypothesis is able to obtain reliable information on the relationship between and among variables in creating certain problem or situation in the social phenomena (Wolf and Pant, 2007, p.78). Setting hypothesis in a social science research is useful to narrow down the objective of the study through which relationship between dependent and independent variables can be explained and analyzed (Creswell, 2003, p.116). During an investigation based on hypothesis, if the relationship between two or more variables acts as per the prediction then the set hypothesis can be proved and a new theory can be generated in that field of study. On the ground of above mentioned meaning of setting hypothesis and its usefulness, the following hypotheses have been set to pursue the study further;

- A. Higher the representation of disadvantaged people, the higher is the recognition for quality performance in the civil service through the reservation policy in Nepal.
- B. Higher the participation of deprived section of society, the higher is the ownership over the governmental activities and operation of public bureaucracy in Nepal.
- C. Higher the positive perception towards employees from the reservation system, the higher is the individual motivation and trustworthiness in the civil service of Nepal.
- D. Higher the effective performance monitoring of reserved civil servants, the higher is the positive outcomes and implementation impact of reservation system in Nepal.

1.6 Significance of the Study

This study mainly focuses on the public policy implementation in a developing country like Nepal whereas few researches which have contributed to public policy

implementation like this. With this respect, Saetern (2005, p. 571) makes the picture clear as regards the overall regional bias of implementation research. Nepal is still struggling with the legacy and hegemony of Hinduism and caste system over the other tribe people from very long time. It is a system irony in our public service that males occupy most top level administrative and managerial positions. The study aims at providing updated information on the successes and challenges of implementing reservation system in the public service, hence, this data will be used by university students in their area of study. The study will enhance researchers' knowledge and understanding on the determination of the reservation system and its effect on the public sector in Nepal. This study will assist the government to re-plan, program and implement inclusion policies that are geared towards management of social diversity, poverty alleviation and human resource development according to the nature of Nepalese society. This study also aims to educate members of the public the difference between the concept of representative bureaucracy and reservation system. The study report and findings will be a strong tool to advocate and entrance for participation and representation in in the civil service of Nepal. The present study has special significance because of its usefulness for the political parties, government, community and other stakeholder organizations to formulate and implement reservation policy, programs and movements for raising participation & representation.

1.7 Limitation of the Study

The reservation system is taken as vague area of coverage but this thesis is concerned with the effects and implementation mechanism of reservation policy of Nepal and its participation in gazetted level, non-gazetted level and floor level of Nepalese civil service. So the main limitation of this thesis are as follows;

- This thesis covers only the status of marginalized people in civil service of Nepal, it doesn't include the employees in public enterprises and private sector in Nepal;
- The focus of study is made only in civil servants selected from reserved quota from open competition conducted by Public Service Commission of Nepal;
- This thesis is only including employees selected from reservation provisions since 2065 to 2077 in the in the civil service of Nepal;
- This thesis is only concerned with the Perceptual effects of reservation system into the civil service of Nepal.

1.8 Organization of the Study

The study has been divided into five chapters: introduction, literature review, research methodology, data presentation and analysis, and summary, findings and conclusion.

Chapter One - Introduction

The introduction chapter deals with background of the study, statement of the problem, objective of the study, significance of the study, key concepts, limitation of the study and organization of the study.

Chapter Two - Literature Review and Theoretical Framework

This chapter is a review of the related literature to policy implementation, social exclusion, legal provisions and inclusion theories regarding the implementation of reservation system in international context, principles of Nepalese civil service and conceptual framework.

Chapter Three - Research Methodology

This chapter explains research paradigm, research design, nature and sources of data, population and sample, data collection procedures, analysis of data, validity and reliability and ethical consideration for this study.

Chapter Four - Data and Information Presentation and Analysis

This fourth chapter deals with the data analysis and presentation. This chapter attempts to analyze and present the collected data through primary and secondary sources for study.

Chapter Five - Summary, Major Finding and Conclusions

This chapter provides summary of the major findings and conclusions of the study. Besides these, the study contains references and appendix at the end of the research work.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW AND THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Literature review is an evaluative report of information found in the literature related to the selected area of the study. The review should be describing, evaluate, summarize and clarify this literature. It should give a theoretical base for the research and help to determine the nature of the research. The literature review is concerned with regarding effects of the inclusion, positive discrimination, reservation policy for weaker section of the society in terms of gender, in terms of discrimination, in terms of poverty, in terms of backwardness, in terms of disability and so on.

2.1 Overview of Public Policy

Public policy can be generally defined as a system of laws, regulatory measures, courses of action, and funding priorities concerning a given topic promulgated by a governmental entity or its representatives. A policy often comes in the form of general statements about priorities, written regulations or guidelines, procedures and/or standards to be achieved. At its simplest, policy refers to a distinct path of action which is suitable for the pursuit of desired goals within a particular context, directing the decision making of an organization or individual. Policies are thus actions which contain goals and the means to achieve them, however well or poorly identified, justified, articulated and formulated. Probably the best-known, simple and short definition of public policy has been offered by Thomas Dye, 'anything a government chooses to do or not to do' (Dye, 1972: p.23). While many organizations and actors create policies to which their members must adhere, we focus on 'public' policies made by governments that affect and influence every member of a nation or a subnational jurisdiction of country. It is through the public policy-making process that governments establish the framework within which all citizens' human and corporate must function. The interpretative approach to policy implementation departs from a different ontological stance than the theoretical contributions. It considers the distinction between facts and values underlying the positivist philosophy of science as unsustainable, and it challenges the possibility of neutral and unbiased observations.

2.2 Policy Implementation: Organizational Culture

At the global level, the discussions have been dominated by first and second generation studies on policy implementation. First generation study of policy implementation involved a period of academic debate about the meaning of implementation (Hill & Hume, 2014). Second generation studies are broadly classified into top-down (administrative) and bottom-up (participatory) approaches of policy implementation (Stewart et al., 2008). Bottom-up theorists emphasize target groups and service providers, arguing that policy really is made at the local level. Studies about public policy by various scholars are implicit on the importance of governance in public policy implementation. Reforms that seek to disconnect policy implementation from political matters may face a more difficult task than had been thought (Hicks, 2014). While theory building was not at the heart of the first generation of implementation studies, the second generation began to put forward a whole range of theoretical frameworks and hypotheses. The third generation of implementation research tried to bridge the gap between top-down and bottom-up approaches by incorporating the insights of both camps into their theoretical models. At the same time, the self-proclaimed goal of third-generation research was “to be more scientific than the previous two in its approach to the study of implementation” (Goggin et al. 1990, 18, emphasis in original). Europe was also the origin of a new strand of literature that focused on the issue of implementation in the context of European integration studies.

Van Meter and Van Horn (1975, p.471), in their framework of policy implementation, have explained the dispositions of implementers and its effect in achieving set standards and objectives of policies. The disposition is about the perception of policy implementers that may affect the application of public policies. Therefore, disposition and commitment of policy implementers can be explained as one of the broader parts of administrative culture. The theories of administrative culture are about the perception and behavior of administrative actors in the organizational operations. Therefore, Van Meter and Van Horn might not deal with the issue of disposition of policy implementers within the broader framework of administrative culture in their study. Hofstadter's study on “Cultures and Organizations” in 1991 has given the message that societal and organizational culture are essential to be considered in the policy process and we can explain the disposition of policy implementers as an associated part of organizational culture. The study found that the commitment of administrative actors has an influence

on the application of reservation system in the civil service. The word commitment is also related to ownership in order to accomplish assigned tasks. Commitment is also associated with the outlook of policy implementers. Disposition is about attitude and perception of administrative actors towards implementing public policies in their organizations. Theoretical literature on policy implementation pronounces that there is a relationship between disposition of policy implementers and effectiveness of policy implementation as argued by Van Meter and Van Horn (1975, p.472). Implementers' responses on the proposed policy may reflect their willingness to carry out public policies. Policy implementers' cognition, their direction, and intensity of responses have an effect on the policy implementation and policy performance.

Administrative actors also link their positive and negative character towards the inclusion in civil service. If they see the proposed reservation policy serves their interest, they may hold positive character and would highly be committed for the implementation of reservation policy. Adversely, if they do not see the inclusion agenda in favor of their interest, they may develop negative nature to implement the reservation policy and consequently their commitment and effectiveness will be low. The study found that in the case of affirmative action in the organizations. The reason was that the proposed performance incentive package was set for the field level employees. Therefore, bureaucrats at the center might not have been interested to apply performance based incentive policy effectively. Employees at the center i.e. ministries and departments could have lost their interest to implement and monitor performance improvement plan in the field level organizations. In sum, the study found that the commitment with positive disposition of bureaucratic actors working at different levels of organization have a great influence for bringing changes and making reform programs effective.

2.3 History of the Social Exclusion

The concept of social inclusion figured prominently in the policy discourse in France in the mid-1970s. The concept was later adopted by the European Union in the late 1980s as a key concept in social policy and in many instances replaced the concept of poverty. This concept which had first appeared in Europe as a response to the crisis of the welfare. However, it means all things to all people. The research carried out in

OECD² countries in (2014) revealed that even though quotas can increase female representation, they should serve as a transitional or correctional measure to reduce historical differences in representation. Quota effectiveness depends highly on the design of the quota and the country's electoral system. In the global context, the concept of social exclusion seems to have a very long history. However, "exclusion is as old as hills" (Oommen, 2010, p. 1). In fact, the term exclusion is found to be described even in the Vedic Period. The caste system has been also described in the Vedic texts. According to this, the exclusion through the emergence of caste system first took place from the sacrifice of the primordial man. According to the text described in the Vedic texts Brahmins were born from the mouth of the primordial man. Similarly, the Kshetriya's were born from the shoulders and those of Vaishya's and Shudras were born respectively from the thigh and the legs/feet. The hierarchy here is shown due to inequality from mouth to legs or feet, feet being the lowest part of the body (Omvedt, 2008).

Exclusion as a subject of debate was begun in France, Europe during 1960 and the concept of the social exclusion was originated there in the early 1970s, when a French administrator referred to a variety of socially stigmatized individuals as socially excluded: the mentally and physically handicapped, aged invalids, those who survived attempted suicides, children subjected to abuse, single parents, those who indulged in substance abuse, delinquent behavior or prostitution (Lenior 1974, as cited in Oomens, 2010). According to Silver (1994), the politicians, activists, officials, journalists and academicians made it vogue and ideological references to the poor as the excluded. However, the discourse of exclusion was unable to be widespread until the economic crisis (Silver, 1994). Beal and Piron (2005) say that it is a concept commonly used in development context following "The World Social Summit" in Copenhagen in 1995. A number of multilateral development agencies have adopted this concept of social exclusion as a multidimensional framework. It has served to broaden poverty analysis and focus attention on both the causes and impacts of social disadvantage (Beal & Piron, 2005). It was a response to the crises of the welfare state and the fear of social disintegration caused by the social and economic crisis. In recent days, the concept of

² The **Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD)** is an international organization of thirty-four countries. Member countries of OECD all have a democratic system of government. A country has a free economy, when its government does not control the economic activities of its citizens and companies.

social exclusion has been related in discourse about poverty, inequality and justice in the context of social and economic changes in the north (Kabeer, 2000).

According to Nepal National Report (2011), in the developmental scenario and inclusion debate of Nepal, there are four groups or communities to have fallen in the area of exclusion. They are women, indigenous nationalities, Madhesi people, and Dalits. Besides, the minorities, Muslims, disable, and the third sex people are also taken as excluded groups. However, in terms of poverty stand point; there can be other groups or people who can fall in the premise of exclusion (NPR, 2011). This argument shows that the caste hierarchy and state ideology were the main cause to the growth of the social inequality. This social inequality has caused social exclusion in Nepal keeping many castes and ethnic communities in the excluded state from socio-economic, political and several other opportunities. In spite of the official abolition of the caste based discrimination in 1963, the caste based practices seems to have continued till much longer period of time. Moreover, the feudalistic orientation of the society also may have helped perpetuate the exclusionary process. In today's date, the discrimination by caste is considered to be against the law and it is highly punishable. However, it has not been completely eradicated from Nepalese society. Even the constitution of Nepal 1990, The Interim Constitution of Nepal 2007 and constitution of Nepal 2015 have clearly stated that the social discrimination and untouchability are as legally highly punishable.

2.4 Evolution of Social Inclusion

The understanding of social inclusion will be stronger with the concept of exclusion because exclusion and inclusion are the two sides of the same coin (Francis, 1997). The meaning of inclusion is not complete without the meaning of exclusion. Indeed, the need for inclusion arises only if exclusion exists (Oommen, 2010). Therefore, exclusion and inclusion are relative terms. There exists “a sizeable grey area between social exclusion and social inclusion, and in the real world most people live most of their lives in this zone, moving closer to social exclusion and Social Inclusion at various points during their lifetime” (Figueiredo & Gore, 1997, p. 42). Therefore, I have explained the terms exclusion and inclusion side by side. Generally, Social Inclusion is chosen in preference to social exclusion and is often used as the opposite to social exclusion; and whenever there is a discussion of Social Inclusion, the related concept of social

exclusion always comes there for discussion (Bhandari, 2012). In this connection, I agree with the argument that no inclusion is necessary if there is absent of exclusion. This is also supported, in a way, by the definition given by O'Reilly (2005) as the language of inclusion and exclusion implies a binary logic, that one is either excluded or included in relation to some variable. The question of inclusion, therefore, is best conceptualized as a sort of sliding scale rather than a binary function, so that exclusion and inclusion are the extreme poles of a continuum relation of inclusion and exclusion (O'Reilly, 2005). Social exclusion is a multidimensional process of progressive social rupture, detaching groups and individuals from social relations and institutions and preventing them from full participation in the normal, normatively prescribed activities of the society in which they live (Silver, 1994).

Also, European Foundation explains the exclusion as the process through which individuals or groups are wholly or partially excluded from full participation in the society in which they live (European Foundation, 1995). Talking in the same line, a layman normally may think that it's obvious that opportunities must be accessible and available for everyone. Beresnevieiute (2003) believes to state the phenomenon of social exclusion is related to the scarcity of material and social opportunities and the lack of skills to participate in economic, social, political, and cultural life in an effective way and is related to alienation or estrangement from the main part of society. On the other hand, the term also covers the denial and non-realization of the civic, political, and social rights of citizenship. It can be treated as an expression of the unequal distribution of various rights (Appasamy, Guhan, & Hema, 1996; Magallanes, & Dominquez, 1997; Nayak, 1994).

Hence, it is a universal category that includes economic, political, cultural, religious, and social aspects and discusses multidimensional mechanisms that exclude individuals or groups from participation in social exchanges and rights for social integration (Klasen, 1998; Combes, 1998 & Andersen, 1999). An individual or a group in a society is said to be socially excluded when resided geographically but cannot participate in the normal activities in the society due to some reasons (Saith, 2001). Peoples are kept away from getting an opportunity to develop themselves due to the social processes and the social constructs prevailing in the society causing the peoples sideline from the development of all kind. In this context, Beal and Piron (2005) have contextualized

exclusion as a condition or outcome and as a process. As a condition or outcome, it is a state in which individuals or groups are unable to participate fully in their society and on the other hand as a process, it is a state which prevents individuals or groups from full participation in socio-economic and political life and from asserting their rights (Beal 18 & Piron, 2005).

2.5 Reservation Policy in Civil Service: Global Context

Protected seat or quota in politics, finance and employment for backward community is generally pronounced as reservation. It will be included in education, health, employment to the minorities. America, India, Malaysia, Japan, China, New Zealand, Sri Lanka and so on countries are practicing the reservation system (Tamang, 2073, B.S., p. 25). This concept believes that reservation ignores the equal competition and equal opportunity among the unequal. It decreases the degree of gap between haves and have not, rich and poor, advanced and backward. The Indian constitution provides for reservation of parliamentary seats for the scheduled caste and tribes in accordance with their proportion in the population whereas article: 331 limited this provision for twenty years, but it has extended every ten years. Nehru said that “I try to look upon the problem not only in the sense of religious minority, but also in the sense of helping backward groups in the country” (Jayal, 2002, p. 92).

In a society, Equity and egalitarian lead to reservation, which help to create equality. If goods are distributed equally among the unequal it creates injustice only. If inequality is existing with unequal distribution gives justice. So, need-based distribution of goods and opportunities is reservation and affirmative action (Chandhok, 2004, p. 134). Equality is not fully favorable for democracy if there is inequality. The democracy should be measured by the indicator of its output behind distribution. Each distribution should be targeted towards equal output. To remove existing inequality and ensure the enhancement among different capability, unequal distribution of goods, services and opportunity is justifiable. In this reference, we should understand reservation is essential thing to make a welfare society and state. If individuals of community are discriminated socially, politically and financially, they become backward. They cannot fight with another. To make them capable, extra opportunity is most needed, which gives an environment of equal competition among equals. It is professed that if persons

or communities were exploited, they must claim for compensation from the state. In this sense, reservation is a kind of compensation too (Chandhok, 2004, p. 136).

2.5.1 United States of America

Although the term "affirmative action" or reservation system was originated in the USA, the American experience is of less relevance to the Nepalese situation than those of some Asian and African countries. Far from being a tool of transformation, affirmative action in the USA was essentially designed to integrate minority groups, and later women, into the mainstream of American life. This is because affirmative action was essentially a conservative notion designed and driven by the ruling class for blacks who largely shared the same sets of socio-economic values with whites. It was never intended to be a tool of egalitarianism, let alone transformation (Maphai, 1993:6).

2.5.2 South Africa

Affirmative action in South Africa was necessitated by evidence of the racial and gender composition of employment of the type, where the management of about 455 South African firms was dominated by white males, accounting for 89 percent, while the remaining 11 percent was held by blacks, colored's or Indians. The reason why there was a need for government intervention is due to the fact that whites are the minorities accounting for only 11 percent of the total population, yet they dominate management positions in a large number of firms. (Msimang, 2000).

2.5.3 Malaysia

Malaysia is another good example of ethnic-based, albeit more successful affirmative action. These were the Malay who constituted close to 50% of the population at the time of independence in 1957. They were regarded as the victims of historical discrimination which Puthuchery described as consisting of structural constraints on Malay participation in the modern sectors of the economy rather than one of domination and exploitation of Malays by other groups. (Puthuchery, 1993). Affirmative action in Malaysia was part of the overall economic development. While members of the Malay middleclass were the main beneficiaries, the incidence of rural poverty also fell significantly from 68,3% of the population in 1970 to 46.10% in 1980 and to an estimated 21.80% in 1990 (Loc.cit.).

2.5.4 Canada

Certain seats are reserved for Aboriginal Indians (Canadian Tribes), women's and physical disabled people in Public sector and college. The allotments of seats vary from 6 percent to 45 percent in various departments and it further changes state by state. The tribal are prevented of their properties and tradition. Further they are given righteous in land, forest and other natural resources (Rai & Lievesley, 2013).

2.5.5 New Zealand

Reserves a proportion of its parliamentary seats for the representation of persons electing to register on seepage Maori roll. The number of seats depends upon the number of people on the roll - there are currently seven (Maori seats). New Zealand individuals of Maori or their Polynesian descent are often afforded preferential access to university courses, and scholarships (Rai & Lievesley, 2013).

2.5.6 Japan

Buramukins and Koreans are given first preference to government jobs and government suggest to have at least 5 percent of Buramukin and ethnic minorities to private companies which has more than 500 employees' further government provides low rate personal loans, free education to any school or college, and some relief in taxes. Marks for universities and all the government's position (including teachers) are determined by the entrance exam, which is extremely competitive at the top level. It is illegal to include se, ethnicity or other social settings (but not nationality) in criteria. Though, there are informal policies to provide employment and long term welfare (which is usually not available to general public) to Burakumin at municipality level (Rai & Lievesley, 2013).

2.5.7 China

Tribal and certain ethnic communities who consist 8% of total Chinese population are provided lower qualification requirements than majority in every public sector jobs and education institutions. While they are provided with scholarships and/or pay no tuition, and are granted a monthly stipend. Tribal and ethnic minorities are exempted from some central policies like Child policy and certain aid is given by deduction in taxes and region autonomous status (Rai & Lievesley, 2013).

State has been regarded to be a product of human action. State operates through the loyalty of the people so it has some obligations for its citizens. State belongs to all the people so it has to create such a conducive environment where every kind of citizens' right are secure and they can freely exercise their opportunities. People feel justice when they get equal access to power, resource and opportunity created by the state. Societies have been found to be fragmented over religion, gender, ethnicity, race, color and culture since long. This is why we cannot find a state where justice has been fully realized by each and every people. In order to overcome the situation, the notion of inclusiveness has been introduced. It tries to correct the historical wrongs made by state to some of its people. Reservation or Affirmative action is one of the tools of social inclusion which is mainly focused on increasing participation through employment, of marginalized people in government and related services as well as in education system of the country. Beside this, developing their competitive capacity and empowerment is another intention. However, this concept of positive discrimination is not free of controversy and criticism. Many liberal scholars believe that reservation affects the merit based selection in civil service (Chalam, 1990).

Furthermore, it helps in preserving the discrimination because state itself, through reservation, recognize people with separate status. Many countries have implemented reservation as a tool to solve the problem of exclusion in our societies. Thus, it is necessary to clarify the concept of exclusion first. Adelman and Morris (1973) see it as lack of opportunity to meet basic needs for substantial sections of the population. Amartya Sen (2000) regards this as a "capability deprivation" and describes two forms of exclusion consists of active exclusion and passive exclusion in our societies. Sen further clarifies that both forms of exclusion are important, to consider, but not in similar way. Similarly, some communities of people are systematically blocked from rights, opportunities, and resources that are normally available to members of society and that are key to social integration. Across the globe, 60 percent of countries have adopted alternative forms of quotas that have advanced women's representation in governance at the national, provincial, and local levels. Quotas are an important conduit for building influence for women, not just in politics but also in public life. The status of women in politics helps to improve the status of women in public life as well (The Women in Public Service Project, 2014).

2.6 Reservation Policy in Civil Service: South Asian Context

Maximum countries in the world are realizing and implementing the reservation system in their public service to make them more familiar to their society whereas south Asia is also employing the policy with different grounds. South Asia is also the home of over one-fifth of the world's women and hundreds of indigenous people with the much diversified society. We should conclude that need-based distribution of opportunity is normally reservation as unequal delivery among unequal's. We can see the practice of Sri Lanka and India regarding reservation system or affirmative action in the civil service.

2.6.1 Sri Lanka

Sri Lanka is a multi-ethnic and multi-religious society. The 17.3 million inhabitants consist of 74% Sinhalese, 18% Tamils, 7% Muslims and 1% this small minority groups. Sinhalese and Tamils are separated by language and religion, the former being 95% Buddhist and the latter being 90% Hindu, (De A. Samarasinghe, 1993). Sri Lanka was more focused on changing the civil service and education system. So Affirmative Action policies implemented by the ruling party United National Party (UNP) were ethnically inclusive but those of the breakaway party Sri Lanka Freedom Party (SLFP) were ethnically biased in favor of Sinhalese. (ibid: 46-47).

2.6.2 India

The policy of inclusion in the public sectors in India came into practice as positive discrimination in the form of quota system by the British India Company Government. The then government introduced elements of reservation in the Government of India Act of 1909. It means there was a kind of practice of inclusive policy in the different sectors of government before the independence of India. After the independence of India in 1947, there were some major initiatives in favor of the Scheduled Tribes, Scheduled Castes (historically disadvantaged tribes and castes listed by Government of India) to increase their participation in public sectors and for their empowerment. The country's affirmative action program launched in 1950 is the oldest such program in the world (Malik, 2013). This affirmative action, also known as reservation in India is the policy of promoting the education and employment of members of groups that are known to have previously suffered from discrimination. The constitution has made the provision of reservation for different marginalized groups of the societies not exceeding

fifty percent of total vacancy. In India affirmative actions are provided to Dalit's and Adivasi's who are termed as Schedule caste and Schedule Tribe. Reservation allows for positive measures to be taken in allotment of government jobs and public universities to people belonging to Schedule caste and Schedule Tribe community. The act provides protection measures to Schedule caste and Schedule Tribe. People so that they are not discriminated more (Rai & Lievesley, 2013).

Most South Asian Constitutions have cherished strong guarantees to ensure women's and marginalized people's participation in civil service and politics. All countries in the South Asian region contain quota system with the exception of Sri Lanka and Maldives (Ibid). The countries of south Asian regions are very diversified in their own in terms of religions, gender, castes, cultures, languages, customs, social norms, values, economic status, geographical structures, exploitation of minority and so on. This allocation quota requirement and its constitutional provisions of different South Asian countries have been briefly demonstrated in the following table. Besides this in Bangladesh and Pakistan, quota system in the services is based on the population ratio of various regions of the countries. In India, Nepal, and Sri Lanka, some representation in services is given on other grounds, as specified in the service requirements (Ibid).

Table 2
Reservation System Provisions in Civil Service of South Asian Counties

Countries	Constitutional and Legal Provisions
Bangladesh	Merit 45%, Reservation 55 (30% reserved for freedom fighter or children of freedom fighter; 10% reserved for women; 5% reserved for tribal; 10% reserved for different districts).
Nepal	Merit 55%, Reservation 45% by considering it as 100%, (for women 33%, indigenous (Janajati) 27%, Madhesi 22%, Dalit 9%, disables 5%, remote region 4%)
India	Merit 50.5%, Reservation (49.5% for other backward community (OBC) 27%, scheduled castes (SC) 15%, and scheduled tribes (ST) 7.5 %.)
Pakistan	Merit 7.5%, Reservation 92.5% (for women 10% and Province 82.5%).

(Narendra Raj Poudel, Inclusive Governance, Article 2016)

In Bangladesh, Nepal, and Pakistan, quota for various provinces/ regions of the country is prescribed under the federal law to ensure their participation of women and other

deprived people in the civil services of the country. However, there is no such provision in Afghanistan, Bhutan, Maldives, and Sri Lanka and they have recruitment based on open merit. In India, the reservation has been applied for Scheduled Castes (SC), Scheduled Tribes (ST), Other Backward Classes (OBC), and Physically Handicapped persons for their participation in the services. Besides this in Bangladesh and Pakistan, quota system in the civil services is based on the population ratio of various regions/provinces of the countries. In India, Nepal and Sri Lanka have limited representation in services is given on other rationale grounds, as specified in their own professional civil service requirements (Ibid).

2.7 Reservation Policy: The Context of Nepal

In the context of Nepal, (Gurung, 2007) argues that the social organization on the basis of hierarchical caste system as the main cause for exclusion. Also, the political ideology of Nepal as a Hindu country that sanctified caste system remained highly exclusionary. According to ADB (2010), Social exclusion which is entrenched in the political, economic and social fabric of Nepal is mainly due to the Hindu caste system that traditionally categorized people into Brahmin, Chhetri's, Vaishya and Shudras. This was formally legalized in the Civil Code (Muluki Ain 1854), the first legal code in the written form of the country. Later, the consolidation of economic and political power by the privileged Brahmin and Chhetris led to further marginalization of other Adivasi (Indigenous groups), Janjati (ethnic groups), Muslims and Madhesi who were even not included in the Muluki Ain (ADB, 2010).

As mentioned in the paper prepared for NPC: restricted access to resources, services and opportunities, disempowerment, cultural and ritual debasement, discrimination and marginalization on the basis of caste, ethnicity, culture, language, religious affiliation, territorial/geographical origin/remoteness and gender, and capacity constraints are some of the major form of exclusion in Nepal. The caste hierarchy and state ideology were the main cause to the growth of the social inequality. This social inequality has caused social exclusion in Nepal keeping many castes and ethnic communities in the excluded state from socio-economic, political and several other opportunities. In spite of the official abolition of the caste based discrimination in 1963, the caste based practices seems to have continued till much longer period of time. Moreover, the feudalistic orientation of the society also may have helped perpetuate the exclusionary

process. In today's date, the discrimination by caste is considered to be against the law and it is highly punishable. However, it has not been completely eradicated from Nepalese society.

Similarly, Jamil & Dangal, (2009) have stated that the bureaucracy of Nepal is basically gender biased, caste biased, language biased, religion biased and geographically biased in terms of demography. We came to know that without the active participation and representation of men and women at all levels of decision- making, especially in governance, we cannot achieve the goals of equality, development, and peace Haque, (2000). Reflecting this global trend, female representation in governance has been quite poor in most Asian countries. In addition to the sustainable development of mentioned groups were categorized for social inclusion in civil service to women, indigenous (Adibasi/Janajati), Madhesi and Dalit people of Nepal, whereas there are two more categories distinguished as people from remote regions and physically disabled people for the same. The following nine districts out of seventy-seven regions fall under the category of the remote regions: Kalikot, Dolpa, Mugu, Jumla, Humla, Achham, Jajarkot, Bajhang and Bajura. People from these backward regions have been provided with 4% of the reserved quota in the process of recruitment of employee in civil service.

2.8 Legal Provisions of Reservation in Civil Service of Nepal

Reservation policy in Nepal has often been a response to the demand by women and other marginalized groups for a role in national life. The demand represents a legitimate fight for equality and is not new. The Interim Constitution of Nepal 2007 includes several gender-friendly provisions and inclusive principles, not least the fundamental right of the citizen to social justice. Article 21 states that women, Dalits, Adibasi/Janajati's, the Madhesi community, downtrodden classes, poor farmers, and workers who have lagged behind from the economic, social or educational viewpoint shall have the right to participate in the state structure based on the principle of proportionate representation. Then, in August 2007, the second amendment to the 1992 Civil Service Act provided for reserving 45 per cent of all vacancies to be fulfilled by way of open competition and, assuming the vacancies thus reserved to be 100 percent, fulfilling the same by way of separately-held competitions from among each of the six specified categories of candidates: Women (33 percent), Adibasi/Janajati (27 percent), Madheshi (22 percent), Dalit (9 percent), persons with disability (5 percent) and those

from the backward areas (4 percent). The Civil Service (Second Amendment) Act, 1991, in 2007 has since formed a reference for other public services and similar, if not the same, provisions have been made in security services, university services and so on. Many factors seem to be at work in achieving representative public administration beyond the arithmetic of reservation, however. Finding them out and addressing them together should be part of the reform agenda for Nepalese bureaucracy

Reservation in Nepal is a form of affirmative action designed to improve the participation of under-represented communities defined primarily by gender, caste, backwardness and disability. Reservation based on gender, caste, backwardness and disability are laws both Constitutional and statutory. The advent of democracy in 1951 steered in many changes in Nepal. Until then the demand for reservation was part of dominated by the broader civil rights movement. Democracy brought with it equal rights for all citizens regardless of gender or other forms of social grouping. The Constitution of the Kingdom of Nepal 1990 enabled inclusive policies in four ways:

- By virtue of a provision to the right to equality conferred by Article 11(3) allowing the State to make laws providing for special measures for the protection and development of women, children, senior citizens with physical or mental disability or classes who have lagged behind from the economic, socio-cultural viewpoint;
- By directing the State in principle to pursue the policy of maximally involving women in national development by making special provisions for the education, health and employment of women [Article 26 (7)];
- By directing the State in principle to pursue the policy of uplifting ethnic groups and communities who have lagged behind from the economic or social viewpoint [Article 26 (10)]; and
- By requiring every political party or organization to field at least five per cent female candidates in the elections for the erstwhile House of Representatives [Article 114].

The Road Map expected a number of reforms, inter alia, amending the law with a view to (a) reserving, for the time being, 20 percent of all entry-level vacancies for women for five years; and (b) for reserving 10 percent and 10 percent positions for Dalit (socially untouchable class as per the Hindu caste system) and Janajatis (indigenous and ethnic community) likewise. The reservation system has received a mixed response

since its inception. It has been praised for diminishing the gap between well represented and under-represented through reservation. It has also been criticized for discouraging a merit based system. Brief Introductory Booklet" The Public Service Commission of Nepal" published by PSC quotes that: The recent historic political change in 2007 A.D. in the country has been characterized by its drive for inclusive society as well as the federal state. The growing emphasis on inclusiveness in recruitment and promotion of public servants seems to have narrowed the scope of the PSC for selection of candidates on a merit basis, besides increasing complexities in its work processes reducing efficiency in operation. To some extent, it has been also exposed a challenge on maintaining meritocracy in the civil service.

2.9 Constitutional Provisions in Nepal

Before 1990, Nepal was enacted major four constitutions with their timely amendments. Democracy was firstly planted in 1951 (2007 BS) which was the termination point of 104 years Rana regime. This declaration of democracy has become the milestone of Nepalese public administration and governance. After all Nepalese society has been faced the various obstacles and challenges to deliver the needs and desire of citizens. The extreme exploitation and domination of Panchayat regime demanded that the first national revolution in Nepal. This first revolution of Nepal has given the birth of constitution of kingdom of Nepal in 1990.

2.9.1 The Constitution of Kingdom of Nepal, 1990

The constitution of Nepal 1990 which was drafted after first national revolution conferred the sovereign power in the people of Nepal thereby guarantying fundamental and human rights and reestablishing a multiparty democratic political system based on equity, equality and social justice in the country. The directive principles of the constitution, in article 25(3), mentions that the social objective of the state shall be to establish and develop, on the foundation of justice and morality, a healthy social life, by eliminating all types of economic and social inequalities and by establishing harmony amongst the various castes, tribes, religions, languages, races and communities. Also, as mentioned in part three of the constitution (Fundamental Rights, article 11), all citizens were equal before the law, and no citizen was supposed to be discriminated by anybody on the grounds of religion, race, sex, caste, tribe or ideological conviction. Also, it mentioned that the state shouldn't discriminates on the

above mentioned grounds except the case of special provisions made by law for the protection and advancement of the interests of women, children, the aged or those who are physically or mentally incapacitated or those who belonged to economically, socially or educationally backward class. This shows that the constitution of Nepal 1990 already moved towards equity, equality, social justice and toward an inclusive thought for supporting the needy people or class.

2.9.2 The Interim Constitution, 2007

The Interim Constitution of Nepal had advocated to be more inclusive than previous one regarding human rights, against discrimination, distribution of opportunities and access to resources etc. The Interim Constitution of Nepal states in its article 13.1, 13.2 and 13.3 as a fundamental right to equality" which can be mentioned as bellow;

- 1) All citizens shall be equal before the law. No person shall be denied the equal protection of the laws.
- 2) No discrimination shall be made against any citizen in the application of general laws on grounds of religion, color, sex, caste, tribe, origin, language or ideological conviction or any of these.
- 3) The State shall not discriminate against citizens among citizens on grounds of religion, race, caste, tribe, sex, origin, language or ideological conviction or any of these."

This Interim Constitution further states, "Provided that nothing shall be deemed to prevent the making of special provisions by law for the protection, empowerment or advancement of women, Dalit, indigenous peoples (Adibasi, Janajati), Madhesi (people originally from southern flat land called Terai) or farmers, workers, economically, socially or culturally backward classes or children, the aged and the disabled or those who are physically or mentally incapacitated. "The Interim Constitution of Nepal further states in its article 21 as a right to social justice," The economically, socially or educationally backward women, Dalits, indigenous peoples, Madhesi communities, oppressed classes, poor farmers and labors shall have the right to take part in the structures of the State on the basis of the principle of 'proportional inclusion." The Interim Constitution of Nepal states in its article 33(dl) as an Obligations of the State, "To have participation of Madhesi, Dalit, indigenous peoples, women, labors, farmers,

disabled, backward classes and regions in all organs of the State structure on the basis of proportional inclusion."

The Comprehensive Peace Accord (CPA) concluded between the Government of Nepal and Communist Party of Nepal (Maoist) states that, "To end the existing centralized and unitary structure of the State so as to address the problems including those of women, Dalit, indigenous peoples, Madhesi, oppressed, excluded and minority communities and backward regions, and make an inclusive, democratic and progressive restructuring of the State, while at the same time doing away with discriminations based on class, caste, language, gender, culture, religion and region." CPA further obligates the state, "Both parties respect the right of every citizen to take part directly or through representative of his or her choice in issues of public concern, to vote, to be elected and to equality in admission to public services."

2.9.3 The Constitution of Nepal, 2015

This constitution is the ultimate result of ten years' home war from 2052-062 and second nineteen days' national revolution of 2062/63 in Nepal. Ultimately three level federalism has been sanctioned in the constitution of Nepal. The preamble of the Constitution of Nepal claims for ending all forms of discriminations and oppression created by the feudal, autocratic, centralized and unitary system, embracing multi-caste, multi-lingual, multi-cultural and diverse geographical specificities, by ending discriminations relating to class, caste, region, language, religion and gender discrimination including all forms of racial untouchability, in order to protect and promote unity in diversity, social and cultural solidarity, tolerance and harmonious attitudes, we also express our determination to create an egalitarian society on the basis of the principles of proportional inclusion and participation, to ensure equitable economy, prosperity and social justice"

- The Constitution of Nepal states in its article 18.1, 18.2 and 18.3 as a fundamental right to equality. It claims that "nothing shall be deemed to bar the making of special provisions by law for the protection, empowerment or advancement of the women lagging behind socially and culturally, Dalit's, Adibasi, Madhesi, Tharus, Muslims, oppressed class, backward communities, minorities, marginalized groups, peasants, laborers, youths, children, senior citizens, sexual minorities, persons with disability,

pregnant, incapacitated and the helpless persons, and of the citizens who belong to backward regions and financially deprived citizens including the Khas Arya."

- Article 24 (3) declares that "racial discriminations shall not be encouraged in any way, or there shall not be any behavioral attitude to exhibit high or low status on grounds of a particular caste, ethnicity or community, or physical condition of a person, or there shall not be any behavioral attitude that justifies social discrimination based on caste, ethnicity, or untouchability, or encouragement for the propagation of attitudes based on caste superiority and untouchability"
- Article 33, right to employment: (1) every citizen shall have the right to employment. The terms and conditions of employment, and unemployment benefit shall be as provided for in the Federal law.
- Article 34, right to laborer (2) every laborer shall have the right to appropriate remuneration, facilities and contributory social security.
- Article 38, rights of women:
 - (4) Women shall have the right to participate in all bodies of the State on the basis of the principle of proportional inclusion.
 - (5) Women shall have the right to obtain special opportunity in education, health, employment and social security, on the basis of positive discrimination.
- Article 40, rights of Dalit:
 - (1) The Dalit shall have the right to participate in all bodies of the State on the basis of the principle of proportional inclusion. Special provision shall be made by law for the empowerment, representation and participation of the Dalit community in public services as well as other sectors of employment.
 - (2) Provision of free education with scholarship, from primary to higher education, shall be made by law
 - (3) Special provision shall be made by law in order to provide health and social security to the Dalit community.
 - (7) The facilities conferred by this Article to the Dalit community must be distributed in a just manner so that the Dalit women, men and Dalit in all communities can obtain such facilities proportionately.
- Article 42, right to justice claims that "socially backward women, Dalits, Adibasi, Janajati, Adibasi/Janajati, Madhesi, Tharu, minority groups, persons with disability, marginalized groups, Muslim, backward classes, gender and sexually minority

groups, youths, peasants, laborers, the oppressed and the citizens of backward regions, and economically poor Khas Arya shall have the right to employment in state structures on the basis of the principle of inclusion."

- Article 86 (2) (a) has provisioned that "members elected from an electoral college comprising members of provincial assembly and chairpersons and vice-chairpersons of village councils and mayors and deputy mayors of municipal councils, with different weights of votes for each, with eight members from each province, including at least three women, one Dalit, one person with disability or minority;
- Article 269 (4) (c) "There should be the provision of proportional participation so as to reflect the diversity of Nepal, in the executive committees at various levels of the party."
- Article 283 for the "appointment to be made on inclusive principles: appointment to the constitutional bodies shall be made based on the principles of inclusion."
- Article 285 (2) Positions of all federal governmental services shall be fulfilled through competitive examinations on the basis of the principle of open and proportional inclusion according to Federal law.

The constitution of Nepal has also made the provision of constitutional bodies such as National Women Commission, National Dalit Commission, National Inclusion Commission, Indigenous Nationalities Commission, Madhesi Commission, Tharu Commission, and Muslim Commission are provisioned in the Constitution. Such Commissions have authority to formulate policy, carry out study and research and make necessary suggestions to the Government for the protection and promotion of the concerned groups. Realization of the strengths of inclusion in the political, administration and community level can enhance the inspiring environment and contribute to the creation of social cohesion and harmony. That's why constitution of Nepal is intensively protects the inclusive principle to make the governmental actions more representative.

2.10 Civil Service Act, 2049 and Regulation, 2050

In spite of a legal framework on a par with the fundamental rights specifically made in the constitution 1990 with a view to encouraging people from previously excluded groups to participate in nation building, no legal frameworks were enacted for any kind

of inclusion in Civil Service due to the lack of the government initiative and commitment to make the Service more inclusive. However, after the promulgation of the Interim Constitution 2007, the legal provisions for the inclusion of deprived and excluded groups was framed. Accordingly, the second amendment in the Civil Service Act,³ 1993 was made in order to encourage women, Adivasi (indigenous/ ethnic groups), Madhesi, Dalit, disabled and people from remote areas. This amendment in the Civil Service act 1993 seems to have brought a remarkable change and is considered as a milestone in making Civil Service inclusive. Finally, talking about the implementation of the policy to demand, select and recommend for the recruitment in the Civil Service, the Nepalese parliament adopted a bill amending the Civil Service Act 1993 and provided reservation for disadvantaged groups by allocating 45 percent of the jobs in Civil Service and the policy was brought into use since 2007 through Public Service Commission Nepal.

Section 7.7 of Civil Service Act has provisioned reservation in order to make inclusive the civil service, forty-five percent of the posts to be fulfilled by open competition shall be set aside and be filled up by having separate competition between the following candidates only, by considering the 45 percentage into 100 percent: Women: Thirty-Three Percent, Adiwasi/Janjati: Twenty-Seven Percent, Madhesi –Twenty: Two Percent, Dalit - Nine Percent, Disabled (differently able)- Five Percent and Backward Area - Four Percent. According to Civil Service Act "backward area" means Achham, Kalikot, Jajarkot, Jumla, Dolpa, Bajhang, Bajura, Mugu and Humla districts and "women, Adiwasi/Janajati, Madhesi, and Dalit "means women, Adiwasi/Janajati, Madhesi, and Dalit who are backward economically and socially. All the residents of Achham, Kalikot, Jajarkot, Jumla, Dolpa, Bajhang, Bajura, Mugu and Humla and all women, Adiwasi/Janajati, Madhesi, and Dalit are considered as economically and socially backward. Vacant post to be filled by people with disability shall be filled up through competitive examination between such disabled only as may be specified for any specific nature of work. Specific nature of the job and severity of the disability is yet to be defined.

Section 7.11 of Civil Service Act specifies 45 percent of vacancies in civil service as a quota reserved for the candidates from the residents of Achham, Kalikot, Jajarkot,

³ Civil service Act, 1993, second amendment was done in 2007.

Jumla, Dolpa, Bajhang, Bajura, Mugu and Humla and all women, Adiwasi/Janajati, Madhesi, and Dalit and people with disability respectively for a period of ten years, after which the quota system would be reviewed. Civil Service Regulation 2050, rule 14, had the provision of determination of number of posts on the basis of percentage of fulfillment of vacancy: (3) For the purposes of Sub-section (7) of Section 7 of the Act, the details of economically and socially backward women, indigenous/nationalities, Madhesi, Dalit communities shall be as specified by the Government of Nepal by publishing a notice in the Nepal Gazette. Provided that, all women, indigenous/nationalities, Madhesi, Dalit communities shall be considered economically and socially backward communities until so specified by the Government of Nepal by publishing a notice in the Nepal Gazette.

2.11 Public Service Commission, Nepal

Nepalese civil service is one of the major employment creator in Nepal. Though the history of modern civil service is much shorter than the history of the country. Modern Nepalese civil service got its foundation only after dawn of democracy in 1951. Public Service Commission (PSC) was established in Nepal on 15 June 1951 A.D. The Commission is involved in selecting meritorious candidates required by Government of Nepal for various vacant posts of the civil service. The continuity of PSC has never been hindered since its establishment. Present Constitution of Nepal has designated the Public Service Commission as an independent constitutional body. That year Public Service Commission was established and Butch Commission headed by N.M. Butch, an Indian administrative expert, suggested to build some basic structure of civil service in Nepal. This was the starting point and it grew further. Present Administrative structure of Nepal government is segmented into the central and field levels. At the central level, there are Ministries, Departments, Constitutional Bodies and other central level offices. All the civil servants are hired on a permanent basis by the Public Service Commission (PSC).

According to constitutional provision of Nepal, Public Service Commission is a sole authority to conduct examinations for the selection of suitable candidates to be appointed to Civil Service positions. In order to select suitable candidates through open competition, it conducts competitive written examinations, competitive practical examination, Short-listings of candidates, and Interview for the final selection. The

vacant positions in Government Offices need to be given to PSC and it selects suitable candidates for those positions and recommends the government to appoint them. These government positions are of several types but basically divided into three categories; Gazetted, Non-gazetted and Class-less. Under these categories there are different positions. All these categories along with positions fall under 10 types of services which form civil service in Nepal.

Many efforts have been undertaken in the past to make better Nepalese Civil service. For instance, Administrative Reorganization Planning Commission, under the Prime Minister Tanka Prasad Acharya, played a very important role in introducing the Civil Service along with the availability of necessary rules and regulations in the field. Following the Acharya Commission of 1956, various attempts on administrative reforms through the formation of commissions were made in Nepal as the commissions submitted their reports with necessary recommendations. Unfortunately, even a single commission never brought the policy of inclusion to disadvantaged groups: Women, Madhesi, Ethnic Nationalities, Dalit, and other marginalized in administrative mechanism of the country. As a result, these groups remained marginalized and deprived of representation in the civil service. Thus, during feudal Rana and authoritarian Panchayat regime, they were deprived of congenial environment and opportunity to join the civil service and pro-marginalized civil service curriculum. In this scenario, the main objective to introduce Reservation in Nepalese civil service was to build such an environment where deprived people can also enter the service. Because, before the new system, very few candidates of these groups were able to enter the service and the representation of these communities in civil service was much lower than their ratio in population.

2.12 Contemporary Theories of Reservation System

A theory itself is a set of interrelated concepts, definitions, and propositions. It explains or predicts events or situations by specifying relations among variables. I believe that a theory presents a systematic way of understanding events, behaviors and/or situations (Glanz, n.d). According to Talib & Tavallaee (2010), the qualitative researcher intends to create an appropriate theory which suits the topic. I endorse these authors for I have presented myself as a qualitative researcher here in this research study. I also agree with the argument made by Parsons (1938) that the theories reveal the gaps in our existing

knowledge and their existence thereby constituting a crucially important guide to the direction fruitful research. The study of reservation system or affirmative action can be based on following theories, which can be briefly described and analyzed accordingly:

2.12.1 Social Empowerment

Empowerment theory is delivered by American Psychologist Julian Rappaport (1981) which literally means giving authority or power to, creating power within and enabling. It is a multidimensional process, which enables individuals and groups to realize their full identity and power in all spheres of life, social, economic, cultural, political and others. The Oxford Dictionary defines empowerment as the action of empowering, the state of being empowered. The root of the word empowerment is power, ability to do, accomplish, to give strength and confidence and performance. It is giving power to make one's voice heard, to contribute to plans and decisions that have impact on public. Empowerment is a process of identifying and removing the conditions, which cause powerlessness while increasing the feeling of self-efficiency'. It should be pointed out, here, that it is not merely external actions that facilitate or ensure empowerment, but it is also a process of changing the internal beliefs of people. Both the external and internal factors have relevance for empowerment.

According to Gitte Sorensen and Helle Poulson, “empowerment means gaining autonomy and control over one's life. The empowered become agents of their own development, and able to exercise choices, set their own agenda and are capable of challenging and changing their subordinate position in society. The several components of empowerment are social, economic, political, and cultural and others. Empowerment also brings legal and moral powers to individuals and groups”. The collective and individual dimensions of empowerment are brought out by Hapke, to whom; empowerment is autonomy, both collective and individual. It encompasses several mutually reinforcing components. Closely related to this view is that of Rapport who says that 'empowerment suggests both individuals' determination over one's own life and democratic participation in the life of one's community through different structures. Empowerment conveys both a psychological sense of personal control or influence and a concern with actual social influence, political power and legal rights.

2.12.2 Representative Bureaucracy

There is a general consensus in the literature that the idea of representative bureaucracy was first proposed by Donald Kingsley in 1944. The fundamental idea from Kingsley's perspective, was a criticism of the public bureaucracy in the UK of its authoritarian and bias nature in terms of the effective of public policy on different categories of people. To overcome this problem, Kingsley (1944) called for a public bureaucracy that reflects the various social backgrounds of officials in the decision-making processes with the view that such backgrounds may influence how these officials make decisions and thus help reduce, if not prevent public policies, from being hijacked or biased toward certain groups of people at the neglect of others in the society (Choi et al. 2018; Peters et al. 2013). He was of the notion that such a bureaucracy will be more politically representative of the general populace. Since Kingsley's proposition, the idea has assumed a significant role in the discussion of how the public bureaucracy should be constituted in order for it to reflect the dynamics of modern society from both theoretical and practical perspectives (Dauda, 2016; Meier, 2018; Peters et al. 2013).

This theory belongs to equitable representation is needed in public institutions. Representative bureaucracy emphasizes that if a bureaucracy is broadly representative of the public it serves, then it is more likely to make decisions that benefit that public (Thieleman and Stewart, 1996). The theory of representative bureaucracy incorporates that a public workforce representative of the people in terms of race, ethnicity and sex will help ensure that the interests of all groups are considered in bureaucratic decision making processes. If the bureaucracy is truly representative in nature, all segments of society feel that they are having good opportunity to involve in national building process and civil service of Nepal. The representative theory claims full participation and fair representation of all segments of society into the mainstream of socio-economic activities, politics and administration are among the basic principles of inclusive development. Among the methods of ensuring participation and representation in such areas are quotas or reservation system. Administrative inclusion increases access of people to their government. Representative bureaucracy believes that if it is broadly representative of the public it serves, then it is more decisions that benefits that public (Thieleman and Stewart 1996).

2.12.3 Theory of Gender Equality

The theory of gender equality is empowered by Christine De Pizan (1405) which deals with the economic, social, religious and other barriers and taboos that are playing stumbling block in terms of gender inequality in the society must be addressed and eradicated for the overall socio-economic development of women and society. Therefore, in order to ensure equitable gender inequality must be dismantled. Over the last fifteen years, gender equality has indeed been a great concern among all partners of development dynamics and social engineering. Gender equality has been brought to bear on development issues when it started becoming clear that planned development efforts, which were meant to improve the lives of whole communities, were not treating women with gender justice. It was observed by the development community around 60's and 70's that development was not reaching the poor majority with mere absence of women's equitable participation in development.

The word 'gender' is used to describe the characteristics of women and men that are socially constructed in terms of role, status, power and capability. It is socially learned behaviors and expectations that are associated with two sexes. Whereas, maleness and femaleness are biological facts, masculinity and femininity are culturally constructed attributes. Gender refers to socio-cultural definition of man women, the way societies distinguish men and women and assign them social roles. The concept of gender is used as an analytical tool to understand social realities with regard to women and men. It is the combination of socially constructed roles and socially learned behaviors and expectations associated with female and male in the society. The major gender perspectives can be:

- All women and men have the right to be considered in the development process and results of benefits according to their gender needs. Gender perspective establishes right-based approach rather women as just beneficiaries or welfare cases.
- Governments around the world have agreed in international agreements and human rights instruments to play a gender perspective in their policies and plans of action.
- A gender perspective improves efficiency and sustainability in content and process of development works.
- Development is all about improving people's a lot, and as such it is a social process of inclusion including gender.

Gender equality is the state of equality among women and men in a broader social system irrespective of biological differences. Based on the rights of women to be equal to men it is equally in rights, resources and voice. It refers to equality in access to resources, equality in participation in decision-making, and equality in sharing of benefits. Equality signifies non-discrimination and absence of disparity with respect to gender differences. Gender equality is measured with multi-dimensional indicators. Such indicators include human development perspective, employment perspective and participation perspective. Gender equality is thus a composite phenomenon determined by equality under law, equality of access, equality of opportunity, equality of voice and equality of benefits. Gender inequality is determined by the content, process and effects in opportunity and benefits to be shared by women and men. It is manifested in various terms including marginalization, subordination, discrimination, gender stereotypes, multiple and unequal burden, violence and exploitation. Gender equity is the state of relationship between efforts, contribution and the benefits among women and men. The extent of gender equity is determined by the gap between the formal equality and substantive equality in result among women and men, and special measures to promote gender equality is necessary.

Gender equality women's rights are the to key to addressing the unfinished business of the millennium development goal (MDGs) and accelerating global development beyond 2015. Gender equality matters in its own right, and as a prerequisite for the health and development of facilities and societies, and a driver of economic growth. Gender initiatives are must to help governments promote gender equality in education and employment. Reducing persistent gender inequalities is necessary not only for reasons of fairness and equality but also out of economic necessity (OECD, 2011).

2.12.4 Theory of Social Integration

Literally, Emile Durkheim (1960) described the Social Integration which means to integrate, sum up or synthesize different groups of society. Yes, it has already been mentioned that Nepal is a multi-ethnic, multi-cultural, multi-religious and multi-lingual country. So, there are several groups of people according to their ethnicity, religion, culture, language and also of different class from economic status. As mentioned earlier, I, however, prefer to stratify them into two strata on the ground of my research study: those groups which are excluded and those which are in the mainstream.

In my opinion, a bonding force between them may be necessary to reduce the gap between them to minimal, and I think this concept of mine is very close with Durkheim's theory of social integration, moreover, social solidarity. This concept however sounds very tuned with Durkheim theory of social integration. According to him, as he has mentioned in 'The Division of Labor in Society', Social Integration can be defined in terms of mechanical and organic solidarity. Mechanical solidarity, according to him, normally prevails in the traditional and simpler or smaller societies where their familial and kinship relations along with their cultures are responsible for the same. On the other hand, in more advanced and developed societies, there prevails the interdependence among them which causes them to keep bounded among each other, and this has been termed as organic solidarity. Anyway, he explains, there is an unseen bond working in the society based upon social solidarity (Shortell, 2012). In this way, the theory of social integration does make a relevance to my study based on affirmative action in civil service. If inclusion process is properly defined to include and integrate every group of people whether excluded or those in the mainstream, this can be a theoretical as well as practical force to reduce the gaps in the society to minimal.

2.12.5 Caste System and Social Justice:

Caste system is the socio-cultural idea obvious to Nepal since the beginning of Hinduism. Wherever no human youngster is conceived with any religious and caste qualities, these are put into the troubles of kid's consequent to their introduction to the world by older folks. The caste framework is for the most part acknowledged as a standout amongst the most complicatedly stratified of all the social frameworks on the earth and it is the most striking promotion of the Hindu culture. Indeed, it cuts over the religious limits and envelops whatever remains of the religious groups in some measure in Nepal. As he further says, "Each Hindu is naturally introduced to a caste and his caste decides his religious, social, economic and local life from the support to the grave. The caste framework is a convoluted one, both hypothetically and basically, it is an organization that forecasts enormous outcomes for all concerned. It is a national issue equipped for wide social strain; the length of caste in Nepal does exist, the Hindus will barely between wed or have any social intercourse with untouchables; and if caste-minded Hindus move to different locales on the earth, the Nepalese caste would turn into a world issue.

There are a few ways and intends to endeavor that claims changes in social qualities and modes of social practices. Realizing social change through enactments is a vital apparatus to convey social justice to a huge degree to destitute and weaker sections of the general public. The Nepalese social reformers fitting in with nineteenth and early twentieth centuries appear to have given extraordinary arrangement of imperativeness to social enactment for this reason. Enactments relating to the weaker sections, particularly ladies viz., Sati Pratha, the revisions to Hindu Marriage & Family laws, Labor Laws, Dowry, Child Marriage Act, the Acts securing the diversions of disabled, minorities and frail gatherings; change identifying with social disasters like poor people, asking, prostitutions and social security were instituted with the trust that these laws would endeavor to nullify social indecencies or encourage in realizing the craved social change. Consequently, there are three criteria to judge the premise of transmission, specifically, rights, deceives or need. These three criteria can be put under two ideas of equality "formal equality" and "proportional equality". "Formal equality" implies that law treats everybody meet and does not support anybody either in light of the fact that he fits in with the advantaged section of the general public or to the disadvantaged section of the general public. Idea of "proportional equality" expects the states to make positive move for disadvantaged sections of the general public inside the system of liberal democracy.

Social Justice is considered by John Rawls (1971) as a fundamental need and concern of human social orders. It structures a part of more extensive idea of justice by and large. The Oxford Dictionary watches, "Justice as simply lead of reasonableness. It implies all types of legitimate activity". The thought and standard of social justice is focused around treating each individual just as giving every equal right. Justice is, consequently, contradicted to inequality, injustice and hardship. "Justice suggests moral allotment and it is the human perfect". The social Justice is "the astute participation of individuals in creating a naturally united group so that each part has an equivalent and genuine chance to develop and group to live to the best of his local capacities". The idea of social justice is established on die fundamental perfect of financial equality and its point is to evacuation of financial incongruities and imbalances.

2.12.6 Merit in Inclusive Civil Service

According to the World Development Report 1997: The State in a Changing World bureaucracies with more competitive, merit-based recruitment and promotion practices and better pay are more capable. “Motivated staff is the lifeblood of an effective state”. Employees can be motivated to perform effectively in different ways, however the most important would be through recruitment and promotion systems based on merit. These principles were used back in nineteenth century by countries which strived to build professional bureaucracies. Later the principles were used in East Asia and transformed countries from weak corrupted ones into competitive and well-functioning systems (World Development Report 1997, p. 9). Central banks over the world are represented in the report as a historically good example of the merit-based system, because they work despite anything that can happen in the country, they are less subject to political interference, their employees are usually comparatively better paid than their colleagues from other parts of civil service.

According to Weber in his 'Weberian bureaucracy and economic growth' 'public administrative organizations with meritocratic recruitment and predictable career rewards are effective at facilitating capitalist growth than other forms of federal organizations' (Evans and Rauch, 1999, p. 749). Basically, Weber states that socio-economically more successful countries are the ones with meritocratic system of civil service. Weber viewed bureaucracy as a particular kind of organizational structure, set in contrast to earlier patrimonial form of government administration. This hypothesis cannot be dismissed simply by the discovery that people who call themselves bureaucrats have engaged in rent-seeking or that corrupt governments have undermined economic growth. Addressing the 'Weberian state hypothesis' means answering the question, 'Are countries whose administrative apparatuses more closely approximate bureaucratic forms of organization characterized by higher rates of economic growth?'. It is believed that one of the most beautiful features of civil service is that it is based on merit system⁴. There have been so many efforts in the history of civil service in order to ensure the merit system within it. The equation of what happens to meritocratic nature of civil service in the wake of adaptation of reservation system in civil service has been one of most debated and glaring issue throughout the history. The reservation

⁴ The merit system was introduced in Britain in the 19th century to make it more inclusive against the patron based recruitment system

system and Nepalese civil service is no exception to this. It is believed that it has serious toll in meritocratic nature of civil service. It's even more questionable as the same person is eligible to get benefit from the provision more than ones.

However, governments do not totally rely on merit systems. Willy McCourt, in his paper 'The merit system and integrity in the public service' states that "in pure merit system all public appointments, from top to bottom, follow a competition based on merit rules that are publicly understood and can be challenged if a breach is suspected" (McCourt, 2007 b, p. 6). However, probably no administration runs a pure merit system as defined by Willy McCourt (2007) definition of merit includes the following:

- Jobs at every level: merit principles apply to promotion as to initial recruitment;
- The best candidate: demonstrably the ablest among a number of candidates, any of whom could do the job adequately;
- Open to all: no internal-only appointments or restricted shortlists;
- Systematic, transparent and challengeable: we welcome challenges to our decisions, including from the unsuccessful candidates, viewing them as valuable feedback which will help us make better decisions in future.

Here are five exceptions for merit-based system provided by Willy McCourt (2007):

- Elected officials. Some officials are appointed, not elected;
- Political and 'direct' appointments. Elected officials mostly should be narrowly confined to senior staff who are working directly to politicians;
- Affirmative action. Several administrations, including Canada, Cyprus, Malaysia and the US, have used 'quotas' and in public appointments to increase the number of members of a disadvantaged group, such as women or certain ethnic groups (the Turkish minority in Cyprus, women and disabled people in Canada);
- Internal appointments and transfers; local managers' discretion. Most administrations have restricted certain promotion posts to existing staff in order to minimize transaction costs and to provide career development opportunities;
- Other appointments: succession plans, subsequent, reallocation of duties, sub-contracting to employment agencies etc. (McCourt, 2007, p. 6)

2.13 Principles of Civil Service in Nepal

The major principles of the civil service of Nepal that operates with the following respects and philosophies in the international and domestic environment of Nepal (Civil Service and Re-structuring of the State, Pushkar Bajracharya and Clive Grace, 2014);

- a) **Values, Morale and Objectivity:** The civil and public service should be guided by appropriate values morale. One formulation is that a member of the civil service in discharge of his/her functions is to be guided by maintaining absolute integrity, allegiance to the constitution and the law of the nation, patriotism, national pride, devotion to duty, honesty, impartiality and transparency. Values, standards and ethics in public life is major concern since earlier time in administrative system.
- b) **Management Practices and Code of Ethics:** Civil servants are required to operate to standards of conduct. Public servants are liable to discharge official duty with responsibility, honesty, accountability and without discrimination. It ensures effective management, leadership development and personal growth. Ethics claims to avoid misuse of official position or information and promise to serve as instruments of good governance and social economic development. Ethics, whether in an entire society, or in a social sub-system, evolves from ancient time and is influenced, during its growth, by a variety of environmental factors.
- c) **Political Neutrality and Leadership:** Civil servants should be politically neutral but committed to governmental polies and plans to serve the people day to day, whatever its political complexion and instabilities. Every decision on policy on behalf of government are the responsibility and duty of the civil servant to give the service relevant information and experience, and honest and impartial advice without fear or favor, and whether the advice accords with the impartial views.
- d) **Merit, Skills and Honesty:** All civil service appointments should be recruited on merit, as should matters of promotion and advancement. There is a need to deploy both generalist and specialist skills, and to allow lateral entry at senior levels to ensure that civil service skills are relevant and sufficient to meet constantly changing demands and expectations. Honesty or absolute integrity, truthfulness and hard work without indulgences form an inherent part of the life

a civil servant whose sole objective is to efficiently deliver services to the general public.

- e) **Inclusiveness and Integrity:** The civil service should follow not only requirements on non-discrimination but also inclusiveness. This takes different forms according to context, such as the Nepal requirements in relation to 45% of appointments being within six designated groups.
- f) **Accountable Service Delivery:** In the modern world there is a requirement that the civil and public service should deliver accountable public services which are efficient, effective, responsive and answerable to the needs of the people. This includes direct delivery by the public service but also by ‘agents’ of the public service including the private sector and civil society.
- g) **Federal Approach of Guardianship:** Federalism is the distribution of powers and responsibilities between the federal government and its constituent units both vertically and horizontally. There are only limited number of services/functions that are exclusively exercised by the federal government and hardly any functions that solely practiced by the sub-national governments only. This is because what happens at the sub-national level (e.g., educational attainment, condition of the roads, etc.) is important to the higher levels of government as well – each will have its own democratic mandate for educational attainment, for example, and will need some involvement. Often the character of that involvement will be that the federal level sets the legal framework, while the provincial level has some flexibility within that framework, and with delivery shared between federal, provincial and local levels (for example, universities at federal level, secondary at provincial, and primary at local level). This suggests that all levels of government have to be involved in many of the services. This has a direct bearing on the restructuring of the civil service.

2.14 Theoretical Framework

A theoretical framework⁵ explains graphically or in narrative form the presumed relationships among the key factors, constructs or variables considered integral to the dynamics of the phenomenon being investigated (Sekaran, 1992; Miles and Huberman, 1994). Making use of prior theorizing and sequential explanatory research as important

⁵ The theoretical framework. and. conceptual model. are used interchangeably during the discussion.

inputs, frameworks can be rudimentary or elaborate, descriptive or causal. Applied, therefore, to the study are the convergent insights of resource dependency and institutional theories to develop a framework which focuses on factors at three inter-related and substantive levels. In addition to input from these theoretical approaches, the framework also draws heavily on the empirical work of Grindle and Hilderbrand (1997); Larbi (1998a); and Batley and Larbi (2004). The framework suggests that factors at the micro organizational, mesoderm task network, and macro broad environmental levels impact on bureaucratic functioning and bureaucratic autonomy. My study is related to effects and status of reservation policy in the transformation of civil service in Nepal. So, I had to focus my study through many literatures related and relevant to social inclusion and affirmative action Nepalese context. In fact, the theories helped sharpen the concept towards my study so that I became able to develop my conceptual framework. I am focused through this work to study the reservation policy, perceptions of policy makers, implementers and the excluded group's representatives so that the few variables related to Nepalese context are selected as independent variables from the literature review for the study.

2.14.1 Dependent Variables

A dependent variable is one that is causally influenced by another variable i.e. independent variable. The effects of reservation policy in implementation is the dependent variable in the study. The study intends to assess the effects of reservation policy implementation activities into the civil service of Nepal. The main thrust of the reservation policy is to expand and sustain quality public services delivery of Government of Nepal. This is why it has to create such a conducive environment where every kind of citizens' right are secure and they can freely exercise their opportunities. People feel justice when they get equal access to power, resource and opportunity created by the state. In order to increase this access, reservation is one of the tools of social inclusion which has been introduced in Nepal since 2064 BS. The main motive behind the policy was to increase participation and expand capacities of the marginalized communities as well as women in the civil services. This thesis tries to access the effects of reservation policy taken by the Government of Nepal and seeks to find how much it has been able to solve the problems of marginalization.

A. Individual Effects

The argument is premised on the belief that such attributes lead to certain early socialization experiences that in turn give rise to attitudes and values that ultimately help to shape the behavior and decisions of individual bureaucrats (Krislov 1974; Saltzstein 1979 cited in Selden et al 1998). For a moment, we can forget whatever discriminations have existed. Many talented people of Nepal's vulnerable communities have achieved the highest accolades in their respective fields. Now they are participating in civil service to consider scenario, there is a greater likelihood that the individual's actual achievements which is noticed and evaluated, rather than the effects of their heredity and social environment. In the study, individual effects are measured on the basis of perception of the respondents towards nature of the work, how often they are eager to taking risk, and responsive towards their designated work. So here, this study wants to know the individual Perceptual effects of reservation system into the civil service of Nepal.

B. Organizational Effects

There are various visible and invisible issues and challenges for women and other reserved facilitated employees in civil services at all levels. Many issues and challenges appear due to gender inclined mindset and masculine organization culture. This inclined mindset is the result of traditional cultural value-based social and family socialization which is also reflected in organization culture. Despite holding political power and threatening the upper-caste controlled apparatus of state-directed development, the lower castes were unable to turn this power into institutional change that could bring sustained or equalizing socio-economic gains for them (Harriss-White, 2003). Principally, it is said that organizational culture should be gender-sensitive, caste sensitive, class sensitive and friendly at all level at any cost. However, in practice, evidence shows that organizational culture has not been gender-sensitive, caste sensitive, class sensitive and friendly as expected. It is hidden and unhidden gender and caste influenced behavior which is experienced by women and other reserved facilitated employees at various levels in civil service organizations. In the similar vein, satisfaction was measured on the basis of respondent's perception towards the level of satisfaction towards their designated tasks in the public sector organizations.

2.14.2 Independent Variables

Independent variables are factors that cause or influence dependent variables. In this study, independent variables are the determinants that influence the implementation of reservation policy. The following sets of independent variables are used in this study. It is observed those who are entering to civil from the quota reserved for disadvantaged groups are mostly from the elite class having comparatively good socio-economic status. It is due to the advancement of their education and access to other service that are beneficial to complete in civil service under the quota system. Therefore, on the basis of the aforementioned independent variable, the conceptual framework of this study is considered be as follows:

A. Representativeness of Civil Service of Nepal

There is an extensive debate in the bureaucracy literature regarding the representation of different groups of people in the civil service. Some scholars argue to continue representation while others argue that civil service cannot, and should not be a representative (Adusah-Karikari & Ohemeng, 2014). In terms of demography, the bureaucracy in Nepal is gender biased, religion biased and caste biased, which means that the bureaucracy favors Hindu males who belong to the upper caste and come from an agricultural background. While higher levels of trust through the recognition of minority groups and social communities are counted as positive consequences of inclusiveness and representativeness of public sector organizations as with any other reform policy, representative bureaucracy is likely to create its own constituency of beneficiaries with reference to social cohesion or integrative civil service. There is relatively safe ground to assume that the positive effects of ‘representativeness’ and ‘workforce diversity’ on organizational performance which is highly contingent on task-specific features, institutional characteristics and employee-related properties of public organizations. Nepali society is patriarchy in nature which shapes the masculine attitude, perception, and viewpoints in the civil service directly or indirectly. Civil service is only democratic and representative when meaningful and valuable representation is guaranteed and deconstructed traditional socially-culturally constructed gender image. Changed and modified cultural gender image and value is required in civil service for the efficient and efficient representation of women and deprived community in Nepal.

B. Participation of Disadvantaged People in Civil Service of Nepal.

Inclusion for this purpose is aimed at equal participation of the marginalized groups in development activities with proportional representation in decision making processes, while also promoting their access to social and economic opportunities with social justice (Awasthi & Adhikary, 2012). This newly introduced policy has been able to give some positive impact in terms of increasing the participation of women in the Civil Service of Nepal, but at the same time, it has created confusion as well as controversies. Further, according to Sen, (2000), the ultimate objective of this policy is capability enhancement, so more considerations are needed in building meaningful participation. The participation of public administrators in civil service is empowered toward the politically important issue of minority hiring. The central hypothesis of civil servants to hiring minorities will be more a function of their occupational concerns and of certain of their socio-political characteristics than of their perceptions of public sentiment and external group pressure. Reservation or Affirmative action is one of the tools of inclusive policy which is mainly focused on increasing participation through employment, of marginalized people in government and related services as well as in education system of the country. In order to increase participation in civil service, government introduced reservation system, with second amendment of Civil Service Act, for women, Ethnic groups, Madhesi, Dalit, Disabled, and the people belonging to remote areas. Participation of all community leads to unity in diversity which means complete harmony, peace, and adjustment among different cultural elements arises from a view of accepting the textual position of the Hindu social system, and explaining as well as justifying the empirical social reality in terms of the Vedic scriptures. The concept of unity in diversity gives an erroneous understanding of Nepalese social reality.

C. Perception towards Reservation into the Civil Service of Nepal

The complete support for government commitments to inclusion provides a critical basis for the implementation of inclusionary practices. In the coming years, it is important to keep track of peoples' support for and perceptions of affirmative action in order to measure the entire progress into the governance and civil service of Nepal. In 2007, Nepal introduced a reservation policy for women and other marginalized groups. The policy was a collective outcome of long struggles of marginalized groups for social inclusion. The amended Civil Service Act, 1993 has not only

reserved seats for women for employment in the civil service, but also increased the age limit to 40 years for them. For others, 35 years is the maximum age for entry into the civil service. Through reservation quotas, about 8,000 women, 6000 Indigenous people, 5000 Madhesi, 2000 Dalit and 1000 disable people have been joined the civil service till 2077 BS and are now working as civil servants holding different positions of authority in the Nepalese bureaucracy. Civil Service Act, 1993 has been complied with the core moral obligation is to make equal treatment and respect the basic human values and norms with equal perception towards all different communities and regions. So, after 12 years of implementation of reservation system in Nepal, the research has been made about the perception in relation to the area of public organizational management. Nepalese reservation system has to give comprehensive attention to all the dimensions of exclusion and its effects on generating different perception of some marginalized people towards national bureaucratic system is praiseworthy.

D. Performance of Disadvantaged People into the Civil Service System of Nepal

Despite the overall political change requiring the neutral to the committed bureaucracy, civil service has not drastically changed as per the requirement and expectation of citizen. There is a need of the development of the synchronizing mechanism between the currier development and the organizational structure and balancing and coordinating in the reservation system and performance based civil service. Performance evaluation system is agreed to be very important to improve the performance capacity, moral and motivation of the civil servants and improve the efficiency and effectiveness of public service delivery as well as organization too. The current idea of meritocracy in Nepal is largely rooted in the exams administered by the Public Service Commission. This patterns of examination neglects other key criteria which influence the work performance of individual personnel such criteria are educational performance, prior job motivation, prior work experience and skill training. This is another critical area for civil service of Nepal. There is not a sufficient culture of performance, achievement, and results orientation. Nepal has practiced performance management in the form of managing for development results, performance incentives, performance contracting and so on covering certain development sectors and organizational functions or system. But these are considered by many to have been executed in a half-hearted way, lacking

consistency and continuity, and failing to demonstrate real impact and prove itself to have the real value it ought to have in the Nepalese context. Therefore, this study has the focus on the performance criteria of quota facilitated employees into the culture of office system of civil service of Nepal and how they are performing their professional public service with the bureaucratic culture taking into the study consideration.

Sekaran (1992) extols the virtues of a meaningful and parsimonious framework which explains the variance far more efficiently than an elaborate and cumbersome one encompassing an unmanageable number of factors which only marginally add to the explained variance. In selecting indicators, use was made of this strategy of parsimony (Lijphart, 1975; Sekaran, *ibid*; Miles and Huberman, 1994) to judiciously restrict choice to those variables which, at least at the outset, seemed most important given the subject being investigated. The three broad areas of analysis are operationalized using indicators that include: the legal and administrative framework; legal tradition; government; interest group participation; internal structures and systems; control over resources; attitudes and behaviors, as well as the capacity of central government and other government institutions. According to Snow and Anderson (1991), by adding one layer of data to another to build a confirmatory edifice, constructs and hypotheses are more strongly substantiated, adding rigor, breadth and depth to the investigation. Whereas theoretical framework is used to guide the investigation and analysis of factors impacting on the practice of bureaucratic autonomy.

By reviewing the related both general and specific literatures related to policy implementation reservation system implementation study in Nepal. Only a few variables, and not all, that are relevant to the Nepalese context, are selected as independent variables from the literature review for the study. The following figure presented the whole framework of the study and its discussions on the relationship between independent and dependent variables in this research work.

Figure 1

Dependent and Independent Variables of Reservation System in Nepal

CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This chapter describes the mixed research methods used to collect the qualitative and quantitative data as well required for the proposed study. The research has been adopted the general sociological research methods. The chapter also discusses the rationale plan for the selection of the study area, research design, nature and sources of the data, universe and sampling, data collection techniques, interview schedule, interview with key informant, non-participant observation, trustworthiness, operational definition and measurement of selected concepts or variables, data processing and analysis and limitation of the study. Thus, this chapter mainly highlights the implementation process of research methodology that generates primary and secondary data and its analysis for the findings in research.

3.1 Introduction

Research methodology is the combination of theoretical assumption for generating scientific knowledge verifications, falsification, explanations and interpretation. Research methodology is also aggregation of various research strategies such as survey, case study, historical description, and comparative study. Research methodology further consists of the techniques for data gathering through questionnaires, interviews, observations, field study notes, and review of documents. In sum, methodology is a set of theoretical assumption about how to produce data and methods are more specific procedures and techniques adopted to produce data. Research methodology illustrates research design constructed as mix research method. The significance of mix research method in cross-cultural research is also illustrated by analyzing from a multi-faceted paradigm with concern paid to objective views and subjective views. According to Vienna Circle “knowledge claimed without using certain methodology is metaphysics. Metaphysical knowledge does not require having proof, but scientific knowledge requires certain proof based on the scientific research” (as cited in Khan, 2001, pp.). Therefore, methodology refers to a scientific way to collect data to the study of socio-economic phenomena.

The question on which method is the most appropriate one may depend on the subject matter of study and interest of the researcher. Methodology is also a strategy to organize

a research work to the study of a social phenomenon. In principle, methodology refers to theoretical analysis of different methods which are applied to the study of a particular field of research. In practice, methodology is a strategy or plan of action that links different methods of data collection, their interpretation and findings. Therefore, methodology consists of various research methods, procedures and techniques that we follow to get required information through questionnaires, interviews, observations, focused group studies, field study notes, and review of documents (Creswell, 2003, p.5). Quantitative method tends to study casual variables and their effect on dependent variables with objective data in numerical terms. Qualitative methods tend to explain and analyze reasons with subjective data. Therefore, mixed approach of research methodology combines both quantitative and qualitative research methods.

3.2 Mixed Method to the Study

There are three major research methods i.e. quantitative, qualitative, and mixed methods which have mainly been applied in social science research (Creswell 2003, Yin 2003, Bryman 2001, Gary et al. 1994, Ragin 1989, Silverman 2006, and Layder 2005). This research study is based on mixed methodology, combining both quantitative and qualitative research methods. It is because, the mixed method provides an opportunity to avoid limitations or bias associated with a single method (Creswell, 2003, p.15). Mixed method also provides an opportunity of data triangulation that mixes different types of data to the study of a single phenomenon. This method allows to use predetermined and emerging tools of data collection, opened and closed ended questions, multiple forms of data from statistical and text analysis within a single study. There are different ways in using mixed method in a research work i.e. sequential, or concurrent, or transformative (Creswell, 2003, p.15-16).

The mixed method is more adaptive and whole process of research moves in the both ways that is inductive to deductive and deductive to inductive (Layder, 2005, p.133). According to Creswell (2003, p.208-217) mixed method allows to collect and analyze the data from the both quantitative and qualitative method in a single case. Mixed method is also useful to expand an understanding from one method to another, to converge and to confirm the findings from data triangulation. Whatever research methods we use; the way a research work is designed is important to draw the scientific research findings. The most important thing is to explain social phenomena in a logical

way either by testing theory, contributing theory building process, or mixing both. The main objective of any scientific research method is to maximize validity and reliability of the research work

3.3 Research Design

The principal aspect of methodology is research design which gives the direction to the research especially during the data collection and data analysis steps. The study is based on the descriptive and sequential explanatory method of research. Descriptive research design is a fact finding operation searching for adequate information on any phenomenon for the collection of facts. The objective of the descriptive research is to collect detailed information that describes the current phenomenon, identify the problems, make evaluation and also explore for the future course of action (Wolf and Pant, 2012). To realize the objectives of the study, mixed methodology within a study, combining both quantitative and qualitative research methods were used. Mixed method is popular for collecting and analyzing data using both the quantitative and qualitative methods (Creswell, 2009, p. 15-16). According to Creswell, (2009, p. 204-217) mixed method allows to collect and analyze the data from the both quantitative and qualitative method in a single case.

Mixed method is also useful to expand an understanding from one method to another, to converge and to confirm the findings via data triangulation. In other words, this method has been selected as the model when a researcher uses two different methods in an attempt to confirm and cross validate the findings within a single study. Whatever research methods are used; the way a research work is designed is important to draw the scientific research findings. The most important thing is to explain social phenomena in a logical way either by testing theory, contributing theory building process, or mixing both. The main objective of any scientific research method is to maximize validity and reliability of the research work. The mixed method has been assumed to be most appropriate for this study because it has the capacity of providing more authentic and comprehensive data. This also provides understanding of social reality in a holistic manner. In this study, the main benefit of mixed method is that it allows exploring quantitative method using numerical data taken from survey followed by description of opinion expressed by the people.

The civil service and the affirmative action or reservation policy are very important subjects of social science. The effects of these issues are very much significant and critical in the context of national political, social and economic discourse in Nepal. Therefore, the descriptive method has been found suitable and hence adopted for this study on the basis of the selected research topic, prescribed objective and set research questions. The units of observation involve various government organizations under different ministries of Government of Nepal. There are 88,316 civil servants working in the Nepalese public service. The sample among this population on the basis of convenience and judgmental sampling basis. The data and information for analysis are collected through the questionnaires and interviews with the professional participants and experts of civil service of Nepal, university professors, and legal advocates of positive discrimination in Nepal. The data and information is collected from the discussions, interactions and articles review shed light on the various issues related to this subject matter. The dependent variable of this study is effects of reservation policy in the today's civil service of Nepal with maintaining the merit system is influenced by the various independent variables these can be such as participation of disadvantaged group, ownership of weaker society, empowerment of marginalized communities, attraction to civil service and status of reserved groups and so on. The data and information have been collected prior consideration of the defined dependent and independent variables.

3.4 Source of Data and Information Collection

Data collection is a process of preparing and reviewing data to obtain information for specific purpose. The data collection steps include setting the boundaries for the study, collecting information through questionnaires, observations and interviews, documents, and visual materials as well as establishing the protocol for recording information (Creswell, 2011). For the data collection process, primary and secondary data has been used for the study. This research study is based on the both primary and secondary sources data and information. Data are systematically collected elements of information about a particular social phenomenon during a research. The main purpose of data collection is to examine and interpret causal relations. To this research data were collected for answering research questions and examining causal relations between the independent and dependent variables.

3.5.1 Primary Data Collection

Primary data is data that is collected by a researcher from first-hand sources, using methods like surveys, interviews, or experiments. The main source of primary data of this study is questionnaire survey and interviews. Questionnaire survey was administered and interviews were conducted with the participants who were and have been directly involved in civil service and their involving in implementation of reservation policy. A questionnaires survey was conducted in April-May- June, 2020. The interviews are held in 1 June -30 July, 2020. The organizations for the questionnaire survey and interviews were purposefully selected and respondents within the organizations were randomly selected. The following sub-sections give detail information on primary data collection.

3.5.2 Secondary Data Collection

Apart from the primary data, I also collected secondary data and information. Secondary data are those data which have already been used and published. Moreover, this type of data generally provides savings in cost and time and reductions in respondent burden as compared to the primary data. The more important fact is that “the secondary analysis of primary data enhances the trustworthiness of the original work (Dangal, 2010, p. 73). In other words, it helps support the qualitative findings. These data were collected by the direct visit to the places or from the different websites. As a supporting secondary data I used the data obtained from the office of PSC, Kathmandu, National Personnel Information Agency, Lalitpur and the official website of the same ministry of federal affairs and general administration (MoFAGA). Apart from this, some data were taken from the books, journal and published article by relevant organizations. Furthermore, some of the documents that I studied were: national plans of different periods, The Constitution of Kingdom of Nepal 2047, Interim Constitution of Nepal 2063 and Constitution of Nepal, 2072 and its provisions and policies regarding Social Inclusion and reservation policy in Civil Service through PSC and also the Civil Service act 1993 (the amended). These were used as and when needed as the supporting documents.

3.5 Population and Sample

Population refers to the group of people, events or things of interest that the researcher wishes to investigate (Wolf & Pant, 2007). The population for this study was comprise of the entire person belonging to disadvantaged group who are aspiring candidates willing to be associated with the civil service in Nepal. In order to fulfill the objective of the study, 6 samples were chosen from the population on basis of convenient, purposive and quota sampling for the in key informant interview based on semi structured interview guideline. Among the 6 samples, 2 were representing from women group and one from Adibasi, one from Madhesi, one from Dalit and representing from open group. The major population and the sample is determined according the subject matter requirement and the convenience of information, which can be mentioned and described below:

3.5.1 Population

The population of the study largely comprised of Nepalese civil bureaucrats appointed in terms of civil service act, 2049. The population of this study is 88,316 civil servants working currently in civil service of Nepal. Within this population, I included the women, Dalit, Janajati, Madhesi, Disables and remote areas inhabitant bureaucrats selected from reserved quota provision in the civil service by the Public Service Commission (PSC) Nepal. The marginalized society of Nepalese society is very comprehensive and traditionally complex and diversified with 125 castes and 123 languages domestically, and the participation of reserved groups in civil service is focused and taken into the consideration while undertaking the study.

3.5.2 Sample

In the process of collecting the data and information, the purposive and quota sampling is applied and 130 participants (including 6 interviewee) are selected who are working in the civil service, are selected and questionnaires were sent to them by hand and email by giving two weeks of time bound to respond with mutual consent of respondents. The selection of sample is based on convenience, strategic importance and diversity, relevancy and representativeness. This study has been done on the basis of judgment of researcher. Among the one hundred thirty samples, the respondents are of gazetted level and non-gazetted level, and covers the all twelve groups and sub-groups of services such as Nepal general administration

service (revenue, administration and account), Nepal audit service, Nepal foreign service, Nepal agriculture service, Nepal health service, Nepal forestry service, Nepal education service, Nepal engineering service, Nepal federal statistics planning service, Nepal judicial service and Nepal parliament service and Miscellaneous service according to the civil service ac, 2049.

3.6 Sampling Method

It is very difficult to collect the data and information from the all respondents which come under civil service identified as population and comprehensive information related with identified variables and due to time and other personal factors only some key informants are selected as samples.

Table 3
Participants Details

Participants	Men	Women	Total
Emailed	100	60	160
Received	95	35	130

(Source: Field Survey, 2020)

Therefore, it is imperatively to apply sampling method to select the sample hence the same have been used to collect the desired data and information, based on the nature of the topic to be studied and the requirements and data and information, the judgmental and quota method of non-random sampling method is used. Judgmental and quota sample is found to be suitable for this study for representativeness and authenticity of data from different sectors and variables.

3.7 Data Collection Methods

Data collection is a process of collecting information from all the relevant sources to find answers to the research problem, test the hypothesis and evaluate the outcomes. Data collection methods can be divided into two categories: secondary methods of data collection and primary methods of data collection. Data collection methods are important, because how the information collected is used and what explanations it can generate are determined by the methodology and analytical approach applied by the researcher. Two key data collection methods are used for the study of this research which are as follows;

3.7.1 Questionnaire Survey

The questionnaire was used as a research instrument for this study because it allowed the collection of data from a large group of people within the time constraints. The questionnaires included closed ended questions. The researcher personally administered questionnaire and collect the data from the employees. Closed ended questions were constructed using the 4 point Likert scale. The 4 point Likert scale has been used scale in this research because it is useful in determining the opinion or attitude of a subject. The researcher examined the response pattern and identify irregularities in the completion of questionnaires. A total of one hundred sixty samples were selected, a set of questionnaire comprising limited numbers of questions which was constructed and sent to a total number of one hundred sixty respondents by email, out of which one hundred thirty responded. As a result, the sampling size is fixed as one hundred thirty. The received data and information have been analyzed and conclusion is made on the basis of analysis and interviews accordingly.

3.7.2 Key Informant Interview

Key informant interview is one of the most important and increasingly popular sources of data collection in qualitative case oriented research method. According to Yin, (2003, p. 89) there are two things which are important to an interviewer i.e. to follow own line of inquiry and to ask the actual questions in an unbiased manner. The Key informant interviews were conducted in the year 2020 to seek the primary information in the reservation policy related issues. It was n-depth, unstructured and semi-structured interviews with the help of interview guides were held. Interviews tool was used with those respondents such as secretary level employees who did not prefer to fill up closed questionnaires and they were interested to express their experience, views, and their observations in a verbal form. In total 6 respondents were interviewed whereas two respondents are women, one Adibasi, one Madhesi, one Dalit and one from open competition exam conducted from PSC. However, honesty of respondents and the extent of their information on the phenomena being studied while having interviews is the main challenge to retain validity and reliability of research.

3.7.3 Participant Observation

The logic behind using the given method in the study was to collect the data by watching behavior of the respondents, events, or noting the physical characteristics of the respondents in the natural setting. It was employed during questionnaire survey as well as conducting the interview survey. Therefore, it was carried out in a non-participatory, unobtrusive, and inconspicuous manner as possible.

3.8 Analytical Tools

The collected data and information have been analyzed by using excel and IBM SPSS 25 to deliver the various analytical tools such as tables, percentages, diagrams, charts and so on. Most of the analysis has been conducted in descriptive and narrative ways as most of the data are qualitative in nature and the reason that the whole research study is also based on descriptive and sequential explanatory research project. As the study is more quantitative and qualitative in nature, the hypotheses, which are better arguments than that of test of hypothesis statistically analyzed the basis of primary and secondary data and information.

3.9 Ethical Consideration

Ethical issues in the social science research play an important role in making the research more standard. Conceptually, research ethics refers to the application of moral standards to decisions made in planning, conducting and reporting the results of research studies. David McNabb (2005, p. 55) explains four practical ethical principles: truthfulness, thoroughness, objectivity and relevance. The study would not disclose the information provided by the individual respondents during the interviews with them. The researcher recognizes the confidentiality of the opinion shared by the respondents working in civil service and other organizations. It would not be mentioned the choices made by the respondents in the questionnaire survey individually. The researcher acknowledges the confidentiality of information and opinion provided by the respondents. It would not like to disclose the names and address of the respondents individually who have provided secondary information of civil service, application of reservation policy, and the dynamics of inclusion in the bureaucracy of Nepal. It is ensured that this study does not bring any harm to the informants and individuals who

shared their opinions, provided information, and contributed their knowledge to this study.

3.10 Validity and Verification

Validity is concerned with the measurement of data in a research work. Validity is also related with the integrity of the conclusion that is generated from a piece of research (Bryman, 2003, p.30). Therefore, validity refers to the truth, authenticity and relevancy of data. It also refers to realness of information. It applies to the degree to which data and implications in a research work are correct. Validity of a research depends on how surveys, measurements, case study, interviews, observation, review of documents, or other methods of investigation are designed and carried out in order to collect data in a research. The degree of validity also depends on the techniques of data collection used for measuring social phenomena. Validity is also concerned with whether the instruments or variables chosen to measure a phenomenon actually measure the phenomenon being researched. Validity in social science research consists of a number of facts that premise a logical truth to draw valid research findings.

Verification is an act of verifying information of collected data. It is a confirmation of truth of the data for an evidence of the phenomenon being studied. Verification helps to prove correctness of data in a scientific study. It is also a process of establishing truth, accuracy or validity of information for drawing scientific research findings. Therefore, data verification is a process where the data are checked for accuracy and inconsistencies are verified. The verification of data helps to determine whether the data is accurately translated. In a social science research verification process consists of statistic, structural, and behavioral aspects where it re-examines and testifies the data and findings. Therefore, verification helps to retain validity of research findings.

3.11 Reliability of the Study

Reliability is related to the question of whether the results of a study are repeatable (Bryman, 2003, p.29). Reliability is concerned with the degree to which variables designed to measure a concept hold consistent, stable and repeatable results. Here, reliability of the claimed results of any study can be measured by applying same research methods in the same ways and procedures that produce similar findings. It means same results may be expected from the research work in another time by the application of same process of sampling and study. To this study, reliability of the

findings is maximized through the valid information collected from various respondents at different level who have important role in the process of positive discrimination the application of reservation system.

3.12 Sum up

Research on social phenomena is a complex task. There can be a number of causal variables that affect social events and phenomena. In order to study social phenomena in a systematic way it is required to follow certain research methods to claim our knowledge is scientific. In this chapter, I explained with terms and terminologies used in the qualitative paradigm of research and presented a detailed account of research philosophy, strategy and methodology of conducting my research work. This chapter also explained journey of my research, research design, data collection procedure, data analysis procedure and ethical principles. In addition, I presented how I was guided by my philosophy to go with the dominant mixed research paradigm; which provided me the ground for various data collection and methods for analysis that I used in my research study. This chapter in fact showed the clear picture of my research study thereby directing from all aspects of methodology including data collection and its analysis. Moreover, the discussion of trustworthiness and ethical considerations in qualitative social research imparted in me another new insight for the research work.

CHAPTER FOUR

DATA AND INFORMATION PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

This chapter focuses on analysis and discussion of sequential explanatory data obtained from the field survey and secondary data and information's. The presentation of the interviews facts is tried to relate with immediate socio-economic environment of the study. In this chapter, it is more relevant to discuss the perceptual effects of the policy execution of this concept in the policy level till its application and implementation. For this, I have preferred to review and remark the gist of the constitutions of Nepal and various related acts and regulations. This chapter presents collected data on the basis of which analysis and interpretation has been done. The data was collected by the researcher using the questionnaire survey, interview, and observation methods. In order to achieve the objectives of the study, the perception of civil servants towards the application of reservation system. Then the findings of the dependent variable and independent variable were discussed sequentially with some of the relevant analysis with the help of data table, literatures review, and observation method during the questionnaire survey.

Therefore, quantitative analysis is made on the collected data through the questionnaire to find out the linkage between dependent variable and independent variable. For the quantitative study, the data is processed by the help of statistical tool i.e. excel and IBM SPSS 25 version for the crosstab analysis of perception of respondents towards the reservation system and participant's observation method was followed to explain the fact more judgmentally. The quantitative data is obtained from questionnaire (Likert Scale) survey of the 130 respondents with purposive sampling, whereas the qualitative information is gathered from interviews with quota sampling in the offices of PSC Nepal, OAG Nepal and MoFAGA, Kathmandu Nepal.

4.1 Background

This research is focused on aspects like the extent and the context of the perceptual effects of the reservation system in civil service of Nepal, the implementation experiences with respect to the marginalized communities' participation increased with entry issues and working problems related to the reservation consideration. Therefore, this research study is identifying the current relationship of reasonable participation,

socio-cultural perception, representativeness of the civil service and the performance of the reservation occupied civil servants as independent variables on the basis of the literature review. Each variable is analyzed with the relation to reservation system application of dependent variable separately on the basis of descriptive and sequential explanatory research analysis. Accordingly, the second amendment in the Civil Service act 1993 was made in order to encourage women, Adivasi/Janjati (indigenous/ ethnic groups), Madhesi, Dalit, disabled and people from remote areas. Finally, talking about the implementation of the reservation policy to demand, select and recommend for the recruitment in the civil service, the Nepalese parliament adopted a bill amending the Civil Service Act, 1993 and provided reservation for disadvantaged groups by allocating 45 percent of the jobs in Civil Service and the policy was brought into use since 2007 through Public Service Commission Nepal. The allocation of the quota for including the specified groups by the policy is shown in the table below.

Table 4
Allocation of Quota in Civil Service in Nepal

Groups	Percentage out of 45 percent
Women	33 %
Janajati/ Indigenous groups	27 %
Madhesi	22 %
Dalits	9 %
Physically disabled people	5 %
People from backward/remote regions	4 %
Total	100 %

(Source: Civil Service Act, 2049)

The above table shows that taking 45 as the 100 percent, the quota allocated for reservation of women, Janajati/ indigenous groups, Madhesi, Dalits, physically disable people and people from backward regions are 33%, 27%, 22%, 9%, 5% and 4% respectively. There are, however, some further agreements reached between the government and other groups to make some amendment in the above allocation. But, it is to be borne in mind that the peoples from disadvantaged groups can compete in the free competition as well whereas the people outside the group cannot compete in the reserved quota according to the policy revealed by the PSC. Moreover, to encourage women's participation in Civil Service, the act has fixed the age bar for women to be

40 years whereas the age bar for entry for others is 35 years. Also, for the above categorized groups, the grace period of one year for being the potentially eligible candidates for promotion has been provided.

Eventually, I could reach out to the people representing the high level government positions as well. There, I could understand the need of positive discrimination in Nepal according to which most of Nepalese people are not provided with the equal opportunities to develop themselves. The people I interacted with emphasized the need of reservation for equal opportunity. On the other hand, I came to understand that the concept of affirmative action as a process of Social Integration (Martison, 2005) as well. Moreover, Nepal being a multilingual and multicultural society, there are plenty of nationalities or groups who may also be seeking their recognition and share in the opportunities. This was realized while talking with the research participants who were selected in the reserved seats. The major concern is that how reservation in civil service has been perceived by the actors in the policy level, in the implementation level, some of the social actors such as politicians, journalists, lawyers, and some of the Civil workers.

4.2 Demographic Structure of Gender

Further, “diversity and difference, whether on the basis of race, disability, religion, culture or gender must be recognized and valued” (Freiler, 2003, p. viii). The following table explains the demographic structure of population in Nepal. It shows the composition of male and female in the total demography.

Table 5
Demographic Structure of Male and Female Population

Year	Male	Female	Total
1991	922,0974	9,270,123	18,491,097
	49.87%	50.13%	100%
2001	15,563,921	11,587,520	23,151,415
	49.96%	50.04%	100%
2011	12,849,041	13,645,463	26,494,504
	48.50%	51.50%	100%

(Source: Centre Bureau of Statistics (CBS), 2011)

It shows that the population percentage of male in 1991, 2001 and 2011 were 49.87 %, 49.96 % and 48.50 % respectively. Similarly, female was 50.13 %, 50.04 % and 50.50 % respectively.

% in 1991, 2001 and 2011 respectively. The demographic structure in the three consecutive census clearly reveals that female occupies more than 50% of the total population. It also reflected that gender exclusion was the root cause of poverty and deprivation of social harmony, and inclusion may be one of the best remedies of its alleviation and ownership. There exists a wide gender gap between men and women in all development aspects such as social, economic, political and educational sectors. In the social milieu, the patriarchal tradition has placed males in a superior position bestowing them with all kinds of privileges and powers, which are out of the reach of women (Thapa, 2012).

4.3 The Composition of Respondents:

In order to collect the primary data and information, key respondents have been identified and selected on the basis of quota and judgment sampling method. Then the questionnaires have been sent to them requesting to send their options and views through email providing two weeks' time deadline. The details information about the key respondents is organized in the following table:

Table 6
Detail Description of Respondents

Respondents Community	Educational qualification			Post/Level of Respondents			Age Group		
	Bachelor	Master	Total	Officer	Non-Officer	Total	Before-35	After-35	Total
Open	26	26	52	28	24	52	40	12	52
Women	14	16	30	18	12	30	22	8	30
Adibasi	7	12	19	12	7	19	15	4	19
Madhesi	10	7	17	5	12	17	16	1	17
Dalit	3	4	7	6	1	7	6	1	7
Disable	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1
Remote Area	3	1	4	28	24	52	4	0	4
Total	57	66	130	70	60	130	104	26	130

(Source: Field Survey, 2020)

Table 7
Brief Description of Respondents

Gender Group	Age Group		Belongs Community		Total
	Below 35	Above 35	Open	Reserved	
Male	78	17	54	41	95 (73%)

Female	26	9	1	34	35 (27%)
Total	104 (78%)	26 (22%)	52 (40%)	78 (60%)	130(100%)

(Source: Field Survey, 2020)

In such a way the total numbers of 130 respondents had been selected on the basis of gender group of 95 (73 percent) males and 35 (27 percent) females, age group of 104 below 35 and 26 above 35 and belongs community of open quota 52 and 78 reserved respondents in order to collect wider and representative views so that final conclusion is more authentic and generalized. Apart from these one hundred thirty samples some experts related to the field are also consulted and discussed. So the respondents are found in non-randomly with the portion of 40 percent respondents are from open competition and 60 percent respondents are from the reserved competition in civil service of Nepal.

4.4 Primary Data Presentation and Analysis in terms of Variables

Social phenomena are complex with many variables affecting them that attract our interest for their study. However, our explanations of social phenomena are often inadequate (Ragin, 1989, p.19). In experimental studies, a dependent variable is an outcome factor on which an independent variable is hypothesized and observed to have a particular measurable effect. In theoretical frameworks, an independent variable is the phenomenon which is seen as influencing the relationship with dependent variable. Such relationships cannot necessarily be simply equated with cause and effect, and the direction of causality cannot be assumed. The purpose of this research is to describe and explain primary variance in the research and examines the relationship between the independent and dependent variables based on the questionnaire survey data. Thus, the implementation of inclusive policy in Nepal adopted only social variables even though Civil Service Act has clearly stated to include socially, politically and economically marginalized communities.

4.4.1 Actors of Encouragement to Enter into Civil Service of Nepal

The shares of reserved people in civil service before 2064 BS was very negligible and insufficient in decisional level and operational level of permanent civil servants. Then the policy of reservation theoretically has been making sure to attract, empower and strengthen their prevailing traditional socio-cultural position and made grand provision of reservation system or quota in every advertisement of civil service to increase the

number of what is being today. There can be many sources of encouragement and empowerment personally but the study has made focus on the major actors of encouragement for the empowerment and attraction of marginalized people to enter into civil service of Nepal. The respondents were asked the question "Who firstly encourage you to enter and attract into the civil service of Nepal? The major actors of encouragement for attraction to enter civil service claimed by key respondents can be shown following;

Table 8

Actors of Encouragement of People to Enter into Civil Service of Nepal

Major Factors	Gender Groups		Belongs Community		Total
	Male	Female	Open	Reserved	
Family	28	22	32	18	50 (38%)
Friends	33	8	8	33	41 (32%)
Relatives	19	4	7	16	23 (18%)
Teachers	15	1	5	11	16 (12%)
Total	95	35	52	78	130(100%)

(Source: Field Survey, 2020)

The study out of the total respondents, 28 males and 22 females are encouraged by their family, 33 males and 8 females are influenced by friends, 19 males and 4 females are influenced by relatives and 15 males and one females are influenced by teachers. The data shows 35 open and 15 reserved employees are influenced by family, 11 open and 30 reserved employees are influenced by friends, 7 open and 16 reserved employees are influenced by relatives and 5 open and 11 reserved employees are influenced by teachers. In average 38 percent respondents are influenced by their own family, 32 percent respondents are influenced by their friends, 18 percent respondents are influenced by nearly relatives and 12 percent respondents are influenced and encouraged by their teachers. Being educated and self-capable to perform the influencing power by the family belongs grandfather, grandmother, father, mother, brother, sister whereas friends are school to college peer friends. Relatives belongs to direct relation from the family and teachers are of college and coaching institutes of preparation. The data is also an indicator that encouragement, empowerment and their capacity development in every aspect of life employment is necessary from anywhere

to have knowledge of their own status and situation. According to this survey mostly employees are encouraged by their family and relatives rather than friends and teachers to increase their attraction for the participation into the civil service of Nepal.

4.4.2 The Mechanism to Mainstream the Marginalized Groups

Throughout the discussions, no people were found to advocate completely against the general understanding of the reservation concept. And, no people completely accepted the reservation policy provisions made by the government. Everyone is convinced that this policy is necessary but they have their own arguments for its timely amendments and implementation to uplift of targeted people of the Nepalese society. Nepalese society is much diversified in terms of religion, languages, traditions, conducts, norms, values, customs, beliefs, festivals, economic status and ownership over the personal properties, so very small group of people are exercising the power and facilities of governance and civilization in Nepal. The rural-urban inequalities and remote areas lifestyles is the center of exclusion and need to be mainstream into the governance. After twelve years of implementation, this research is also dealing with various effects of reservation policy into the civil service of Nepal. On this ground, this question is asked to respondents, which is "Do you agree that reservation policy is a main instrument of inclusion to mainstream marginalized community in Nepalese society?" The results of survey are as follows;

Table 9
The Mechanism to Mainstream the Marginalized Groups of Nepalese Society

Particular	Gender Groups		Belongs Community		Total
	Male	Female	Open	Reserved	
Yes	72	33	32	73	105 (81%)
No	18	2	15	5	20 (15%)
Don't Know	5	0	5	0	5 (4%)
Total	95	35	52	78	130(100%)

(Source: Field Survey, 2020)

In this study, 72 males and 33 females are said yes, 18 males and 2 females are selected no and 5 males are selected that they don't know about the question of the reservation policy is a main instrument to mainstream marginalized community in Nepalese society. The data shows 32 open and 73 reserved employees are selected yes and 18

open and 2 reserved employees are selected no and 5 openly selected employees have been selected that they don't know about the question of the reservation policy main instrument to mainstream marginalized community in Nepalese society. This shows that mostly respondents are saying somehow yes of having the reservation policy whereas around 20 percent respondents are saying no to mainstream people through reservation policy enacted by the government of Nepal. In an average 81 percent respondents are selected yes, around 15 percent respondents are selected no whereas 4 percent respondents are selected that they don't know about the question of reservation policy as a main instrument to mainstream marginalized community in Nepalese society. Therefore, this research wants to know whether the reservation policy is mainstreaming the deprived society or not and 81 percent respondents are convinced and 19 percent respondents are not convinced of having reservation policy that has been conducted according to their objectives for inclusive civil service in Nepal. When the respondents have been asked about the reservation system as one of the best policy option to mainstream marginalized group of society into the civil service of Nepal.

4.4.3 Role of Reservation System for the Inclusive Civil Service of Nepal

The poor representation of women, ethnic groups, Madhesi, Dalit, differently able, and backward people in politics and administration justifies that they have been under privileged from state sponsored opportunities. Realizing such fact, for the first time in the history of Civil Service of Nepal, reservation for women, Dalit and ethnic groups was introduced in FY 2064/65. The reservation system has been practiced by PSC Nepal started only from 2007 after being made an amendment in the Civil Service act 1993 was made. The new provision includes 33% for women, 27% for indigenous nationalities, 22% for Madhesi, 9% for Dalit, 5% for differently able, and 4% for backward area within reserved 45% of total vacant posts. After twelve years of implementation of this system, this study realizes to know the perception of employees about the role of reservation system. On this origin, the research question of "How is the role of reservation policy in the transformation of civil service of Nepal? The result of survey are as follows;

Table 10
Role of Reservation System for the Inclusive Civil Service of Nepal

Particular	Gender Groups		Belongs Community		Total
	Male	Female	Open	Reserved	
Very Good	42	28	10	60	70 (54%)
Good	49	6	38	17	55 (42%)
Not Good	4	1	4	1	5 (4%)
Don't Know	0	0	0	0	0
Total	95	35	52	78	130(100%)

(Source: Field Survey, 2020)

In this study, 42 males and 28 females are said very good 49 males and 6 females are selected no whereas 4 males and one female are selected not good and nobody select they Strongly Disagree about the question of the role of reservation system in the transformation Nepalese civil service. Whereas the data shows 16 openly selected and 54 reserved employees are selected very good, 38 open and 17 reserved employees are selected good and 5 openly selected and one reserved employees have been selected not good about the question of the role of reservation policy in the transformation Nepalese civil service. This shows that mostly respondents are saying somehow very good role of reservation policy enacted by the government of Nepal.

In an average 54 percent respondents are selected very good, 42 percent respondents are selected somehow good, it means 96 percent respondents are believing that the affirmative action is leading good role of reservation system in the transformation Nepalese civil service whereas 4 percent respondents are selected that not good about the question of the role of reservation system in the transformation Nepalese civil service. So this research shows that the role of reservation policy is mainstreaming the Nepalese society good or not and 50 percent respondents are selected very good and 40 percent respondents are somehow selected good of having reservation policy that has been conducted according to their objectives of reconcile marginalized group of Nepalese society into the civil service for inclusive governance in Nepal. In Therefore, 96 percent respondents are agreed that the reservation system is playing somehow good role for the inclusive civil service and it would lead to sense of social inclusion and harmony in civil service of Nepal.

4.4.4 Guardian Education of Respondents in the Study

The status of back-warded groups must cover from the initial stage of their education, empowerment, and ownership with the basic consciousness, motivation and interest of attraction among them towards civil service of Nepal. The reform must be started with all terms of policy, institutional, strategically, periodic programs and projects and various incentives to those willing to join the civil service of Nepal. Nepalese society is traditionally most diversified in terms of gender, languages, religions, ownership, class, caste, color and so on which have the pervasive level of inequality in every steps of social behavior that hinders the perception towards the patriotism and nationality. So the family environment leads to complete support and guidance from their own family is the foundation to make attention towards the civil services as professional employment. So the question was asked "what level of education of your guardians/parents have?" then survey data is shown as bellows;

Table 11
Guardian Education of Respondents in the Study

Particular	Gender Groups		Belongs Community		Total
	Male	Female	Open	Reserved	
Higher Degree	12	2	8	6	14(11%)
SLC	16	4	9	9	18(14%)
Literate	53	10	24	38	62(47%)
Illiterate	17	19	11	25	36(28%)
Total	95	35	52	78	130 (100%)

(Source: Field Survey, 2020)

In this research, 14 respondents are having highly educated parents, 18 respondents are having SLC passed parents whereas 62 respondents are having somehow literate parents and 36 respondents are having illiterate parents as an educational background to of civil servants of Nepal. Whereas the data shows 8 openly selected and 6 reserved employees are having highly educated guardians, 9 openly selected and 9 reserved employees are respondents are having SLC or equivalent educated parents and 30 openly selected and 32 reserved employees are somehow literate patents and 11 openly selected and 25 reserved respondents are having illiterate parents that has been diagnosed by the data analysis. This data shows that more than 50 percent respondent's parents are somehow

literate whereas 28 percent respondent's parents are illiterate. In an average 11 percent respondent's parents are highly educated, 14 percent respondent's parents are SLC passed or equivalently educated whereas 47 percent respondent's parents are somehow literate and 28 percent respondent's parents are illiterate. So this research shows that the educational backgrounds is also one of the major foundation to attract in the civil service of Nepal.

However, employees with educated parent lead to effective education and training in cases which such education and training would compete to result in better organizational and individual performance The study represented that the selected civil servants belonged to the same kind of family's members of which were already in civil service because targeted women and deprived people were not able to compete due to lack of education, appropriate culture, and environment required to compete for the exam in the civil service of Nepal.

4.5 Categorical Data Analysis: Likert Scale Questionnaire Survey

The questionnaire form is development with Likert Scale to find the perceptual effects of policy beneficent. The most widely used is the Likert scale. Likert-type scales are frequently used in social sciences research. It is developed in 1932 by Rensis Likert to measure attitudes. In an ordinal scale, responses can be rated or ranked, but the distance between responses is not measurable. The Likert scale measurement is same as 4 points Likert scales measurement was completely (1) strongly agree, (2) agree, (3) disagree and (4) strongly disagree. This question that goes either way that is linked with intermediate agreement answer options. These questions are used to measuring customer satisfaction about the subject matter. The reason it is named as such is that the user is forced to form an opinion and there is no safe 'neutral' option. Therefore, the data collected from the questionnaire survey is analyzed as following;

4.5.1 Representativeness of Civil Service of Nepal

This amendment in the Civil Service act 1993 seems to have brought a remarkable change and is considered as a milestone in making Civil Service inclusive. The general assumption of representative bureaucracy is good to be provided and will eventually lead to more qualified decision-making in the public sector, more effectively implemented policies, better-served and more-satisfied clientele groups, not to speak of better motivated and more innovative staff. We seem to be on relatively safe ground to

assume that the positive effects of ‘representativeness’ and ‘workforce diversity’ on organizational performance is highly contingent on task-specific features, institutional characteristics and employee-related properties of public organizations. In this section, representativeness related questions was asked to respondents and provided them with set of five closed ended question. Further, on the basis of this data, the respondents were asked the five questions about the representativeness of civil service of Nepal. The data as a response of the respondents are as follows;

Table 12
Representativeness of Civil Service of Nepal

Questions	Options/Coding				Total
	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	
Do you agree that.....					
The Constitution of Nepal-2015, ensure that more opportunities to women and disadvantaged group into governance of Nepal.	43	82	3	2	130
The reservation policy is only one alternative to mainstream of women and disadvantaged people into the civil service of Nepal.	6	27	66	31	130
The reservation policy has been playing crucial role in promoting social justice of the women and disadvantaged people of Nepal.	33	88	7	2	130
The reservation policy has been building the foundation of balancing equality and equity for stimulating social integration of targeted people.	36	85	7	2	130
The actions of positive discrimination is unable to recover the highly disadvantaged people of Nepal.	23	55	44	8	130

(Source: Field Survey, 2020)

The above table illustrates that among 130 respondents, somehow all respondents i.e. (125) 96% agree about first question of the Constitution of Nepal-2015, ensure that more opportunities to women and disadvantaged group into governance of Nepal whereas 4% disagree about it, on this ground constitution of Nepal ensures the prior opportunities to deprived people of Nepal. In second question, majority of the respondents i.e. (97) 75% disagree about the reservation policy is only one alternative to mainstream of disadvantaged people into the civil service while only 25% agree about it, it means there can be more options of inclusion into the civil service. In third question, almost all respondents i.e. (121) 93% agree about the reservation policy has

been playing crucial role in promoting social justice of the disadvantaged people of Nepal whereas 7% disagree about it, on this ground reservation policy is establishing social justice of the disadvantaged people of Nepal. In fourth question, all respondents i.e. (121) 93% agree about the reservation policy has been building the foundation of balancing equality and equity for stimulating social integration of targeted people whereas 7% disagree about it. In fifth question, majority of the respondents i.e. (78) 60% agree about the actions of positive discrimination is unable to recover the highly disadvantaged people of Nepal while 40% disagree about it, this data shows that the quota system is not still reaching the actual targeted candidates and people according to the policy objectives.

In this regard, the majority of respondents are agreeing about the today's provision of inclusion of deprived people into the civil service of Nepal. So, it is also clear from the literature review that Ferdous, (2015) argues that the validity of some part of quota system has been challenged taking into consideration the provisions of the Constitution that guarantees equal opportunity of employment for all inhabitants and avoids discrimination against "any backward section of citizens" and particularly women but there is no definite technique which was specified by the Constitution to attain the satisfactory representation of diverse groups in society especially in the civil service.

4.5.2 Participation of Reserved People in Civil Service of Nepal

According to the census of 2011, the population of women (51.50%) in Nepal is greater than population of male (49.50%). In this section, participation related questions were asked to respondents and provided them with set of five closed ended questions. The concept of inclusive bureaucracy, equal and reasonable participation in decision making, the responsive governance and gender equity is mostly pronounced in today's political environment as well. Representative bureaucracy can contribute the effective public service delivery and all sector of the society is culturally diversified but mentally integrated for the national building and getting the sensational achievement in the field of governance and long run development. That's why the equitable participation of reserved people into civil service is enormous for the inclusive and sustainable development of Nepalese public bureaucracy. Also, Haque, (2003) cited in Kabir, (2015) highlighted that the validity and trustworthiness of democracy will be in question if women, who constitute half the population, remain absent from the decision-making institutions of a society. Further, on the basis of this data, the respondents were

asked the five questions about the meaningful participation of women and other deprived people imperious for civil service of Nepal. The data as a response of the respondents are as follows;

Table 13
Participation of Reserved People in Civil Service of Nepal

Questions	Options/Coding				Total
	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	
Do you agree that.....					
Women and marginalized people don't have sufficient participation in the Nepalese civil service according to their total population size.	102	22	3	1	130
The increasing numbers of marginalized people is enhancing the sense of their recognition and ownership into the civil service of Nepal.	52	70	7	1	130
Women and disadvantaged people participation increase the voice of voiceless and develop the new diversified ideas into civil service of Nepal.	35	78	14	3	130
The changing environment with unprivileged people into civil service is changing the employee friendly infrastructure into your organization.	12	35	79	4	130
The participation of women and reserved people is leading the application of inclusiveness and belongingness in civil service of Nepal.	54	62	11	3	130

(Source: Field Survey, 2020)

The above table illustrates that among 130 respondents, almost all respondents i.e. (124) 95% agree about first question of the Women and marginalized people don't have sufficient participation in the Nepalese civil service according to their total population size whereas 5% disagree about it, on this ground there should be proportionate participation of disadvantaged people into the civil service according their population. In second question, 52 respondents are strongly agreeing and 70 respondents are agreeing, i.e. (122) 94% about the increasing numbers of marginalized people is enhancing the sense of their recognition and ownership into the civil service of Nepal whereas 6% disagree about it. In third question, majority of the respondents i.e. (113) 87% agree about the women and disadvantaged people participation increase the voice of voiceless and develop the new diversified ideas into civil service of Nepal whereas 13% disagree about it, on this ground except some critics, increasing number of deprived people are somehow dealing their neglected voiceless voice into the civil

service of Nepal. In fourth question, majority of the respondents i.e. (83) 64% disagree about the changing environment with unprivileged people into civil service is changing the employee friendly infrastructure into your organization whereas 36% agree about it, according to third data most public organization are not women and disable friendly infrastructures. In fifth question, majority of the respondents i.e. (116) 89% agree about the participation of women and reserved people is leading the application of inclusiveness and belongingness in civil service of Nepal while 11% disagree about it, according this data participation of reserved people into the decision making level of governance leads to inclusion and harmony with civil service delivery. In this regards, Kabir, (2015) also mentions that without active participation of women and disadvantaged people incorporation at all levels of decision-making, the goals of equality, improvement and reconciliation cannot be achieved. So this research claims that the need of women and deprived people participation in civil service is very necessary for enhancing the sense of their recognition and ownership into the civil service of Nepal.

4.5.3 Perception towards Reservation into Civil Service of Nepal

Controversies over who should benefit are likely to lead to a perception of affirmative action as a policy effects which benefits some, while being a burden to others. This affirmative action is implemented in the allocation of scarce resources for diverse demand in the field of employment. As their availability is limited, the allocation of jobs to some will mean exclusion of others. This will invariably lead to conflict about the application of reservation system into the civil service of Nepal. In this section, perception related questions was asked to respondents and provided them with set of five closed ended question. In addition, Selden (1997) cited in Bradbury & Kellough, (2008) also concluded that attitudes, beliefs, and values lead, for some public administrators, to the formation of a "minority representative role perception" that, in turn, leads to the formation of decisions consistent with minority interests. Further, on the basis of this data, the respondents were asked the five questions about the perception of civil service. The data as a response of the respondents are as follows;

Table 14**Perception towards Reservation into Civil Service of Nepal**

Questions	Options/Coding				Total
	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	
Do you agree that.....					
The dominance of upper class Khas/Arya male employees is reducing and balancing after the acting of reservation system into the civil service.	4	83	40	3	130
The old age civil servants are biased of having and supporting the employees from reserved quota in your public organization of civil service of Nepal.	44	69	13	4	130
The people from reservation are biased to utilize minimum resource and facilities regarding their position and professions in the workplace.	9	28	80	13	130
Family relation and caste belongingness differs the behavior in the workplace that discourage the lower caste civil servants.	49	74	4	3	130
The Government of Nepal should continue the reservation system implementation for one another decade to recover the targeted potential people.	25	96	6	3	130

(Source: Field Survey, 2020)

The above table shows that among 130 respondents, the majority of the respondents i.e. (87) 67% agree about first question of the into dominance of upper class Khas/Arya male employees is decreasing and balancing with female employees after the application of reservation system into the civil service whereas 37% disagree about it, on this ground the hegemony of high class elite male employees is somehow balancing after the participation of female and reserved people in civil service of Nepal. In second question, majority of the respondents i.e. (113) 87% agree about the old age civil servants are biased of having and supporting the employees from reserved quota in your public organization of civil service of Nepal while only 13% disagree about it, it means the old age employees are biased for supporting the reserved facilitated employees into the civil service of Nepal. In third question, majority of the respondents i.e. (93) 72% disagree about the people from reservation are biased to utilize minimum resource and facilities regarding their position and professions in the workplace whereas 28% agree about it, on this ground there is not that much discrimination using resources and facilities regarding the position and professions. In fourth question, most of all respondents i.e. (123) 95% agree about the family relation and caste belongingness

differs the behavior in the workplace that discourage the lower caste civil servants, while only 5% disagree about it that's why data shows that caste and caste relation differs the interpersonal relation and behaviors in civil service. In fifth question, majority of the respondents i.e. (121) 93% agree about the Government of Nepal should continue the reservation system implementation for one another decade to recover the targeted potential people while 7% disagree about it, this data shows that the quota system should retain to recover targeted candidates and deprived people according to the policy objectives.

4.5.4 Performance of Disadvantaged Employees in Civil Service of Nepal

The performance of civil servants in Nepal has been a major public concern and civil service of Nepal has been characterized by low work performance and poor service delivery. Beside that this research wants to find out that how is the performance situation of reserved people comparing others. Whatsoever, regarding the inclusion in Civil Service, it seems that there is prevalence of negative attitude towards entire performance of the beneficiaries from reservation; and a kind of discrimination is prevailing because of their socio-cultural outlook and impression also into the civil service of Nepal. However, it is not possible to change a whole structure overnight; so, this initiative taken by the government has brought some positive impact in making a bureaucracy somehow representative one. Therefore, on the basis of this performance and practice, the respondents were asked the six questions about performance in civil service. The data as a response of the respondents are as follows;

Table 15
Performance of Women and Deprived Employees into Civil Service of Nepal

Questions	Options/Coding				Total
	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	
Do you agree that.....					
The people from the reservation are still not regarding the key actor in decision making and top levels like CDO and CAO.	12	92	22	4	130
Male civil servants have more superiority complex and negative attitudes in workplace towards female regarding information sharing about the service.	49	68	10	3	130
The people from reservation are not capable to delivering the quality service in comparison with other people in workplace.	3	22	87	18	130

The potentials and possibilities of energetic reserved employees are somehow not motivated to explore and implement their action in public organizations.	16	74	35	5	130
Very low performance and bad experiences exist with the service seekers from reservation facilitated employees.	2	5	87	36	130
Male civil servants are more risk taker and optimistic to settle down the emergency difficulties than female civil servants	19	88	22	1	130

(Source: Field Survey, 2020)

The above table illustrates that among 130 respondents, the majority of the respondents i.e. (104) 80% agree about first question that the people from the reservation are still not regarding the key actor in decision making and top positions like CDO and CAO whereas 20% disagree about it, on this data ground there is still the lack of trust and practice to have best performance of reserved people but nowadays many women are starting to lead the district and local level organizations. In second question, majority of the respondents i.e. (117) 90% agree about the male civil servants have more superiority complex and negative attitudes in workplace towards female regarding information sharing about the service while only 10% disagree about it, it means there is still the male dominance performance system into the civil service of Nepal. In third question, majority of the respondents i.e. (105) 81% disagree about the people from reservation are not capable to delivering the quality service in comparison with other people in workplace whereas 19% agree about it, on this data ground the people from the reservation are not that much poor in performance with the conducive working environment. In fourth question, majority of the respondents i.e. (90) 69% agree about the potentials and possibilities of energetic reserved employees are somehow not motivated to explore and implement their action in public organizations whereas 31% agree about it, it means that civil service is very close elite system to restrict the individual possibilities. In fifth question, almost all respondents i.e. (123) 95% disagree about the very low performance and bad experiences exist with the service seekers from reservation facilitated employees while 5% agree about it, this data shows that the quota facilitated employees are not as blamed in market but they are trying to deliver more citizen friendly services. And, in sixth question, majority of the respondents i.e. (107) 82% agree about the male civil servants are more risk taker and optimistic to settle down the emergency difficulties than female civil servants while 18% disagree about it, on this data ground due to the male friendly bureaucratic system the female

employees are taking risk taker but this perception is gradually changing into the civil service of Nepal.

Therefore, the quality performance is determined merely by the working environment, decision discretion, resources, authority, supportive environment, past experiences, and so on. So the impact of reservation policy is the inclusion of reserved people into civil service to deliver the gender friendly, disable friendly, language friendly, cultural friendly and citizen friendly public services. The male dominance civil service of Nepal is slowly becoming democratic, inclusive and responsive after the participation of women and other disadvantaged people. Traditional and close chain of command system is not easily excepting the new paradigm shift but nowadays women and other disadvantaged people are getting the role of secretary, CDO and CAO of civil service of Nepal. Similarly, the performance is measured on the basis of perception of the respondents towards the learning and adjusting, decision making, and level of performance capabilities of the respondents.

4.5.5 Individual Effects of Reservation System into Civil Service of Nepal

Affirmative action appears to have had positive supplements in that an increasing number of public servants are able to communicate in the variety of languages that clients speak and have a greater understanding of the needs of the sections of communities who were neglected under discrimination. This section examine that the individual factor of the respondents has relationship with the reservation system. This study refers how the respondents perceive about confidence, personal values and belief, skills and potential and motivational factor, which are regarded as strong determining factor to achieve the desired objectives in the respective organization. Based on these key points, five of questions related to the individual factor are asked to the respondents. But in the questionnaire these questions are set in the statement form with closed ended question. Therefore, on the basis of this performance and practice, the respondents were asked five questions about representation of civil service of Nepal. The response of the respondents is presented as following table;

Table 16
Individual Effects of Reservation System into Civil Service of Nepal

Questions	Options/Coding				Total
	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	
Do you agree that.....					
The reservation facilitated civil servants are not that much confident to take responsibilities rather than other.	3	9	91	27	130
The reservation facilitated civil servants are more absent and not interested to provide service rather than other.	2	3	98	27	130
Special subsidies and facilities for female and disable civil servants are lacking in the working environment.	33	91	5	1	130
The result merit of PSC can measure the quality of performance in the field of desired public employees.	1	2	53	74	130
The PSC examinations and process of selection are capable of determining merit of competent candidates.	3	47	78	2	130
The opportunities provided by your public organization are fair enough to enhance your skills and potentials.	4	47	68	11	130

(Source: Field Survey, 2020)

The above table illustrates that among 130 respondents, the majority of the respondents i.e. (118) 91% disagree about first question that reservation facilitated civil servants are not that much confident to take responsibilities rather than other open merited employees whereas 9% agree about it, on this data ground there is still the lack of confidence to take all kind of responsibilities in the workplace. In second question, most all respondents i.e. (125) 96% disagree about the reservation facilitated civil servants are more absent and not interested to provide service rather than other while only 4% agree about it, it means they are always punctual even in difficult situation of civil service of Nepal. In Third question, almost all respondents i.e. (124) 95% agree about the special subsidies and facilities for female and disable civil servants are lacking in the working environment whereas 5% disagree about it, it show there is no women and disable friendly workplace. In fourth question, almost all respondents i.e. (127) 98% disagree about the result merit of PSC can measure the quality of performance in the field of desired public employees whereas 2% agree about it, on this data ground the people from the reservation cab be the best performer with the conducive working environment. In fifth question, majority of the respondents i.e. (80) 62% disagree about the PSC examinations and process of selection are capable of determining merit of competent candidates whereas 38% agree about it, it means todays merit system is

somehow being capable of determining merit. In Sixth question, most respondents i.e. (79) 61% disagree about the opportunities provided by your public organization are fair enough to enhance your skills and potentials while 39% agree about it, so, we can say that current opportunities provided by your public organization are still not fair and more influential. It means the respondents are able to utilize their own potential whatever the opportunities the organizations are provided to them and the respondents are fully benefitted by it and it is very helpful to enhance their capacity.

4.5.6 Organizational Effects of Reservation System into Civil Service of Nepal

In Nepali society, even today social and cultural impediments also did not allow many women to do any outside work; they were expected to remain at home and do only household chores (Paudel, 2017). Here an organizational factor refers to the rule based procedures, structures and complex working procedures, centralized decision making practice to deliver every action and service, performance challenges, performance, attitudes, and satisfaction level of the respondents towards the organizations. On the basis of the given key factor, the perception of the respondents was analyzed. Along with it most of the women and reserved employees have a positive opinion about the organizations they serve, and they seem quite satisfied with the notion that their contributions and achievements are recognized by their organizations. Regarding the representatives of the organizations, the organizational consent and acceptance is necessary for their participation Based on these key points, five of questions related to the individual factor are asked to the respondents. But in the questionnaire these questions are set in the statement form with closed ended question. Therefore, on the basis of this performance and practice, the respondents were asked five questions about representation of civil service of Nepal. The response of the respondents is presented as following table;

Table 17

Organizational Effects of Reservation System into Civil Service of Nepal

Questions	Options/Coding				Total
	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	
Do you agree that.....					
The reservation system is a main interruption for safeguarding general standard of merit in civil service.	8	33	79	10	130
Male are good learner, adjustable and decision maker than female employees in the civil service of Nepal.	2	26	79	23	130

The working space, working channel and working pattern are male friendly in your public organization.	32	85	9	4	130
The working pattern of civil service is manmade, which is obstacles to deliver motivated service particularly for the women and disadvantaged employees in the office.	28	95	4	3	130
The reservation system helps to explore more diversity and more ideas from different socio-cultural employees.	29	98	2	1	130

(Source: Field Survey, 2020)

The above table illustrates that among 130 respondents, the majority of the respondents i.e. (89) 69% disagree about first question that the reservation system is a main interruption for safeguarding general standard of merit in civil service whereas 31% agree about it, on this data ground, the reservation system is not regarded obstacle of standard of merit. In second question, most respondents i.e. (102) 79% disagree about the male are good learner, adjustable and decision maker than female employees in the civil service of Nepal while only 21% agree about it, it means female employees are also good learner and adjustable in civil service of Nepal. In third question, almost all respondents i.e. (117) 90% agree about the working space, working channel and working pattern are male friendly in your public organization whereas 10% disagree about it, on this data ground the working environment of civil service is more male oriented. In fourth question, almost all respondents i.e. (123) 95% disagree about the working pattern of civil service is biased which is obstacles to deliver motivated service particularly for the women and disadvantaged employees in Nepal whereas 5% agree about it, it means today's working pattern is so traditional and elite friendly. In fifth question, almost all respondents i.e. (127) 98% agree about the reservation system helps to explore more diversity and more ideas from different socio-cultural employees while 2% disagree about it, so, the affirmative action in Nepal is leading inclusive and unity in diversity in civil service in public organization.

Interview No. 1

Two female Section Officer of MoFAGA shared her views on her own words;

.....Yes, it is very positive environment of attraction after the application of reservation system for participation of underprivileged people in the civil service because of having seat for provisioned people motivated to employ into government job. Democracy demands the equal participation in every level of governance, that's why affirmation action is very necessary to reconsider the isolated people in

Nepalese society from the history. It creates the different ideas to make decision with the more opportunities with permanent nature of civil service. It should make more criteria to attract targeted people to participate in civil service. Meritocracy doesn't mean to measure the competence and the pace in performance in the organization. It provides the gender and ethnic friendly look to workplace for that base biasness and discrimination can be eradicated after all. Working condition is not that much prioritize to perform the job according to the provision, where as we are biased to give the full top responsibility and authority for the decision making. The positive effect is that it promotes the isolated people but negative effect is that it somehow hampers the equal competition for the job. I don't know any bad experience with service seeker yet but I feel they are so satisfied with me. Besides this, the people are still not even known about the government permanent employment in remote area and deprived communities and they completely behind the coverage of government, so I think the reservation policy must be carried on until the isolated and very remote area of Nepal for further years, (Interview, 2020/01/20)

The women and disadvantaged people in Nepal are traditionally and systemically biased and undermined from the ancient time and they are supposed to limit into the house, family settlement and domestic agricultural activities. The time changes and they are now conscious of their potentiality and psychological strength to fight against injustice and hegemony of male leadership in all sector. The concept of inclusive bureaucracy, equal and reasonable participation in decision making, the responsive governance and gender equity is mostly pronounced in today's political environment as well. Representative bureaucracy can only contribute the effective public service delivery and the overall sustainable development of nation. All sector of the society is culturally diversified but mentally integrated for the national building and getting the sensational achievement in the field of governance and long run development. That's why the equitable participation of women in civil service is rigorous for the inclusive and sustainable development of country which contributes to socio-economic advancement and empowerment of the marginalized communities.

According to the data of PSC Nepal, the shares of reserved people in civil service before 2064 BS was very negligible and restricted in decisional level and operational level

permanent professionals' civil servants. Then the policy of reservation has been developed linking with the concurrent constitution to make sure to empower and strengthen their prevailing traditional socio-cultural position and mainstream into the governance of Nepal. Government of Nepal has made provision of reservation seat or quota in every advertisement of civil service to increase the number of what is today. The reservation policy supports the concepts of inclusive development by ensuring enhanced participation of those left behind from nation building process. The basic foundation of reservation system is to minimize the inequality prevailed on the basis of cast, sex, religion, among others. From the above analysis it is also said that it contributes in socio-economic development of the country. Reservation system might be an effective tool to attract a group of people towards the secured and prestigious civil services but without adopting the required inclusive measures in order to enhance the people capabilities. Therefore, the reservation system in civil service accumulates the recognition and participation of women and deprived people thereby it leads to contribute inclusive development of civil service of Nepal. Therefore, reservation system ensures the equity in social improvement process.

4.5.7 Data Analysis and Discussion of Independent Variable: Crosstab Analysis

The independent variable of the study is Representativeness, Participation, Perception and Performance. Perceptual data of respondents is collected and measured by using 4 points Likert scale measurement as Strongly agree-(1), Agree-(2), Disagree-(3) and Strongly disagree-(4). Further, this scale is specially recoded for the agreement tabulation in 4 scale measurement as Strongly disagree (1), Disagree-(2), Agree-(3) and as Strongly agree-(4), in this case the no respondents don't have the choice to remain silent or neutral to giving their perception. Further, there is used the IBM SPSS 25 version and excel sheet for the calculation and analysis and this 4 point Likert scale is recoded in two scale measurement as strongly disagree plus disagree equal to 1(Disagree) and agree and strongly agree equal to 2(Agree) whereas there is no case that the respondents compulsorily give opinion and no way for giving their opinion. The following section sections deals with the relationship between dependent and independent variable through bivariate analysis. The Chi-square test is used to determine if there is a significant relationship between two nominal (categorical) variables. The frequency of each category for one nominal variable is compared across the categories of the second nominal variable. The researcher did the study of Civil

Service Act-1993 and Constitution of Nepal which ensures the opportunity of participation and equitable excess into the civil service of Nepal. The responses of the respondents were taken in 4 point Likert scale measurement because all respondents are the direct and indirect beneficiaries of affirmative action/ reservation system in the civil service of Nepal.

4.5.7.1 Effects of Gender, Age and Education into the Civil Service of Nepal

This study deals with the relationship of gender, age and education with the. Though there are many factors which comes under Scio-demographic factor, but here the researcher has only taken gender, age, educational qualification, and entry level position of the respondents as important variable for desired study. Therefore, the relationship between Scio-demographic factors with the inclusiveness is listed in the given table.

Table 18
Effects of Gender, Age and Education in Inclusiveness of Civil Service

Variables		Inclusiveness of Civil Service of Nepal				
		Number of Respondents	Percent (%)		Chi-Square Test	
			Agree	Disagree	Value	Sig. Level
Gender	Male	95	79	21	9.732	0.021
	Female	35	62	38		
Age Group	Before 35	104	74	45	.676	0.879
	After 35	26	77	33		
Educational Qualification	Bachelor	57	71	29	6.333	0.378
	Master	66	79	21		
Level/position	Officer	70	76	24	3.252	0.354
	Non-Officer	60	73	27		

(Source: Field Survey, 2020)

The first variable which is gender. The given table shows the relationship between gender and inclusiveness. There are altogether 130 respondents, when gender and representativeness is crosstab, then the given table shows that 62% of female respondents agree that gender has more to deal with inclusiveness while in case of male respondents only 79% of the respondents agree about it. The bivariate analysis of the given table shows that when gender and inclusiveness was crosstab than we got the value of chi square as 9.732 and $p = 0.021$ which means that there is high relationship between this two variable and are statistically significant at 0.05. From this analysis,

we can conclude that there is strong relationship between the gender of the respondents and inclusiveness and plays the crucial effects into the sense of inclusion.

Khadka & Sunam (2018) in their paper "Workforce diversity and reservation policy in Nepal: A strategic approach to strengthening women's voice and visibility in formal employment sector" has presented that Nepal's good policy measures of gender and social equality, affirmative action policies have not only increased women's representation and visibility in government employment and the employment in development industries, it has also created opportunities for women to express their voices in their organizations which can potentially make a difference in development and institutional transformational process in the country's federalization systems. However, it is not enough just to have women's engagement in the public service their effective participation in policy making and decision-making need to be reinforced through gender awareness training, gender budgeting and gender mainstreaming training and other mechanisms that policy making and the allocation of resources is gender responsive.

The second variable is age. Here in the survey the age of the respondents is collected in years than it was classified into age group between before 35 and after 35. In order to see how the age affects the notion of representativeness, the bivariate analysis is used. From the above table, it is clear that maximum number of respondents belongs to before 35 age group and 55% of the respondents agree that age have crucial role in the inclusiveness of civil service of Nepal. The bivariate analysis of the given table shows that there is no relationship between age of the respondents and the inclusiveness. When age and inclusiveness was crosstab than the findings indicate that the given variable are not statistically significant at 0.05 (chi square 0.676 and $p = .879$). It means age doesn't matter in case of inclusiveness.

Interview No. 2

One Section Officer of PSC shared his views on his own words;

.....it is very different situation after the inclusion as a level of participation has been increasing after execution of reservation system, I also participated in civil service because of having more opportunities with permanent nature, I think it should be corrected with more clarity of reservation criteria of targeted people to

participate, their participation in the organization realizing the diverse and friendly look to workplace. Besides this, merit is somehow biased with them but their performance in my organization is satisfying. They are less believed than other to give the full responsibilities and this mindset is slowly changing, number is increasing but the targeted/expected people are still behind the coverage, so the level of performance is progressively increasing compared to last few years, (Interview, 2020/01/16)

In the survey, the third variable is education, there are 57 respondents who have bachelor degree and 66 respondents who have master degree. Here, in this survey who have minimum qualification (i.e. 75%) agree that minimum requirement of education have crucial role in inclusiveness than in comparison to those who have master degree. The reasons may be as the level of the education is determining factor for the upward movement of the respondents and it can also provide more opportunities in comparison to the less educated person. Above the given table of bivariate analysis shows that the education and inclusiveness are not statistically significant as the value of chi square is 6.333 and $p = .378$. It indicates that both the variable has no relation at all. It can be interpreted in such a way that the minimum educational qualification for the gazette post is bachelor degree and only that candidate will apply for the job. Therefore, the foremost requirement is bachelor degree but if some have the master degree it will be the plus points for the new candidates for upward movement easily than those who have only bachelor degree. Therefore, the entry level positions of the respondents do not have much to deal with the inclusiveness.

In the given survey, the fourth variable is position and 70 respondents are gazetted officer posts while only 60 respondents enter through non-officer. Similarly, the nature of agree and disagree between gazette and non-gazette officer differs slightly so it can be interpreted in this way that the reservation system has been very helpful and the target group have been able to come into mainstreaming while some of the respondents do not agree on it. Due to this policy, many disadvantage groups are able to get full benefit from it. Likewise, in the survey 78 respondents have entered the civil service regarding the benefit of inclusiveness. In this regards, one of the major reasons behind this may be some of the respondents has been benefited by this policy and they are able to enter in the civil service in the gazette and non-gazette posts. When the entry level position

of the respondents and inclusiveness was crosstab then the findings were its chi square value is 3.252 and p is 0.354, which means that these variables are not statistically significant. It means entry level position do have much more to deal with the inclusiveness as the desired people have already enter in the civil service whether from the gazette post or from non- gazette post. Therefore, the upward movement of their career entirely depends upon him/her competences.

In this discussions, there exists a wide gender, caste and regional gap between men and women in all development aspects such as social, economic, political and educational sectors. it has been most pronounced about who are targeted people and whether the targeted people are included by the policy or not? The need of this policy was felt and brought for the purpose of realizing social inclusion into the civil service of Nepal. But few people are not happy with the implementation part of the policy as the real targeted people are not being included and problems of the real targeted people are still in exclusion. But, according to the previous discussions, in the name of those marginalized and deprived people, the elites of those groups are taking the benefits.

4.5.7.2 Individual Effects of Reservation System in Nepal

This study examines that the individual effects of the respondents has relationship with the representativeness, participation, perception and performance or not. Individual effects in the study refers how the respondents perceive about individual attitude, personal values and belief, skills, potential and motivational efforts, which are regarded as strong determining factor to achieve the desired targets in the respective public organization. It means the respondents are able to utilize their own potential whatever the individual opportunities the organizations are provided to them and the respondents are fully benefitted by it and it is very helpful to enhance their capacity. Based on these key points, six set of question related to the individual effects are asked to the respondents. The questions are set in the statement form with closed ended question to make the agreement. The overall bivariate analysis examines the relationship between the reservation system and its individual effects are highlighted in the following table.

Table 19

Individual Effects on Reservation System in Civil Service of Nepal

Variable		Individual Effects		Total	Chi Square Test	
		Disagree	Agree		Value	Sign Level
Representativeness	Disagree	20%	26%	23%	13.942	0.124
	Agree	80%	74%	77%		

Participation	Disagree	0%	6%	3%		
	Agree	100%	94%	97%	27.511	0.001
Perception	Disagree	0%	34%	17%		
	Agree	100%	66%	83%	10.494	0.312
Performance	Disagree	60%	18%	39%		
	Agree	40%	82%	61%	32.056	0.000
Total		100%	100%	100%		

(Source: Field Survey, 2020)

According to the above given table, the first variable shows the relationship between representativeness and its individual effects. In case of level of confidence, nearly majority respondents i.e. 77% agree that they are very important that the reservation system gives the sense of their value into the civil service of Nepal and this is very helpful for the representative civil service but whereas 23% disagree. The major reasons behind the representativeness and individual effects is to integrate and cope social diversity of every reserved people for the competition, preparation with the proper subsidies and facilities and equal opportunities that they are representing to achieve their individual desired goals. Here, the bivariate analysis of the given table also supports the discussed argument and shows that there is no significant relationship between representativeness and its individual effects in. Similarly, the calculated value of chi square is 13.942 and $p=.124$, which shows somehow less significant relationship but at the same time the 23% of the respondents agree that individual factors like level of confidence, educational achievement, motivation that plays very crucial role in the achievement of the persons desired targets.

Interview No. 3

One Nasu (Gazette-I) of PSC (Janajati) shared his views on his own words;

.....it is very necessary in Nepal to incorporate inclusion because we are extremely exploited from Hindu hegemony and High class emperor since its history. Now we are somehow mainstreaming from primitive indigenous to differently identified into the governance from 2064. I think we should be participated into the government affairs and decision making that's why we should be motivated to participate into all level not only in civil service. Reservation system is playing very crucial role to make civil service gender and ethnic friendly and feel them a part of bureaucracy. Only merit doesn't mean to treat the quality of service delivery I think it is an irony to dominate the voice of inclusion into the civil service. Somehow we are treated the

second class employee in terms of giving official facilities and opportunities as well as they don't completely believe on us to give top level responsibilities and decision making authority. I'm working in non-gazetted level and we are increasing in numbers into civil service. I think we are more friendly and open than old age high class employees whereas service seeker is also more satisfied with us then their interest and behaviors. I believe that the elite group of high class people are fully playing and advocating against affirmative action in leading very ridicules idea of merit but I should be inevitably implemented for further five to ten years, (Interview, 2020/01/21)

The second variable shows the relationship between participation and its individual effects. In case of level of reasonable participation, almost all the respondents i.e. 97% agree that they are high participation promotes the individual recognition and ownership into the civil service of Nepal whereas 3% disagree. The major reasons behind the participation is to attract the individual into the mainstreaming and feel them into the inclusion and belongingness of governance of Nepal. Here, the above table also supports that there is significant relationship between participation and individual motivation and attraction for the long recognition and ownership into the civil service of Nepal. Similarly, the calculated value of chi square is 27.511 and $p=.001$, which shows somehow strong and significant relationship that's why almost all 97% of the respondents agree that participation of reserved people attract, give respect and opportunities for the positive individual perception of motivation which empower the disadvantaged people into the civil service of Nepal.

The third variable shows the reservation perception and individual effects. In case of level of positive attention, nearly most respondents i.e. 83% agree that they are very high level of dominance of upper class male civil servants, biasness of old age employees, behavioral discrimination and perceptual diversity lead to individual effects into the civil service of Nepal. Here, above table also supports the discussed argument and shows that there is no significant relationship between reservation/inclusion perception and individual effects into the civil service. Similarly, the calculated value of chi square is 10.494 and $p=.312$, which shows somehow less significant but at the same time the 17% of the respondents disagree that individual factors like elite justice, social discrimination, poor educational background, low

motivation from the society, etc. plays very crucial role in the achievement of the personal interest into the civil service of Nepal.

The fourth variable shows the relationship between performance of reserved people and its individual effects. In case of equal treatment and support, most of the respondents i.e. 61% agree that they are high performance with equal responsibilities and leadership promotes the individual recognition and ownership into the civil service of Nepal whereas 39% disagree. The major reasons behind the performance is to treat equally, support equally, behave equally to individual into the working environment and motivate them to take challenge with their full authority and supervisor support into the civil service. Here, the above table also supports that there is significant relationship between participation and individual motivation and attraction for the long recognition and ownership into the civil service of Nepal. Similarly, the calculated value of chi square is 32.056 and $p=.000$, which shows somehow strong and significant relationship that's why most 61% of the respondents agree that performance of reserved people to deliver public service competently that positively attract and effects every individual of disadvantaged people into the civil service of Nepal. This result is focused with deprived individual social and symbolic bonds which is economic, institutional, and individually significant and normally tie with the individual disadvantaged people of society into the civil service of Nepal.

4.5.7.3 Organizational Effects of Reservation System in Nepal

Here, this study examines an organizational effects refer to the administrative culture, structure, chain of command, professionalism, rules and regulation, job recognition, participation, performance, attitudes, and challenges of the respondents towards the organizations. In addition, Reskin (1998) has identified the additional benefits of proactively preventing discrimination, and increasing organizational diversity to enhance creativity, innovation, and organizational success. On the basis of the given key variables, the perception of the respondents was analyzed, which are regarded as strong determining factor to achieve the desired targets in the respective public organization. It means the respondents are able to utilize their own potential whatever the organizational opportunities are provided to them and the respondents are fully benefitted by it and it is very helpful to enhance their capacity. Based on these key points, five set of question related to the organizational effects are asked to the

respondents. This bivariate analysis deals with relationship between the reservation system application and its organizational effects are highlighted in the following table.

Table 20
Organizational Effects on Reservation System in Civil Service of Nepal

Variable		Organizational Effects		Total	Chi Square Test	
		Disagree	Agree		Value	Sign Level
Representativeness	Disagree	0%	44%	22%		
	Agree	100%	56%	78%	33.715	0.000
Participation	Disagree	46%	7%	26%		
	Agree	54%	93%	74%	50.313	0.000
Perception	Disagree	31%	11%	21%		
	Agree	69%	89%	79%	15.904	0.069
Performance	Disagree	46%	17%	31%		
	Agree	54%	83%	69%	13.260	0.151
Total		100%	100%	100%		

(Source: Field Survey, 2020)

According to the above given table, the first variable shows the relationship between representativeness and its organizational effects. In case of reservation system, nearly majority respondents i.e. 78% agree that the policy is very crucial weapon to recover the deprived people to make the civil service more representative more deliberative during their organizational framework whereas 22% disagree to make them inclusion. The major reasons behind representativeness and its organizational effects is to make habitual those respondents who have strong aspiration and expectation, proper subsidies and facilities and equal opportunities to achieve their individual desired goals. Here, the bivariate analysis of the given table also supports that there is strong and significant relationship between representativeness and its organizational effects in civil service. Similarly, the calculated value of chi square is 33.715 and $p=0.000$, which shows somehow very significant relationship that the respondents agree that until the representativeness promotes the uncovered and reserved candidates into the civil service for the national socio-cultural harmony, bureaucratic democracy and gender, caste and regional inclusion into the organizational structure and it plays very crucial role in the socio-cultural achievement for inclusive civil service of Nepal.

Interview No. 4

One Director of OAG, Nepal (Dalit) shared his views on his own words;

.....this time is the most favorable time after the application of reservation policy to motivate into the civil service of Nepal and it has been the foundation to attract and participate deprived people into governance. It is giving the great contribution to make civil service more inclusive. Merit is only voice of favoritism and nepotism of the dominance community and it also doesn't mean to measure the performance and quality service delivery. My family and friends have been very happy of my selection in civil service. I have found normal working environment whereas I becomes usually an option to get extra facility and opportunity in office. We are normally biased to get extra challenging role of top position whereas. It should be focused to targeted people to educate, empower, and develop capacity to remote inhabitant isolated people in Nepal. I have good experiences with all service seeker but many bad experiences within office close system and dominated people and to make it fairer treatment reservation system must be remained until they cannot be increased as the population size. (Interview, 2020/01/22)

The second variable shows the relationship between participation and its organizational effects. In case of level of decisional participation, mostly respondents i.e. 74% agree that they are high level of participation promotes the organizational inclusion, rule and regulation adaptation, decisional ideas for the complex problem solving of socio-cultural debates and disputes settlement into the civil service system of Nepal. The major reasons behind the participation is to maintain the performance standard, make learning, adjustable and motivated civil servants to accept the gender, caste and disable friendly working environment into civil service of governance of Nepal. Here, the above table also supports that there is strong and significant relationship between participation and organizational inclusion and very supportive and friendly working behaviors into the civil service of Nepal. Similarly, the calculated value of chi square is 50.313 and $p=.000$, which shows somehow strong and significant relationship that's why most 74% respondents agree that participation of reserved people have the strong value to make the working environment of civil service more friendly, supportive and inclusive structure to give respect and opportunities for the organizational democracy which motivate the disadvantaged people into the civil service of Nepal.

Interview No. 5

One Section Officer of OAG, Nepal (Madhesi) shared his views on his words;

.....this condition is the very encouraging after the commencement of reservation policy into the civil service of Nepal to participate from the Terai region and it became the groundwork to mainstream Madhesi people into decision making level of bureaucracy. It has given the great opportunities to inter not only into civil service but also in different government services. Merit is not the issue to pronounce and downsize the voice of disadvantaged peoples to cover into the civil service who are historically exploited and isolated from the nation's benefits. My community has become very happy of my selection in civil service. I have found biased working environment in terms of sharing information and I used to feel they are somehow discriminating by saying and behaving for the facility and opportunity in office. We are normally biased to give the role of top decision making position. It should be continued to attract the still deprived youth people of Terai.(Interview, 2020/01/24)

The third variable shows the reservation perception and its organizational effects. In case of level of positive attention, nearly most respondents i.e. 79% agree that they are very high level of representation of disadvantaged people into the civil service is helping to balance the dominance of Brahman and Chhetri's male civil servants, biasness of office system, physical discrimination, caste hegemony and perceptual unacceptance to public organization that leads cooperative organizational effects into the civil service of Nepal. Here, above table also supports the discussed argument that there is no significant relationship between reservation/inclusion perception and its organizational effects into the civil service. Similarly, the calculated value of chi square is 15.904 and $p=.069$, which is more than 0.05 and it shows somehow less significant between them but at the same time the 21% of the respondents disagree that organizational factor like elite capture system, discrimination office culture, low motivating outlook of public organization are still exist into the public bureaucracy and that be the challenge and hindrance in the achievement of inclusive and representative civil service of Nepal.

The forth variable shows the relationship between performance of reserved people and its organizational effects. In case of equal treatment and support, most of the respondents i.e. 69% agree that they are performance of reserved facilitated employees with the equal responsibilities and leadership role promotes the organizational recognition and reward into the civil service of Nepal. The major reasons behind the

performance is to teach equally, support equally, behave equally into the office working environment and motivate them to take crucial challenges with the full authority and supervisor support into the civil service. Here, the above table also supports that there is no significant relationship between performance of women and deprived people and its organizational compliance but for the effectiveness of civil service there should be first representation of targeted people of reservation system into the civil service of Nepal. Similarly, the calculated value of chi square is 13.260 and $p=.151$, which shows somehow less significant relationship between the performance and organizational structure that's why most 31% of the respondents agree that performance of reserved people is not the matter but initially they must be incorporated into the civil service system to deliver performance regarding public service competently that positively effects of deprived people into public organization of civil service of Nepal. Observing the effects of affirmative action can provide useful guidance on what contributes to public organizations' performance. For example, increasing functional diversity, merit-based selection and employees' morale are all supposed to improve organizational performance. Through increasing social diversity, affirmative action also promotes functional diversity (Schneider and Northcraft, 1999). So, the performance of organizations implementing affirmative action should improve over time of policy.

4.6 Published and Unpublished Secondary Data presentation and Analysis

This study focuses on the assessment of implementation position of the reservation system in Nepalese civil service. Further this studies tries to examine the fulfillment of objective of legal provision of inclusion policy implementation in the civil service of Nepal, through the analysis of available ten to twelve years' secondary data published by Public Service Commission and Ministry of General Administration then (MoFAGA now), Department of Personnel Records and Public Service Commission(PSC).

4.6.1 Current Status of Reservation System in Civil Service of Nepal

The reservation policy in public service is adopted with the objective of (i) creating a representative public service (ii) mainstreaming excluded people from different class groups, caste/ethnic groups, regions and communities, and engaging them in nation building activities (iii) projecting existing public service scenario, and (iv) narrowing down the gap between the dominant and excluded groups (Awasthi & Adhikari, 2012). Reservation is a form of affirmative action designed to improve the participation of

under-represented communities defined primarily by gender, caste, backwardness and disability. Reservation based on gender, caste, backwardness and disability are laws both Constitutional and statutory. The advent of democracy in 1951 ushered in many changes in Nepal. Until then the demand for inclusion was part of and perhaps overshadowed by the broader civil rights movement. Democracy brought with it equal rights for all citizens regardless of gender or other forms of social grouping.

In this chapter, the current status of reservation system and its practices were analyzed. Though, a gap in the implementation of the policy is seen, there is some room for contentment as the process of including and recruiting the excluded groups through Public Service Commission has begun. Small amounts of secondary data were analyzed. This analysis helped me to study the overall trend of the affirmative policy implementation in Civil Service. The issues on the inclusiveness in the Nepalese Civil Service were analyzed and these are more likely to be addressed for the reduction of exclusion from the Civil Service. For this reason, the reservation policy has been implemented in Nepalese civil service since 2064 through the amendment in the civil service act 2049. The constitution of Nepal gives the mandates to make special provisions by law for the protection, empowerment or development of the citizens including socially or culturally back warded classes. So the trend and current condition of implementation in civil service of Nepal since F/Y 2064/065 to onward. Finally, I have presented the scenarios of representation since last twelve years. That can be shown as bellow;

Table 21
Current Status of Reservation System in Civil Service of Nepal

Fiscal Year	Open Quota	Employees Selected from Reserved Quota						Total
		Women	Janajati	Madhesi	Dalit	Disables	Remote	
2075/076	2394	625	509	409	168	95	77	1883
2074/075	4007	1088	858	711	292	163	132	3244
2073/074	5273	1383	1026	901	385	189	142	4026
2072/073	3300	797	629	503	213	101	95	2338
2071/072	2783	639	547	454	168	95	76	1979
2070/071	2767	626	509	384	173	91	71	1854
2069/070	1707	372	318	254	106	51	35	1136
2068/069	1805	352	280	212	99	40	30	1013

2067/068	2487	471	371	300	105	59	43	1349
2066/067	2080	495	368	319	142	64	43	1431
2065/066	840	117	94	91	36	15	12	365
2064/065	2228	366	245	183	84	33	17	928
Grand Total	31671	7331	5754	4721	1971	996	773	21546

(Source: Public Service Commission, 12 years Reports, 2077)

In this table, out of the 88,325 civil servants of Nepalese bureaucracy are mostly diversified in terms of their socio-economic occupancy and cultural traditions from the ancient times. In the early stage of Nepalese civil service was dominated by the very limited group of the Nepalese society. In the Rana regime there was existence of spoil system and completely committed to emperor at this time. According to the Public Service Commission, 31671 employees are recruited by openly quota competition whereas 21546 employees are recruited from reserved quota competition since F/Y 2064/065 and that consists of 7331 women, 5754 Adibasi/Jangati, 4721 Madhesi, 1971 Dalit, 996 disables, 773 remote area's employees since 12 years. In an average of 12 years' data shows that out of 100 percent employees, 60 percent employees are selected from open quota whereas 40 percent employees are recruited from reserved system.

4.6.2 Comparison of Post Advertisement Portion After 12 Years of PSC

The application of reservation policy in the civil service is somehow representing the inclusiveness of diversified society of Nepal. So the comparison of advertisement and post of different two years is analyzed below;

Table 22

Comparison of Advertisement Portion After 12 Years (F/Y 2064/65 and 2075/76)

S.N.	Particulars	2064/065		Percent	2075/076		Percent
		Adv. No.	Post No.		Adv. No.	Post No.	
1.	Open Competition (x)	396	2228	70.60%	36	2394	55.97%
2.	Reservation Competition						
	a) Women	189	366	11.60%	25	625	33.19%
	b) Adibasi/Janajati	118	245	7.76%	24	509	27.03%
	c) Madhesi	88	183	5.80%	23	409	21.72%
	d) Dalit	74	84	2.66%	16	168	8.92%
	e) Disables	31	33	1.05%	8	95	5.05%

f) Remote Area	16	17	0.54%	6	77	4.09%
Reservation Total(y)	516	928	29.40%	102	1883	44.03%
Grand Total (x+y)	912	3156	100%	138	4277	100%

(Source: Public Service Commission, 2065-2076 Reports)

Before the description of table, the constitution of Nepal has recognized the spirit of diversity of gender, caste, culture, geography and religion. So after the second amendment of Civil Service Act, 2049 made in 2064 according to the Interim constitution 2063, the segregated percentage of open competition and reserved competition was very differentiated with the legal provision like 70.60 percent open competition and 29.30 percent reserved competition in 2064/065 but the after 12 years the provision is enacted with 55.97 percent for open competition and 44.03 percent for reserved competition with different categories such as women, Janajati, Madhesi, Dalit, disable and remote area. That's why the today's civil service is becoming somehow inclusive and representative with number increment of marginalization community.

4.6.3 Gender Differences after 12 Years in Different Level Civil Service of Nepal

The table below reflects the of number of civil servants in the FY 2064/065, before the implementation of reservation policy and in the FY 2075/076 after the decade of the implementation of reservation policy, in gazetted, non-gazetted and classless level⁶ presenting both excluding and including health service and judge. The table is the comparison of number of civil servants in the FY 2064/065, before the implementation of reservation policy and in the FY 2075/076 after the decade of the implementation of reservation policy. The following table explains the comparative number of existing civil servants in terms of gender in the year 2064 and 2077 in the federal, state and local level civil service of Nepal.

Table 23
Gender Differences after 12 Years in Different Level Civil Service of Nepal

Class	2064/65					2076/77				
	Men		Women		Total	Men		Women		Total
	Number	%	Number	%		Number	%	Number	%	
Chief Secretary	1	100	0	0	1	1	100	0	0	1
Special Class	60	100	0	0	59	67	95.71	3	4.29	70
Gazetted First	463	94.88	25	5.12	488	522	92.88	40	7.12	562

⁶ Nepal Civil Service Act, 1956 grouped government employees into gazetted, non-gazette and classless posts. A gazette post refers to all those posts advertised by government notification in the *Rajpatras*, the government gazette

Gazetted	3160	95.18	160	4.82	3320	2985	92.02	259	7.98	3244
Second										
Gazetted Third	9537	89.77	1087	10.23	10624	8357	84.17	1578	15.83	9929
Non-gazetted	23963	85.78	2973	14.22	27936	21106	80.99	4953	19.01	26059
Classless	17705	95.25	1487	7.75	19192	11667	90.55	1218	9.45	12885
Health Service	11557	59.44	7885	40.56	19442	13676	58.2	12620	41.8	26296
Justices/judges	298	97.39	8	2.61	306	335	93.84	22	6.16	357
State/Local level	0	0	0	0	0	6689	75.05	2224	24.95	8913
Total	66743	82.03	14625	17.97	81368	65405	74.06	22917	25.94	88316

(Source: Department of Civil Personnel Records, Hariharbhavan, Lalitpur, ashadh 2077)

Before the implementation of reservation policy in 2064/065, the representation of female in special class was zero. In first class was 5.12 percent, in second class was 4.82percent, in third class was 10.23 percent, and in non gazetted first class 14.22 percent. Excluding health service and judge, in gazetted level, 90 % were male and 10 % were female. In non gazetted level, 88 % were male and 12 % were female. The total participation of male was 89 and female was 11 % excluding health service and judge. In health service, in the FY 2064/065, the representation of female was around 41%. The percentage of participation in the health service in comparison to the civil service shows higher because some of the posts like staff nurse, assistant nurse midwife in the health service are only for women. In Judiciary service, 97.39 % male and very negligible 2.61 % female were judge. The total participation of female in the civil service including health and judge service is 18 %.

After the twelve years of implementation of reservation policy in 2076/077, the representation of female in special class is 4.29% in first class is 7.12%, in second class is 7.98 %, in third class was 15.83%, in non gazetted first class 19.01% and in non gazetted second class is 17.45 %. Excluding health service and judge, in gazetted level, 87 % were male and 13 % were female. In non gazetted level, 87 % were male and 13 % were female. The total participation of male was 87 % and female was 13 % excluding health service and judge. The representation of female in health service increased to 40 % from 41% and judge is 4%. The total participation of female in the civil service including health service and judge is 24%. The comparative table shows that before the implementation of reservation policy, in the F/Y 2064/065, excluding health service and judge, the total participation of female in the civil service was 11% and after the decade of the implementation of reservation policy, in the F/Y 2076/077,

the total participation of female is 13%. Including health service and justice, the total participation of female in the civil service was 18% and after the decade of the implementation of reservation policy, in the F/Y 2076/077, the total portion of female is 25.94%. Excluding health service and judge, the percentage growth of female in the twelve years' period is 3%.

4.6.4 Caste/ethnic Breakdown of Civil Servants in Civil Service of Nepal

After the second amendment of the Civil Service Act 1993, the number of women civil employees is increasing. But most of these women belong to Bahun and Chhetri castes. A distant second portion of women belong to Adivasi/Janjati and backward areas. But participation of Madhesi and Dalit women is virtually nil. To ensure inclusion of women belonging to marginalized and backward communities in proportion of their populations, an amendment of the Act is made in 2007. Then the participation of marginalized community in civil service takes place and they started to attract in the government employment through the second amendment in 2064. The following table presents the existing posts for inclusive group. After the implementation of reservation policy in practice with the aim of bringing the inclusive group in the civil service.

Table 24
Caste/ethnic Breakdown of Civil Servants in Civil Service of Nepal

Caste/ Ethnicity	Classless	Non- gazzated	Gazatted			Special Class	Chief Secretary	Total	%
			Third	Second	First				
Dalit	842 (2.75%)	569 (1.93%)	175 (1.20%)	17 (0.48%)	2 (0.38%)	–	–	1605	2.036
Janajati Newar	2046 (6.67%)	1838 (6.23%)	1361 (9.35%)	376 (10.71%)	56 (10.61%)	5 (10.20%)	–	5682	7.21
Janajati Tharu	1215 (3.96%)	818 (2.77%)	347 (2.38%)	27 (0.77%)	1 (0.19%)	1 (2.04%)	–	2409	3.056
Other Janajati	4213 (13.74%)	2001 (6.78%)	706 (4.85%)	97 (2.76%)	14 (2.65%)	1 (2.04%)	–	7032	8.92
Madhesi	4697 (15.31%)	4105 (13.91%)	2731 (18.75%)	363 (10.34%)	53 (10.04%)	1 (2.04%)	–	11950	15.18
Muslim	196 (0.64%)	140 (0.47%)	106 (0.73%)	20 (0.57%)	5 (0.95%)	–	–	467	0.60
Khas/Arya	17463 (56.93%)	20049 (67.92%)	9130 (62.72%)	2610 (74.36%)	397 (75.19%)	41 (83.67%)	1 (100%)	49691	63.02

Total	30672 (38.90%)	29520 (37.44%)	14556 (18.46%)	3510 (4.45%)	528 (0.69%)	49 (0.062%)	1	78836	100
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(Source: Department of Civil Personnel Records, Hariharbhavan, Lalitpur, June 2016)

Dalit community cover for 13 percent of Nepal’s population, but their share in civil service is very low. They constitute only 2.036% of civil employees, with 2.75% in classless, 1.93% in non-gazetted, 1.2% gazetted third class, 0.48% in gazetted second class, 0.38% in gazetted first class and 0% each in special class and chief secretary. Muslims have the lowest share in civil service. They constitute only 0.6% in civil service with 0.0064% in classless, 0.47% in non-gazetted, 0.73% gazetted third class, 0.57% in gazetted second class, 0.95% in gazetted first class and 0% each in special class and chief secretary. Ethnic breakdown of civil employees shows Nepal’s civil service is dominated by Bahun and Chhetri. Among Adivasi/ Janajatis, Newars are ahead with 38% share. Among Madhesi, high-caste people from the Tarai are ahead of other Madhesi ethnic groups. Share of Madhesi Dalit's participation is virtually nil. Dalit and Muslims fare worse in terms of their shares in civil service. Nepal’s ethnic diversity is not reflected in civil service. It has been a decade since Nepal adopted a policy of reservation to promote inclusion, but the government still lacks official figures about representation of various ethnic groups in civil service. The Ministry of Federal Affairs and General Administration has recently begun an assessment of the impact of the reservation policy, though. If the government has willingness to prepare ethnicity-wise data of civil employees, it may not be an uphill task. But as a result of dominance of a certain group, the government is just not willing to prepare ethnicity-wise data of civil employees.

4.6.5 Ten Years Gender Differences in Civil Servants after Reservation

The following table presents gender differences in terms of number of civil servants after the implementation of reservation policy from the fiscal year 2066/067 to 2075/076.

Table 25

10 Years Gender Situation Analysis in Civil Servants after Reservation

Fiscal Year	Male		Female		Total
	No	%	No	%	

2066/067	66357	85.45%	11303	14.55%	77660
2067/068	67075	86.16%	10773	13.84%	77848
2068/069	67928	85.33%	11679	14.67%	79607
2069/070	67834	84.95%	12017	15.05%	79851
2070/071	67381	84.03%	12806	15.97%	80187
2071/072	67226	82.33%	14424	17.67%	81650
2072/073	67231	80.76%	16014	19.24%	83245
2073/074	67682	77.85%	19260	22.15%	86942
2074/075	68518	76.40%	21169	23.60%	89687
2075/076	65419	74.06%	22906	25.94%	88325

(Source: Department of Civil Personnel Records, Hariharbhavan, Lalitpur, Asar 2077)

The above table shows the number of male and female civil servants in the civil service after the implementation of reservation policy from the fiscal year 2066/067 to 2075/076. In 2066/067 the percentage of male was 85.45 % and female was 14.55 %. Then the share of female in the 2067/068, 2068/069, 2069/070, 2070/071, 2071/072, 2072/073, 2073/074, 2074/075 and 2075/076 has been gradually increasing like 13.84%, 14.67%, 15.05%, 15.97%, 17.67%, 19.24%, 22.15%, 23.60% and 25.94% respectively. Coming to the year 2075/076, the participation of male was 74.07 % and female was 25.94%. Before the reservation policy implementation, the female participation was 11% at the end of Ashadh, 2065. The pattern of female participation is in gradually increasing form after the implementation of reservation policy and they are now advocating and empowering their own right and employment independently. Here, the analysis is made with gender differences in the various professional services in the civil service of Nepal according to Civil Service Act⁷, 2049 and Regulation, 2050.

Table 26

Participation of Male and Female in Different Services in Civil Service

S.N.	Services	Male	Female	Total	Male %	Female %
1	Nepal Economic Planning and Statistics Service	346	50	396	87.37	12.63

⁷ There are 12 services including Health and Parliamentary service. There are separate acts for health and parliamentary service while Civil Service Act, 1993, governs other ten professional services.

2	Nepal Agriculture Service	3640	696	4336	83.95	16.05
3	Nepal Administrative Service	28066	5154	33220	84.49	15.51
4	Nepal Forestry Service	4805	618	5423	88.60	11.40
5	Nepal Education Service	1307	303	1610	81.18	18.82
6	Nepal Health Service	13985	12879	26864	52.06	47.94
7	Nepal Miscellaneous Service	1903	1426	3329	57.16	42.84
8	Nepal Engineering Service	7121	876	7997	89.05	10.95
9	Nepal Justice Service	3156	722	3878	81.38	18.62
10	Nepal Foreign Service	228	63	291	78.35	21.65
11	Nepal Audit Service	328	55	383	85.64	14.36
12	Nepal Parliament Service	196	41	237	82.70	17.30
13	Constitutional Representatives	338	23	361	93.63	6.37
Grand Total		65419	22906	88325	74.07	25.93

(Source: Department of Civil Personnel Records, Hariharbhavan, Lalitpur, Asar 2077)

The above table also demonstrates the number of male and female civil servants in various services in the civil service in the Nepal after the implementation of reservation policy from the fiscal year 2075/076. In Nepal planning and statistics service the percentage of male was 87.37% and female was 12.63% whereas in Nepal agriculture service the percentage of male was 83.95 % and female was 16.05%. In Nepal administrative service the percentage of male was 84.49% and female was 15.51% whereas in Nepal forestry service the percentage of male was 88.60% and female was 11.40%. In Nepal education service the percentage of male was 81.18% and female was 18.82% whereas in Nepal health service the percentage of male was 52.06 % and female was 47.94%. In Nepal miscellaneous service the percentage of male was 57.16% and female was 42.84% whereas in Nepal engineering service the percentage of male was 89.05 % and female was 10.95%. In Nepal justice service the percentage of male was 81.38% and female was 18.62% whereas in Nepal Foreign Service the percentage of male was 78.35% and female was 21.65%. In Nepal audit service the percentage of male was 85.64% and female was 14.36% whereas in Nepal parliament service the percentage of male was 82.70 % and female was 17.30% and constitutional representatives having 93.63% male and 6.37% female participation. In average the participation of male was 74.07 % and female was 25.94% in 2077. Before the reservation policy implementation, the male participation was 89% and female participation was 11% at the end of Ashadh, 2065. The pattern of female participation

is highest in health 48% and in miscellaneous 43% in comparison of other services in the civil service of Nepal but in an average the attraction and competition is gradually increasing after the implementation of reservation policy. The share of women in civil service is somehow increasing but it is not sufficient to empower them in terms of their population and socio-economic situation.

4.6.6 Regional Caste Participation in Civil Service of Nepal

The following table demonstrates the representation of major casts in civil service. It encompasses Brahmin, Chhetri, Indigenous, Dalit from Hill and Terai, Newar, Muslim and others.

Table 27
Regional Caste Representation in Civil Service

SN	Caste	Percentage	Index
1	Hill Brahmin	39.00%	1.0000
2	Hill Chhetri	22.30%	0.9719
3	Terai Brahmin, Chhetri	3.30%	1.0000
4	Terai others	9.70%	0.3851
5	Hill Dalit	0.90%	0.0978
6	Terai Dalit	0.50%	0.2474
7	Newar	9.00%	0.4227
8	Hill Indigenous	9.00%	0.4382
9	Terai Indigenous	4.60%	0.4227
10	Muslim	0.70%	0.1574
11	Others	0.4%	0.6073

(Source: TU, Department of Sociology, 2071/072)

This table describes about the participation in the civil service on the basis of caste, based on the research study done by the Central Department of Sociology, Tribhuvan University in 2014. The table shows that the Hill Brahmin, Hill Chhetri, Hill Indigenous and Newar are the major caste representing in civil service. Terai (others) are also in mark able numbers but the real target group of inclusion of Hill and Terai minorities and marginalized representation are still very low in number in comparison to the Hill Brahmin.

4.7 Sum-up

This study has been identified the three major independent variables which are representativeness of civil service, perception towards the reservation system, participation and performance of reservation facilitated people in civil service of Nepal. As the data are mostly qualitative and interpretative in nature that is classified in such a way that the respondents are strongly agree, somehow agree, disagree and strongly disagree and the description has been made on the basis of the table and numbers of respondents. If we look after the data individually and in average figure all arguments are accepted which is also accepted by the secondary data. On the basis of the primary and secondary data and their result all hypothetical statements about the reservation system as a policy instrument is not the best or single option for ensuring the proportionate representation and dignity of marginalized communities in civil service of Nepal but the educational programs, empowerment activities, trainings, playing dramas in their own languages and financial subsidies to reach to the point of qualification of enrollment in examination of civil service of Nepal. The gender discrimination and caste untouchability of socio-cultural factors which are the chronic disease to distract and hinder the career development of disadvantaged people of our society. It is also accepted that the application of reservation policy has been advocated to some extent of merit based bureaucracy with the equitable opportunities for the competition of competent candidates.

The hypothesis has been made in the first chapter and according to the primary and secondary data and information analysis here we can say that higher the representation of disadvantaged people, the higher is the recognition for quality performance in the civil service through the reservation policy in Nepal. Whereas higher the participation of deprived section of society in civil service of Nepal, the higher is the ownership over the governmental activities and operation of public bureaucracy in Nepal. And if there is higher positive perception and attitude towards civil servants from the reservation system, the higher is the individual motivation and trustworthiness in the civil service of Nepal. Whereas higher the effective performance monitoring of reserved facilitated civil servants, the higher is the positive outcomes and implementation impact of reservation system in Nepal. The good governance seeks to overcome this inherent limitation by opening wider avenues for participation of individuals in governing the government. It encourages participation-driven model of Nepalese governance down to

the level of the individual to ensure that all citizens have a representation and voice in government decision-making. Governments engage with citizens in one form or another at various stages of policy and service development.

The factor of socio-economic deficiency or lack of economic ownership as a financial background of weaker section of society is automatically stopped the aspirants to gather the proper education, qualifications and family support for the entire consideration. So, after the long history of revolution against the prevailing elite system in Nepal recalls the constitutional provision (Interim constitution, 2063 and new constitution of Nepal, 2072) and legal consideration (Second amendment of Civil Service Act, 2049 in 2064/65) for the equitable right to the huge deprived sectors population of Nepal to be a part of the whole governance system and reasonable public service delivery from the accessible location. Then the political will and commitment has been included into the constitutional and legal inductions and its timely amendments. The role of monitoring and executing institutions of reservation system in Nepal are firstly the Government of Nepal (MoFAGA) and Public Service Commission Nepal which are playing the somehow primary executing role of implementation of affirmative action and inclusiveness to uplift the numerical increment of employees belongs to poor, customarily dominated and exploited community and remote areas. But the monitoring institutions such as parliamentary different committees, thirteen constitutional bodies and judiciary are very passive and weak in this subject matter.

Therefore, development of marginalized community can be the foundation of grass root development of country. One of the most important aspect of culturally back-warded people's development is their equitable participation and recognition into the civil service for the nation building through diversity management. The equitable representation in civil service is very much important for inclusive and sustainable development of society. These issues and hindrances must be addressed to ensure their enhanced and ultimately equitable entry into the civil service and mainstream into the governance of Nepal. So the reservation policy is one of the frequent used policy options in developing as well as developed countries as it gives quick outcomes. But it is just an option of inclusiveness and there are other ways to ensure equitable entry such as the overall development of education as well as quality education, personality development, positive attitude towards government of Nepal and promoting the equal

and equitable opportunities that can be other effective options. The issues of complete merit based bureaucracy is somehow retained by PSC different examination and equitable access of deprived peoples into the civil service. To include the individuals in government decision-making in civil service to promote long term sustainability by community ownership over federal to local undertakings. Since for operational reasons, working partnerships are biased towards organized groups, many citizens remained far removed from the activities of the federal government. Building a sense of community ownership over resources could help to release new ideas and practices about how they might be put to best use into the workplace of public organization of Nepal.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY, MAJOR FINDINGS AND CONCLUSION

This chapter consists of the summary, major findings and conclusion of this research on current situation of reservation policy and its perceptual effects in civil service in Nepal. The concept of inclusion and affirmative actions does not have a longer history in Nepal. Despite its short history, it has become very popular in Nepal and worldwide scenario in the present context. In Nepal, the concept has been incorporated and implemented in the government recruitment system through PSC Nepal. However, my research is focused to examine the effects of reservation policy in Civil Service in Nepal. The concept of inclusion in this context is usually found to be used as quota or reservation (Aarakshan). It was found welcoming in one way and also perceived as matter of discrimination in the working environment among the civil servants especially between the beneficiaries from free competition and reservation. This chapter explains the overall summary and major findings of the study derived from the analysis of the collected data corresponding to my research work which is entitled below;

5.1 Summary of the Study

The concept of inclusiveness in general and public sectors is relatively a new concept in civil service of Nepal. The actors involving in governance have diversified and issues to be dealt are also being complex, rigid and dangerous existed in contemporary Nepalese socio-cultural environment. Among various function of actors and institutions, civil service is one of the vital pillars of good governance all governing activities. The main function of bureaucracy is to implement the all plans and policies of the government with full commitment and devotion for the nation. The basic idea behind the formation and its timely reform of bureaucratic structures is to provide stable and sustainable government.

The first chapter contains statement of problems, objectives, and significance and research questions as well. The main purpose of my study was to analyze the existing situation of reservation policy in Civil Service of Nepal and to explore the associated challenges and opportunities as well as the perceptions of the civil servants and the beneficiaries. In short, my main purpose was to study the policy and effects of

affirmative action in the Civil Service of Nepal. And regarding the research questions, it comprises main questions which were designed to address the research problems.

In the second chapter, it consists of the significant knowledge construction by reviews of the literatures relevant to my research study. From the collection of my materials, I sorted more relevant literatures which were mostly related to the context of developing countries and a few related to the Nepalese context as well. In this chapter, I usually am trying to find the theory of social inclusion and affirmative action while surfing and browsing the internet. But, I couldn't find original developed as a theory itself. Later, however, I could find so many related theories to it. It consists of the theory of empowerment, representative theory, theory gender equality, social integration, the theory of social justice and so on. All the theories were found to be related to my research study to some extent. Furthermore, I found some intersecting space among all these theories in relation to reservation system.

In chapter three, there is dealing with the research methodology. Being a social science researcher, I have concentrated and presented reality of the understandings of reservation policy in Civil Service of Nepal by the mixed method. Additionally, I also used some secondary data which helped me quantitatively analyze the trend, its present status and also the effects of affirmative action in Nepal. I have mentioned how the policy of affirmative action developed the space in Nepalese context. I have taken the references of the constitutions of Nepal. I found Kathmandu as the most appropriate study area for it is the working place of most of the actors such as policy makers and implementers of reservation policy. My research participants and respondents are the policy beneficiaries along with the formal and informal interview and in depth interview focused with the major consideration of study.

In chapter four, I am focused myself on the policy effects and perception that is related to reservation system in civil service of Nepal. This chapter mainly contains the emergence of the policy through making amendment in the Civil Service act 1993 for the second time in 2007 and its consequences. There are various questions subject about the inclusiveness, affirmative actions, gender equality, equitable participation motivation, recognition, representation, empowerment, reservation system and its effectiveness into the questionnaire form. The contradiction between the affirmative action and the merit of bureaucracy is today's concern but they are not absolute rather

than relative from each other. After the collection of the data from rigorous effort of months, the collected data was managed in systematic way in excel and SPSS for the presentation and analysis. During analysis, the references were taken from various sources. In this regards, both qualitative and quantitative method were used during the data presentation and analysis.

The second amendment in Civil Service Act, 2049 in 2064 BS is said that this provision will be improvement after 10 (Ten) years but 12 years' time completed. In this regards the maximum respondents are also realizing the timely reform or practical amendments in the provision of reservation in the Civil Service Act of Nepal. They claim that the reservation policy is somehow playing the positive role only in recruiting and numerical representation but also reasonable quality education, awareness programs like road drama, role play, social media awareness, trainings, coaching classes, special classes, individual, family and community counseling programs, motivational campaigns, positive attitude oriented seminars, empowerment activities, outing exposures, travelling, field visit and proper guidance about the government employment. They believe on that targeted people are still not in coverage of governing jurisdiction of action after 12 years of application whereas the very limited elite people, family members and urban inhabitants of reserved or marginalized community. The government should have the very practical and effective plans, programs and projects to mainstream the really isolated and deprived children, women, indigenous people, landless and houseless poor people, Dalit family, Madhesi women and Madhesi Dalit in the new consideration of inclusive government. There should be options of reservation policy made according to the SWOT analysis of social, cultural, economic, financial, political, administrative, academic access, geographical, psychological phenomenon of targeted people of Nepalese society. The Legal provisional remedies of Governance Act, 2064 and Muluki Ain, 2074 should be dispersed to the rural and remote area's citizens and aspirants to make them aware of their more opportunities.

Inclusion desires to bring public administration closer to the people. Behind them is also the desire to effect positive improvements in service delivery. If representative activate in dynamic terms, bureaucracy can be close the democracy. Unfortunately, the term representativeness has been understood in reservation terms. Representation is about diversity of people, of values, of capabilities. Reservation and representation are

not synonyms. They never were and never will be in future. Understanding reservation in terms of compensation for past discrimination can also prohibit more fruitful discourses about. No one is standing for compensation around here. All of us are after something important to do in life, after developing ourselves to our own potential, after realizing our own agency to represent with their best. All issues that have a bearing on the purpose should be discussed and resolved to allow going forward. Representative bureaucracy, especially in its active form, is certainly one of the right issues to lead deliberative bureaucracy.

5.2 Major Findings of the Study

The Interim Constitution, 2063 provisions and Civil Service Act 1993 (second amendment in 2007) has made a provision for reservation system in 2064 BS. Before this reservation policy introduced in Nepal, share of women in civil service only 11%. Shares of Dalit, Muslim and disabled were virtually almost zero. Adivasi/Janajatis, Madhesis and Khas/Arya of remote area people had slightly higher shares. Further while analyzing the female's participation in Nepalese Civil Service, it was remarkably low participation of women in terms of population portion. In 2003, overall 8 percent of the women has been participated in civil service examination. Likewise, they were 15 percent in 2010 and 18 percent in 2015. In 2076/077 (2020), after 12 years of implementation of reservation system the shares of women in civil service is increased to 25.76% and shares of Adivasi/Janajatis, Madhesi's, Dalit, Muslim, disabled and remote area's people is also moderately accumulating in terms of numerical representation in the civil service of Nepal.

Based on the sequential explanatory study done to shows that among 130 respondents, above 85% agree that the principle of proportional representation and participation is fully ensured in the civil service and remaining respondents disagree about it. Perception of respondents was collected and measured by using Likert scale measurement. The survey shows that nearly all the respondents agree that disadvantage group feel to be included in the mainstream into the civil service in Nepal. Along with it, all the respondents agree that the targeted group have been able to utilize the opportunities provided in the civil service act and the constitution has guarantees equal opportunity to employment for all people and avoids discrimination. In case of perception towards the reservation, more than 70% of the respondents agree that male

has more superiority complex and negative attitudes towards female. It means that the male has more superiority complex and negative attitudes towards female. Similarly, 85% of the respondents agree that special arrangement for male friendly are absent in the organization environment. Finally, the majority of the respondents i.e. above 80% disagree about the people from reservation are not capable to delivering the quality service in comparison with other people in workplace whereas 19% agree about it.

Individual Effects:

This study scrutinizes that the individual effects of reservation system which consists of how the respondents perceive about an individual understanding, educational schooling, confidence, personal values and beliefs, attentions, and potentials, and attraction towards the civil service, which are regarded as strong determining relationship to achieve the personal desired targets in the public organizations of Nepal. In this regards, the bivariate analysis of individual effects of reservation for the inclusiveness shows that there is less significant relationship between the individual representation and individual perception with inclusiveness of civil service. As the calculated values of representativeness chi square is 13.942 and $p=.124$ and calculated values of perception chi square is 10.494 and $p=.312$ which shows less significant with inclusive civil service. And, analysis of individual effects of reservation for the inclusiveness shows that there is highly significant relationship between the individual participation and individual performance with the inclusiveness of civil service. As the calculated values of participation chi square is 27.511 and $p=.001$ and calculated values of performance chi square is 32.056 and $p=.000$ which shows highly significant relation with the inclusive civil service. Therefore, we can conclude that there is high relationship between individual effects of reservation system and inclusiveness of civil service of Nepal.

Organizational Effects:

In the study, the organizational factor refers to the Office structure, working channel, rule and process, performance challenges and evaluation, motivation, coordination, leadership, responsibility, support, decision making and the satisfaction level of respondents towards the organization after the application of reservation system in Nepal. The findings of the survey show that, there was highly significant relationship between organizational effects of reservation system for the inclusiveness and the

variable of representativeness and participation in civil service of Nepal. In the bivariate analysis, the calculated value of representation chi square is 33.0715 and $p=.000$ and calculated values of participation chi square is 50.313 and $p=.000$ and which shows highly significant relationship of independent variables with the inclusive civil service. The organizational effects of reservation for the perception and performance shows that there is less significant relationship with the inclusiveness of civil service of Nepal. Therefore, we can conclude that there is high relationship between organizational effects of reservation system and inclusiveness of civil service of Nepal.

The major over-all findings are disclosed as below;

- As an effect of reservation policy, shares of women, Adivasi/Janajati, Madhesi, Dalit, disabled and people from backward areas are gradually accumulating in civil service.
- The dominance of Khas-Arya people in civil service is declining in the last 12 years. Furthermore, the inclusive civil service which has been the concern for all people of Nepal definitely brings a positive transformation in the socio-cultural thought.
- The meaningful inclusion of diverse social, caste, cultural, religious, ethnic, gender groups and regions has made government employment services more equitable and accessible to diverse communities, and sense of recognition, participation and ownership is increasing towards civil service among these marginalized communities.
- There is a generous biasness between the beneficiaries from free competition and reservation whereas the unseen role of the elder officers in creating this environment. That's why, there is a prevalence of sympathetic discrimination existing in workplace due to lack of tactfulness of performance of the beneficiaries from reservation in the uncooperative environment causing threat in the process of social inclusion in Nepal.
- Ministry of Women, Children and Social Welfare, various commissions and institutions are now running coaching classes to help women and people from marginalized communities to join civil service. But these opportunities are very limited and unplanned to Kathmandu and other cities, and beyond the reach of socio-culturally and economically targeted and outreached people.

- The practice of approving strategically programs and allocating budget for them in the spirit of reservation, positive discrimination and gender friendly funding is increasing.
- The segregated seats reserved for women, Adivasi/Janajati, Madhesi and Dalit are actually reserved for socially and economically backward women and Adivasi/Janajati, Madhesi and Dalit. But the state has not still prepared the clear bounded criteria to identify socially and economically disadvantaged women, Adivasi/Janajati, Madhesi and Dalits. As a result, the real goals of inclusion in Nepal has not been accomplished.
- As an effect of reservation policy, reasonable recognition and participation of women and marginalized communities is somehow increasing while share and dominance of Khas/Arya is declining. Therefore, those communities whose dominance is on the balance seem to have launched initial campaign of mainstreaming and the issue of merit is mostly announcing through the support of social media to depreciate those women and marginalized people who have joined civil service through reserved quotas.

Therefore, this study shows that the measurable and reliable indicators of inclusive civil service of Nepal which has the equitable opportunity for representativeness, participation and mainstreaming of the target group for the positive changes and cultural friendly organizational environment. In order to enhance the recognize and representation of disadvantaged groups of society in civil service of Nepal, there could be several short term policies, programs, strategies, targeted and specialized projects, conferences, financial subsidies, tuition and coaching classes, awareness programs, empowerment schemes to guardians and relatives of original aspirant candidates and equal access and intuition of opportunities to needy applicants, decentralized exam centers, gender and disability friendly placement and working environment and equitable recruitment. There should be such programs that can bring about the major changes in socio-economic and socio-cultural perception particularly in the context of mutual awareness, psychological empowerment and behavioral cooperation in the rural environment. There might be several options to uplift the participation of marginalized groups of Nepalese society in the civil service such as gender sensitive public policies, amendments in the acts to make marginalization friendly, advocacy, and placement. Socialization and working environment, capacity building, awareness projects,

orientation and opportunities like training, practical workshops, motivational seminars, learning opportunities, capacity development activities and change oriented efforts.

Therefore, my research determination was not to advocate whether reservation system is good or bad. I have explained what the policymakers, implementers, beneficiaries and other people expecting in the society that have perceived regarding the implementation of reservation system in Civil Service of Nepal, and at the same time I also explored what the effects and current position of the implementation is and what the tendency of inclusion in Civil Service if Nepal is. Unless and until the individuals and group of people perceive the policy positively, the implementation part cannot give a sound output and consequence. In other words, the attitude of stakeholders regarding policy highly affect the practice. Therefore, my focal ambition of the research is to examine the policy effects and practical obstacles of reservation policy in Civil Service along with the deep understanding and commitment of how all the stakeholders have perceived the reservation policy in Nepal.

5.3 Conclusion of the Study

For the conclusion, the effects of the reservation policy is imposing the social, cultural, ethnic, economic and regional diversity reflection in civil service of Nepal. Historical dominance of one caste group in civil service is gradually balancing with other disadvantaged people. The participation of women and disadvantaged people in civil service is gradually increasing after the application of reservation system. When the civil service becomes more inclusive, government services have become more accessible to diverse communities, and sense of their ownership towards civil service is increasing. For this, proportional representation of all communities in state organs including civil service is the key to recognition, participation and overall inclusive consideration. This is the purpose of recent political changes, and this ideal has been reinforced by the constitution and several international laws endorsed by the Nepal.

Therefore, the reservation policy is being more popular and scientific, and the state must prepare acts/laws regarding policy to strengthen relations between the nation and marginalized communities with conducive environment. And all the respondents agree that the targeted group have been able to utilize the opportunities provided in the civil service act and the constitution has guarantees equal opportunity to employment for all people and avoids discrimination. Whereas 85% of the respondents agree that special

arrangement for male friendly are absent in the organization environment. According to crosstab analysis, the individual effects of reservation for the inclusiveness shows that there is highly significant relationship between the individual participation and individual performance with the inclusiveness of civil service. An organizational effects of reservation system for the inclusiveness shows that there is highly significant relationship with the representativeness and participation in civil service of Nepal. It has the positive impacts in civil service elsewhere Nepal's affirmative action policy is not free from criticism. Critics suggest that reservation has benefitted women and men from the privileged castes and ethnic backgrounds, and thus women and men from rural areas of underprivileged caste/ethnic groups are still excluded. While there is lack of a multi-year analysis of beneficiaries of women reservation by caste, ethnicity and disability, preliminary evidences suggest that women from the privileged social groups have benefitted more than others.

In 2015, 48 out of 50 women officers recruited under reservation seats for three civil service sectors administrative, revenues and accounting belonged to Brahmin and Chhetri. In comparison to the major caste representing in civil service Hill Brahmin, Chhetri, Indigenous and Newar, the real target group of inclusion of Hill and Terai minorities and marginalized representation are still very low in number. Positive discriminatory measures have not been worked out for candidates who come from highly marginalized communities, Dalits (from both Hills and Terai) and the communities. The objectivity of the reservation system had been promoting of the economically and socially backward communities, corrective measures are needed to control the dominant caste group utilizing the quota system in civil service of Nepal.

Finally, the policy has been made by top down approach according to which it is very difficult to empathize with the native characteristics of the real targeted people. It would rather much better if the bottom-up approach is followed. I have also realized that if there is lacking the proper understanding for the phenomenon of social inclusion, this may cause negative impact on the society instead of bringing about a harmonious change after all. The need of educational trainings and applicable infrastructures related to attitude change and development of anti-discriminatory thought in every level of Civil servants has been realized the sense of humanity, respect and coexistence of other through reservation policy. The quota system or reservation (Aarakshan) has become

popular as well as controversial in public discourse due to lack of proper education in the public level. Multiple understanding of reservation policy is found from person to person. However, in totality, the concept can be taken in regards of process of providing equal access of opportunity of the reach of diverse groups in the process of mainstreaming with the feeling of a social right and justice in order to widen their reasonable participation and enhance their overall empowerment. Also, from sociological perspective, it has been visualized as the anti-marginalization process that will bring social change gradually through individual, national and societal levels.

Way Forward for Reservation Policy in Civil Service of Nepal

Nepal's new constitution considered social inclusion and proportional representation as one of the guiding principles for the future vision, mission and goal of nation. So there is no alternative to making Nepal's civil service more inclusive, more representative and more competent. For this to happen, the state must undertake following measures:

- The reservation policy must be employed in the spirit of the Civil Service Act by clearly identifying socio-economically deprived classes and ethnic communities.
- There must have effective analysis of data, information and shares of people belonging to diverse gender, ethnic communities, class and regions in civil service.
- The Government of Nepal must have a strategically plans and programs with details of which ethnic communities, gender, class and regions can be represented and competitively empowered in future civil service in proportion of their populations.
- The preparation of focal coaching classes must be conducted to empower socially and economically marginalized ethnic communities, gender, class and regions to attract and join civil service of Nepal to empathize the feeling of recognition.
- The Government of Nepal must guarantee that once a person has been benefitted from reservation/reservation policy will not get reserved benefit for another time.
- The empowerment structures and programs for socially and economically outreached communities must be incorporated in annual budget and periodic plans.

5.4 Scope for the Future Research

The study recommends that further research be conducted using a longer series to assess the impact of the reservation policy on the employment of the designated groups in public administration positions. The study would benefit by disaggregating data according to the different categories of designated group, such as rural women and disadvantaged people with whose representation is still out of coverage of affirmation action and inclusion. The research is conducted for academic purpose and is done within the limited scope and time. Along with it, the research primarily focus is on the perception analysis of the civil servants towards the reservation system. But, the perceptions have been generalized with the limited respondents taking as key samples. Therefore, the overall scenario of the perception had somehow not reflected in the study by ignoring other types of respondents like technical services, health service as well as other officers of public enterprise organizations due to various limitation as mention earlier in chapter first. Besides above reasons, inclusiveness of civil service itself is very vague relationships and covers the several dimensions. So, it is definitely unfair to compare of inclusiveness with only the perceptions or attitudinal changes of the respondents. For this purpose, one of the best ways may be to make comparison between different services at different levels and also by including the officials of the private and public enterprises sector organizations too. Therefore, the future research can be directed towards covering the others dimensions of the inclusiveness as well as while doing the perception analysis, the sample size should be large and nearing covering all the marginalized group prescribed by the Civil Service Act of Nepal.

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Appendix 1: Questionnaire

Tribhuvan University

Faculty of Management,

Central Department of Public Administration, Kathmandu, Nepal

"Effects of Reservation Policy for the Inclusive Civil Service of Nepal"

(A) Individual Form of Key Respondent

1) General Information:

Date: 207.../...../....

Name:

Age:

Post/Level:

Service/Group:

Gender:

Appointed Date:

Name of your Organization:

2) Educational Qualification:

a. PCL/10+2 b) Bachelor c) Masters d) M.Phil./PH. D

3) Description of Respondents;

a) Age Coverage: Below 35 Year Above 35 Year

b) Belongs Community: Open Reserved

If Reserved: i. Women ii. Janajati iii. Madhesi

iv. Dalit v. Disables vi. Remote Area

4) Who firstly encourage you to enter civil service of Nepal?

a. Family b) Friends c) Relatives d) Teachers

5) Do you think that the reservation system has the very positive effects to mainstream the socio-economically marginalized people into civil service of Nepal?

a. Yes b. No c. Don't Know

6) How is the role of reservation policy for the inclusive civil service of Nepal?

a. Very Good c. Not Good

b. Good d. Don't Know

7) What is the level of educational background of your guardian/parents have?

a. Illiterate c. SLC/Equal

b. Literate d. Higher Degree

Appendix 1: Questionnaire

Group B: (A) Representativeness

Q. N.	Question Do you agree that..... <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Options/Coding			
		Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1)	The Constitution of Nepal-2015, ensure that more opportunities to women and disadvantaged group into governance of Nepal.	1	2	3	4
2)	The reservation policy is only one alternative to mainstream of women and disadvantaged people into the civil service of Nepal.	1	2	3	4
3)	The reservation policy has been playing crucial role in promoting social justice of the women and disadvantaged people of Nepal.	1	2	3	4
4)	The reservation policy has been building the foundation of balancing equality and equity for stimulating social integration of targeted people.	1	2	3	4
5)	The actions of positive discrimination is unable to recover the highly disadvantaged people of Nepal.	1	2	3	4

(B) Participation

Q. N.	Question Do you agree that.....	Options/Coding			
		Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
6)	Women and marginalized people don't have sufficient participation in the Nepalese civil service according to their total population size.	1	2	3	4
7)	The increasing numbers of marginalized people is enhancing the sense of their recognition and ownership into the civil service of Nepal.	1	2	3	4
8)	Women and disadvantaged people participation increase the voice of voiceless and develop the new diversified ideas into civil service of Nepal.	1	2	3	4
9)	The changing environment with unprivileged people into civil service is changing the employee friendly infrastructure into your organization.	1	2	3	4
10)	The participation of women and reserved people is leading the application of inclusiveness and belongingness in civil service.	1	2	3	4

(C) Perception

Q. N.	Question Do you agree that.....	Options/Coding			
		Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
11)	The dominance of upper class Khas/Arya male employees is reducing and balancing after the acting of reservation system into the civil service.	1	2	3	4
12)	The old age civil servants are biased of having and supporting the employees from reserved quota in your public organization of civil service of Nepal.	1	2	3	4
13)	The people from reservation are biased to utilize minimum resource and facilities regarding their position and professions in the workplace.	1	2	3	4
14)	Family relation and caste belongingness differs the behavior in the workplace that discourage the lower caste civil servants.	1	2	3	4
15)	The Government of Nepal should continue the reservation system implementation for one another decade to recover the targeted potential people.	1	2	3	4

Appendix 1: Questionnaire

(D) Performance

Q. N.	Question Do you agree that..... <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Options/Coding			
		Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
16)	The people from the reservation are still not regarding the key actor in decision making and top positions like CDO and CAO.	1	2	3	4
17)	Male civil servants have more superiority complex and negative attitudes in workplace towards female regarding information sharing about the service.	1	2	3	4
18)	The people from reservation are not capable to delivering the quality service in comparison with other people in workplace.	1	2	3	4
19)	The potentials and possibilities of energetic reserved employees are somehow not motivated to explore and implement their action in public organizations	1	2	3	4
20)	Very low performance and bad experiences exist with the service seekers from reservation facilitated employees.	1	2	3	4
21)	Male civil servants are more risk taker and optimistic to settle down the emergency difficulties than female civil servants	1	2	3	4

(E) Individual Effects

Q. N.	Question Do you agree that.....	Options/Coding			
		Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
22)	The reservation facilitated civil servants are not that much confident to take responsibilities rather than other employees.	1	2	3	4
23)	The reservation facilitated civil servants are more absent and not interested to provide public service rather than other employees.	1	2	3	4
24)	Special subsidies and facilities for female and disable civil servants are more absent in the office environment.	1	2	3	4
25)	The result merit of PSC can measure the quality of performance in the field of desired public employees.	1	2	3	4
26)	The PSC examinations and process of selection are capable of determining merit of competent candidates.	1	2	3	4
27)	The opportunities provided by your public organization are fair enough to enhance your skills and potentials.	1	2	3	4

(F) Organizational Effects

Q. N.	Question Do you agree that.....	Options/Coding			
		Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
28)	The reservation system is a main interruption for safeguarding general standard of merit in civil service.	1	2	3	4
29)	Male are good learner, adjustable and decision maker than female employees in the civil service of Nepal.	1	2	3	4
30)	The working space, working channel and working pattern are male friendly in your public organization.	1	2	3	4
31)	The working pattern of civil service is biased which is obstacles to deliver motivated service particularly for the women and disadvantaged employees in Nepal.	1	2	3	4
32)	The reservation system helps to explore more diversity and more ideas from different socio-cultural employees.	1	2	3	4

Appendix 2: Interview Guideline

Name of the participants:	
Address:	
Academic qualification:	
Name of Office:	
Date:	

Guidelines: (Please Write in Small Handwriting without Crossing Next Question)

1. What are the major reasons for applying reservation policy in government service of Nepal?
.....
2. What is the previous & present condition with the provision of inclusion of civil service of Nepal?
.....
3. What is the condition of motivation towards and participation of isolated people in civil service?
.....
4. What are the main contributions of reservation system for changing the civil service of Nepal?
.....
5. Do you think that reservation system application hampers the standard of merit in civil service?
.....
6. Reaction from friends and colleagues while recruiting from reservation in civil service of Nepal
.....
7. How is the condition of working opportunities for the performance to quota facilitated people?
.....
8. What do you think that government doesn't believe to give them in chief/ leading role and position?
.....
9. In which level of civil service you are working and how many of you are in decision making level?
.....
10. What are the expected/positive and unexpected/negative effects of reservation system in Nepal?
.....
11. Any good or bad experiences with the beneficent from quota facilitated employees in Office.
.....
12. How long time the reservation policy should practice more in the Nepalese public bureaucracy?
.....